

Just observing a fellow human being can inspire us to strive for the same goal as the other person. In social-cognitive research this effect is known as "goal contagion". Here, several experiments are presented testing this effect with prosocial goals and the goal to earn money. However, the author and his collaborators did not find any evidence for goal contagion. Moreover, they show that the published literature on goal contagion is biased towards statistically significant results.

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*From Observation to Inspiration?
Why the Goal-Contagion Effect is Overestimated.*

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A Personal Prologue and Acknowledgements

Scientific findings and another person's life story have something in common: when reading or hearing about them from other people, these stories seem to be clean and straightforward endeavors. For instance, when you read a classic academic paper in psychology, usually all studies fit well together to form a coherent package that supports the theorizing from beginning to end. Similarly, when people tell something from their past or describe their professional life in a letter of motivation, all the steps they took and career choices they made in their life seem to be logically fitting. None of this was true for me.

When it comes to my working life and education until now, I did not plan to do experiments in social psychology. After high school, I actually wanted to become a journalist, but failed to meet the requirements for the bachelor's program. Instead, I studied political science, sociology and peace studies in my hometown Halle and later in Frankfurt/Main in Germany. Back then in 2007 to 2012, I did not even know what social psychology entailed or how it could be different from psychotherapy (something that is also true for anyone outside academia).

What I knew, however, was that I liked it when in popular scientific books that I read at the time – such as in Steven Pinker's "The better angels of our nature" (2011) or Jonathan Haidt's "The righteous mind" (2012) – the authors sometimes reported lab experiments involving human participants to support their arguments about how the mind works or people interact. In late 2012, after a semester abroad in Oslo, I decided

to figure out where I could do these kinds of lab experiments, preferably in a master's program.

After some internships, I concluded that I could not find any suitable program in Germany, where the next closest thing probably was psychology, which required a bachelor's degree in this field. Nevertheless, in 2013 I could luckily enroll in the program "Social and Behavioral Sciences", which included a major in Social Psychology at Tilburg University in the Netherlands. Little did I know that my interest in lab experiments would be shaken soon after.

Around the same time, I enrolled there, Tilburg University received some media attention, but in the least positive way. One of their rising star professors in social and behavioral sciences, Diederik Stapel, falsified most of his research for decades and got caught by some of his own PhD students. Moreover, the whole field stumbled into a crisis of non-replicable research findings showing that many studies seemed to be unreliable, sparking the "replication crisis". This is what I learned from my teachers and peers in Tilburg. That was also why the master's program had a heavy focus on two aspects of research that I had hardly ever paid attention to: solid methods and open science.

Rather by accident, I was thrown into a program that taught me how important sample size, statistical power and adequate statistical tests (solid methods) were, and how study preregistration (registration of a hypothesis and analysis plan before any data is collected) and the sharing of methods, data and code (open science) would make my research better. Wow – that was certainly not what I was signing up for. However, the more I got involved, the more I appreciated it – also due

to my great teachers, like Mark Brandt, Wilco Emons, Tony Evans, Hans IJzerman, Marcel van Assen, and Marcel Zeelenberg.

After my graduation, there was another unexpected turn. Instead of ending up at a German university, it was the social psychology section at the University of Graz in Austria that called me back after my application. The job ad read that Katja Corcoran, the professor of this section, wanted a research assistant for a project on a certain social-cognitive effect.

Initially, I was not sure about this project because social-cognitive effects were the ones that we had learned in Tilburg about being prime examples of the above-mentioned non-replicable and unreliable findings. However, my parents convinced me that I should not dismiss an opportunity like this. After all, I felt that Katja and the people that I already got in contact with – Gaya (Katja’s postdoc), Lisa (my potential future colleague), and Dagmar (our secretary), seemed to be really kind and supportive. I gave it a try.

I moved to Graz in early 2016 in the naive mindset that the replication crisis was a hot and popular topic all over the discipline – in not only the social and behavioral sciences, but also potentially in all the adjacent fields, such as cognitive psychology, biological psychology, organizational psychology, or developmental psychology. Indeed, Katja, Lisa and I talked openly about all these issues and importance of solid methods and open science from the beginning on. But when I approached researchers from other areas, I did not get the impression that many of them paid much attention to the crisis. Even the diagnostic methods department was rather

involved in its own research and did not seem to follow the recent developments.

Given that the replication crisis did not have such an impact in Graz, I started to underestimate its importance for the first couple of months, which reflected on my own research. The first few experiments that we ran were not preregistered, and we did not document data and code properly either. The practical test of how research should really be done proved to be difficult for me: although I had learned about it in theory, I did not fully embrace it in reality. There was room for improvement.

However, by the end of the first year of my PhD in 2016, our section had made considerable progress. We used online repositories for our research more and more effectively, and taught about open science in front of bachelor students, master students and even PhD students. Now, more than three years later, I am even happy to promote open science outside of my section eagerly.

This brings me to the second thing that typically does not yield straightforward and clean stories, namely scientific findings. I learned this quickly, when my collaborators and I investigated the goal-contagion effect, which is the topic of this dissertation.

When people ask me, what I am doing for my PhD, I typically start with: “Do you know the movie ‘Inception’, where people try to implant an idea in someone else’s mind without this person being aware of it? This is essentially what I am doing.” Then, I usually get an excited, but confused look, sometimes accompanied by a “But... How?”

I then continue: “Well, we actually do not enter people’s minds. Rather, we have participants watch other people doing something. For instance, they watch a video showing someone jogging in a park. Then we measure whether they get inspired to also do sports.” I would then get a less excited look, accompanied by: “Oh, okay. And how do you measure how they got inspired?”

I would say, “In different ways. Sometimes we just ask them about their motivation, sometimes, we look whether they got more attentive towards sports-related words. You know, like ‘football’, ‘racket’, ‘sprint’ or ‘squat.’” – “But don’t people like very different kinds of sports... if they like sports at all?” – “Well, that’s true, but we try to account for these things in our methods and statistics.” – “Ehm, okay.”

Then I have to fight for not losing them by quickly wrapping it up: “To make it short: We did not find that people get inspired that easily by just observing others.” – “Oh, you don’t?” – “Nope, no inspiration there.”

This is really what we found throughout our research. We started out quite optimistically. After all, many published research findings presented evidence for this effect. First, we tried to create similar (but not identical) experiments, where we expected to find the basic goal-contagion effect with prosocial goals and sports-related goals, which we then wanted to connect to social-comparison processes (see <https://osf.io/9q5h4/>). As we did not find this effect in earlier experiments, we invited Henk Aarts, the first author of the first goal-contagion paper, and he kindly helped us create a research design.

By the beginning of the second year of my PhD, we used this research design for a line of experiments that resembled early studies on goal contagion with the goal of “earning money”. Importantly, we did not conduct our main experiments yet, as we made use of the new registered report article format that some journals offered, which has the potential to revolutionize research in our domain.

Usually, researchers submit their articles when everything is done; theory, methods and results are all written down and discussed. The article is then sent out to a journal for a peer-review. Different to these conventional article formats, a registered report contains theory, hypotheses, and a statistical plan, but does not contain results for the main study, as the data collection only starts after peer-review of the initial research plan that is presented.

The advantage here is that reviewers will not be inclined to evaluate a paper based on the results (reviewer: “Oh, the results show the exact effect that was theorized, that’s great!”), but based on the theory and methods alone (reviewer: “Yes, given this theoretical reasoning and that experimental design, they should be able to find that effect.”). Also, researchers are less inclined to please the reviewers when they write up results that are inconsistent with the initial theorizing and change their hypotheses post hoc, which was common practice before 2011 (researcher: “Oh no, we will never get these results published in this form. Wasn’t there a theory that could explain these results better? Let’s look it up!”).

Yes, registered reports can be considered a blessing for the sciences. I started appreciating them a lot as they also

corresponded well to the open science practices that we initiated in Graz.

While the registered-report manuscript was under a longer review process, we decided to do a meta-analysis on the goal-contagion effect in the third year of my PhD. For this kind of analysis, one has to systematically scan the literature to identify all effects of one kind (in our case the goal contagion effect). The results are then summarized to one overall effect. Although this overall effect should be theoretically more precise than effects from single studies, it could also be biased through studies that were published because the reviewers liked the results (called “publication bias”).

To illustrate this problem, imagine a teacher, who has to formally report the average grade for her course at the end of the school year: it would make a huge difference, if she decides to report all the pupils’ scores, including the ones that failed the course, or decided to only report the average for the pupils who passed (i.e., received over 50%). The latter case represents the current state of the publishing system in some way.

It also represents the effect that we found in the meta-analysis for goal contagion. There was an overall goal-contagion effect, but it seemed to be biased towards “positive” results. In reality, this effect might be much closer to zero.

Moreover, once we collected all the data for our registered report and analyzed it throughout the fourth year of my PhD, we saw that these results turned out to be null results. This is what we almost expected, given the meta-analysis we had done the previous year.

People sometimes ask me if these results frustrate me. My answer is that they do not. There are two main reasons why I am relaxed about these results. First, they are overshadowed by my feeling that we did an overall good job on the methodological side. We made use of what I learned about in Tilburg: solid methods and open science. Something that is incredibly satisfying in hindsight.

The second reason is that the way we got to these results was a collaborative learning process for the whole lab that I am grateful to be part of. Discussing with these people on everything that is science-related was at least as insightful as my many searches through statistics books and papers, as well as internet forums. I therefore want to thank all these people: my supervisor Katja Corcoran, who pushed me softly to become more structured in my work and who was always supportive for any kind of research idea, teaching concept or conference I wanted to attend; my colleague Lisa Eckerstorfer for keeping a good balance between work and fun in the office; our secretary Dagmar Schmelzer for dealing with almost all of the formalities; Ursula Athenstaedt and Gayannée Kedia (both of which I also did side projects with), who always gave valuable input and heated up the discussions; Silvia Macher who gave great support for the statistical analyses; Christoph Anzengruber and Andreas Höfler, without their technical know-how there would not have been any lab experiment possible; our many student assistants, who did the “dirty work” of data collection, like Jasmin Rainer (from whom I got my first flat in Graz), Robert Spörk, Larissa Titze, Edda Pavalec, Marlies Brunnhofer, and Elija Dentler.

There are way too many people outside our own lab, who were more or less involved in this project, but who deserve to be mentioned. I want to thank Gaby Hofer and the people from the Graz Open Science Initiative, without whom I would probably not do as much open science as I do today; Robbie van Aert and Marcel van Assen, who elevated my meta-analysis to the next level; Esther Maassen for checking this prologue; my former girlfriend Feliz Macahis for listening to me talk about all the things that went well and wrong; the bouldering crew (including Christopher Schneider) and the board game crew who helped me clear my mind around weekends.

Finally, I want to thank my parents Monika and Eberhard for being on my side throughout all these years. Although mostly on Skype, they were much more emotionally involved in this process than one would imagine.

Abstract

English version

From Observation to Inspiration? Why the Goal-Contagion Effect is Overestimated

Just observing a fellow human being can inspire us to strive for the same goal as the other person. Such goal contagion has been shown to occur because one first automatically infers the goal on an implicit level and then adopts it for oneself (Aarts, Gollwitzer, & Hassin, 2004). In this dissertation, my collaborators and I investigated this goal contagion effect in three studies on prosocial goals (total $N = 659$) and another three studies, including one registered report, on the goal to earn money (total $N = 840$). We also accounted for the theoretically derived moderators' effort to pursue the goal (by the observed person) and goal value (for the participants). Across all experiments, participants either read a brief story or saw video clips of a person who either wanted to pursue a goal (experimental conditions) or not (control condition). We hypothesized that high effort increases goal inference, whereas personal goal value strengthens the relationship between goal inference and goal adoption (i.e., work to earn money). Results of our analyses using structural equation models showed that participants indeed recognized the goal explicitly, but our implicit measure did not detect a goal inference and there was no effect of the moderators. Moreover, we did not find evidence that participants in the experimental condition would adopt the goal to earn money more often than participants in the control condition, despite our high-powered designs. These results were then embedded into a meta-analysis,

summarizing the effects of goal contagion across the social-psychological literature. This meta-analysis showed a large discrepancy between a considerable effect from the published literature Hedges' $g = 0.42$, and a null-effect from the unpublished literature (including our own studies), $g = -0.01$, indicating publication bias. To prevent this in the future, we suggest that new studies on goal contagion should make use of open science practices.

German Version

Werden wir inspiriert, wenn wir andere beobachten? Warum der Effekt der Zielansteckung überschätzt ist

Die bloße Beobachtung einer Tätigkeit einer anderen Person kann uns manchmal dazu inspirieren, das gleiche Ziel wie diese zu verfolgen. Dieser Effekt der Zielansteckung setzt voraus, dass wir das Ziel zunächst aus dem Verhalten der anderen Person automatisch ableiten, bevor wir es übernehmen (Aarts, Gollwitzer & Hassin, 2004). In dieser Dissertation haben meine KollegInnen und ich dieses Phänomen in einer Reihe von Studien untersucht: in drei Studien mit 659 ProbandInnen versuchten wir prosoziale Ziele zu aktivieren; in drei weiteren Studien für einen Registered Report mit 840 ProbandInnen, versuchten wir das Ziel Geld zu verdienen zu aktivieren. In allen Studien beschrieben oder zeigten wir ein Verhalten einer anderen Person in Texten oder kurzen Videos. Dieses Verhalten implizierte entweder das konkrete Ziel (Experimentalbedingung) oder nicht (Kontrollbedingung). Innerhalb des Zielansteckungsprozesses vermuteten wir verschiedene Moderatoren: das Bemühen der anderen Person ihr Ziel zu erreichen, sollte die erfolgreiche Ableitung fördert, und der persönliche Wert des Zieles (für den/die ProbandIn) sollte die Übernahme des Zieles fördern. Für die Analyse nutzten wir Strukturgleichungsmodelle, um alle relevanten Variablen einzubinden. Die Ergebnisse zeigten, dass ProbandInnen das Ziel nicht implizit und automatisch ableiteten. Wir fanden auch keine Belege für eine stärkere Zielübernahme in der Experimentalgruppe im Vergleich zur

Kontrollgruppe und keinen Moderatoreinfluss. Diese Ergebnisse bettetten wir in eine Metaanalyse ein, in welcher wir die Evidenz zur Zielansteckung über die gesamte Literatur zusammentrugen. Eine starke Diskrepanz zwischen beträchtlichen Effekten in der publizierten Literatur (Hedges' $g = 0.42$) und Effekten nahe Null in der nicht-publizierten Literatur, inklusive unserer Studien ($g = -0.01$), legt eine Publikationsverzerrung nahe. Daher empfehlen wir, dass zukünftige Studien zur Zielansteckung von offenen Wissenschaftspraktiken Gebrauch machen.

Chapter 1

**General Introduction:
Goals, Inferences and
Goal Contagion**

Pursuing goals in everyday life is something that we do naturally. Sometimes we pursue goals after deliberate planning – for instance, when we organize an upcoming holiday trip. And often we do it intuitively, for example, when we execute daily routines such as getting our meal from the fridge, booting the computer in the office or even reading a book like you – the reader – are doing at this very moment. It is not even controversial to say that holding and pursuing goals is an existential part of a living being (Zech, 2018). However, although we know from daily observations that people pursue goals, it is less clear how and under which conditions these goals come into being on a cognitive level.

To be sure, much research has been done on goals throughout the last decades within the field of social cognition to find answers to this question (e.g. Bargh, Gollwitzer, Lee-Chai, Barndollar, & Trötschel, 2001; Shah & Kruglanski, 2002; Aarts, Custers, & Veltkamp, 2008). A crucial focus of the research on goals has been to what degree they could be activated in people when they see others pursuing the same goals. Potentially, observers could get “inspired” to also start pursuing the observed goal without being aware of it initially. For instance, after casually seeing a jogger in the park, one could be more inclined to also do sports later that day. Evidence on this so-called “goal contagion” effect (Aarts, Hassin, & Gollwitzer, 2005) accumulated over the years (e.g., Dik & Aarts, 2007; Loersch, Aarts, Payne, & Jefferis, 2008; Leander & Shah, 2013). That is, more and more research found that people pursue goals, or at least have them activated in their mind, after recognizing them in the behavior of others.

Notably, this research in the domain of goals was paralleled by another, more fundamental, development in the whole field, which put several of the older social-psychological findings into question. This development started out as the “Replication Crisis” when it turned out that many older studies would not replicate if they were redone by independent research teams (Open Science Collaboration, 2015). This is problematic because the accumulation of knowledge and generation of new theories usually requires replicable findings for inductive reasoning. Only if evidence is sufficiently provided for one hypothesis, should one continue to test new hypotheses that build on top of the established finding (see Chambers, 2017). Recently, the crisis has shifted into a “Credibility Revolution” (Vazire, 2018), as awareness among researchers increased that more transparent and open research practices, which were not a given in most older studies and experiments, are required to reestablish credibility in the findings of the field. Moreover, researchers started testing a specific effect thoroughly and repeatedly before proceeding in their research.

Naturally, this development influenced the present research on the goal contagion effect: Research from before the crisis suggested that observed goals can be “contagious” and that observers start pursuing these goals as well. As described above, this effect should be secured in further studies before one sets out to build new research on top of it. Hence, the goal of this dissertation was to primarily test the goal contagion effect accounting for these developments by applying open science practices.

Before I give an overview of my research, I want to provide a definition of “goals.” I want to approach the meaning of goals from a broad social-cognitive perspective, followed by a description of how the goal-directed behavior of others can influence us. These elaborations will provide the theoretical underpinnings for the later chapters.

What are Goals?

In general, goals can be seen as mental representations of desired end states for an individual, which can be achieved through action (Kruglanski & Kopitz, 2009). The term “desired end state” implies a discrepancy between the situational is and the pictured ideal: there is a state that is more beneficial to the individual than the current one (Carver & Scheier, 1981). If the individual acts through controlled action, e.g., by physically approaching beneficial things or avoiding harmful things in their environment (see Elliot & Harackiewicz, 1996), they can actually change the discrepancy to achieve the pictured ideal (Custers & Aarts, 2005; Kruglanski, 1996; for a more nuanced approach through self-discrepancy theory, see Higgins, 1987).

Early after birth in a human being’s ontogenesis, there are not many ideals to achieve apart from those revolving around most basic needs (see Maslow, 1943), such as eating and drinking, excretion, sleeping and parental care and cuddles. However, this quickly changes throughout the human development and later in life it will be important to organize different and more complex goals and activities, such as doing homework, playing video games, doing sports or doing the

chores. Often, these goals require coordination with others (Tomasello, 2014, Chapter 3).

Different social aspects determine our goals or our goal pursuit. First, human beings learn from early on to understand and interpret intentions of other people for collaborative or joint goals: toddlers already understand the difference between individual goals (e.g., “I want to build this tower of wooden blocks”) and shared intentions to achieve a goal (e.g., “We both want to build this tower together”; see Tomasello, 2019, Chapter 2). Second, humans often adjust their behavior towards prosocial goals to help others in both everyday situations and emergency cases (e.g., Batson et al., 1981; Amato, 1990; Batson et al., 2007). Third, certain goals of humans can be determined by their cultural group and hierarchies within this group. In this respect, adhering to cultural norms to avoid punishment can be a goal (Fehr & Gächter, 2002; Nook et al., 2016; Silk & House, 2016), or working hard to gain more socio-economic status can be another (Elliot & Thrash, 2001; Srivastava, Locke, & Bartol, 2001). The point here is that other people play a crucial role in our daily decisions for goal-oriented behavior.

As human cognition seems to be so dependent on others, it is conceivable that others’ behaviors can also affect our cognitive processes on a less conscious level. But what are the underlying cognitive processes that make us decide which goal is important and should be pursued? How will these different goals be activated? These questions are addressed in the following.

Associative Networks and a System of Goals

At face value, goals seem to be similar to semantic concepts or mere cognitive representations of other things in our mind. After all, goals that a person seeks to achieve can be conceptualized as nodes in associative networks that are connected to related semantic concepts and also to goal-related behavioral concepts (Fiedler, 2018). In order to cognitively activate a concept, the person has to be “prepared,” which is often achieved via priming.

For instance, a semantic prime for an observer, that is the indirect confrontation with concepts through word grids or word completion tasks, might cognitively activate a respective concept in the semantic network, eliciting a cascade of initially more closely – later less closely – related concepts (Neely, 1977). These connected concepts can also include behavioral representations, which might prepare the observer for action, even if she or he is not aware of it in the moment. Such a goal prime should therefore prepare observers more directly for action (Bargh et al., 2001; see also Förster, Liberman, & Friedman, 2007).

Therefore, the distinction between mere semantic concepts and goals may lie in intermediate steps connecting goals and behavior. On the one hand, high self-efficacy – the individual’s perception that his or her abilities are sufficient to attain the goal – may be an important element that fosters motivation (Bandura & Cervone, 1983). On the other hand, the goal may require an emotional and affective component: only if there is positive affect associated with the goal may people be inclined to look for means to pursue it (Fishbach,

Shah, & Kruglanski, 2004). Overall, goals may be part of a system of knowledge structures; in these systems they are connected to motivational and affective elements, as well as means to attain the goal. Additionally, within these systems, goals may also have different levels of concreteness and can even be in conflict with other goals.

The interconnections of goals and means can span from very abstract to concrete. One can think of “doing sports” as an overarching abstract goal (e.g., a higher-order goal; Carver & Scheier, 1981). But to serve the purpose of the higher-order goal, one has to focus on more concrete physical-activity goals on a lower level thereafter. Examples of these concrete goals would be “jogging in the park,” “hitting the gym,” “playing football” or “skiing” (i.e., “doing sports” is an equifinal goal, see Kruglanski et al., 2002). However, these concrete goals require different means to achieve them (e.g., football requires a ball and people to play with; skiing requires skis and snow; and both require distinct sets of skills) and how to achieve them can be a matter of preference, but also of time and resources to pursue other goals.

Life becomes problematic when there are goals in conflict with each other (Kruglanski et al., 2002). If you want to go jogging, but a friend has also invited you for drinks at the same time, these two goals may be in conflict, as you may want to pursue and accomplish both of them. Decisions about which goal to pursue and which one to postpone or even drop often require careful consideration about how urgent or enjoyable these goals are. Meeting a friend for a drink can be enjoyable, especially if one has not seen this person in a long time, but when it comes to staying in shape, going for regular runs might

be preferable. Resolving such a goal conflict can sometimes require cognitive effort. However, some lines of research suggest a link to quick and automatic processes being involved in decisions on how and which goals to pursue (Shah, Friedman, & Kruglanski, 2002; Custers & Aarts, 2010).

Automatic Processes and Inferences of Traits and Goals

In general, the social-cognitive literature distinguishes deliberate processes, which are based on explicit, conscious thinking and reasoning, from automatic processes that occur quickly and on a rather implicit level (Kahneman, 2012). Both processes may play a certain role when it comes to the pursuit of goals, but it is the latter process that caught the attention of researchers (Chartrand & Jefferis, 2003; Gollwitzer & Bargh, 2005). Although everyday experiences show that people mostly plan to pursue goals in rather deliberate ways, research could demonstrate that the cognitive underpinnings of goal pursuit may have implicit elements too.

As mentioned in the previous section, once the concept of a goal is activated (e.g., the concept of “doing sports”), it might spill over to associated concrete means and ways to pursue this goal (e.g., “jogging in the park”). Importantly, this preparation for a goal-relevant action might occur unconsciously and quasi-simultaneously to the activation of the goal (Chen & Bargh, 1997; Pulvermüller, 2005). In this process, goal pursuit can become more likely when the goal-directed behavior is executed frequently enough to become a routine and if the observer assigns a high value to the goal (Custers & Aarts,

Figure 0. The conceptual model for the process of goal contagion. Black boxes and arrows signify the core model; grey boxes and arrows signify additional, moderating theoretical effects.

2010). However, an implicit and automatic pathway might be relevant not only for goal pursuit, but also for the activation of the goal itself – and one way to activate a goal is to infer it from another person’s behavior (for a conceptual model see Figure 0).

In earlier research on quick and automatic inferences about others’ behavior, the focus was not on the observed person’s potential goals, but rather on their personality traits (see, e.g., Uleman, Newman, & Moskowitz, 1996). For instance, watching a jogger in the park would foremost elicit the thought that this person must be sporty and physically active in general. Hence, observers identify a cause for this person’s behavior, which is the supposed trait of this observed person. Consequently, Hassin and colleagues (Hassin, Bargh, & Uleman, 2002) synthesized these findings in the framework on spontaneous causal inferences. However, although inference on traits can occur automatically, they often do not account for all types of behavior. Therefore, goals as an alternative cause for behavior became a popular topic for research.

Hassin, Aarts, and Ferguson (2005) extended the framework on inferences about traits towards inferences about goals. In one important experiment, they presented participants with short sentences that implied a goal of a protagonist who was behaving in a certain way (e.g., “The man with the suitcases goes to the airport”). Although the goals were not mentioned in the vignettes, participants falsely indicated that it was part of the sentences shortly after (e.g. “travel”). Although these indications did not hint at an activation on an implicit level per se, they were still spontaneous and under time constraints, demonstrating that

participants vividly pictured this goal in the context of the experiment. Hence, this result suggested that people's inference processes about the behavior of others are not restricted to traits about the person but may also occur for their potential goals. What this experiment could not show, however, was whether the activation of the goal-related concept could have an effect on the observer's own future behavior.

From Observation to Inference to Action

Quick and automatic inferences of goals, which were shown in Hassin et al.'s experiments (2005), mooted the question of whether they could spill over to the observer's own behavior. After all, semantic priming experiments not only showed that associated concepts become more accessible (as in early experiments, see Neely, 1977), but that certain abstract semantic concepts like "achievement" or "cooperation" can even have behavioral consequences (Bargh et al., 2001). Compared to these semantic primes, the observation of goal-directed behavior is even less subtle and by definition more directly linked to actual behavior than a mere semantic prime. Therefore, it was reasonable to assume that the observation of goal-directed behavior might have the potential to change the behavior of the observer, although the process might not be identical to a regular semantic prime.

For observed goal-directed behaviors of others, this process might be somewhat different from a semantic prime: Instead of activating a concept semantically, the concept of a behavior is likely the first activated node, which is followed by

an activation of the concept of the observed goal. As this is the goal inferred from the behavior of another person, it might then be attributed to the self in the process (see also Laurin, 2016), which may prepare for subsequent action, if an action is within the realm of possibilities.

After a goal is successfully inferred and activated in the observer, she is ready to pursue it herself. To this end, the current situation in her environment has to allow the pursuit of that goal. For instance, if an observer sees a second person providing help to a third person, she (the observer) might get ready to also provide help for a brief moment. However, if there is nobody in the direct environment who might need help, the potential for action evaporates after some time (see Förster et al., 2007). If, on the other hand, an opportunity for help opens up, the observer could be inclined to pursue this goal. Aarts, Gollwitzer, and Hassin (2004) were then the first to show evidence that a behavioral observation can indeed result in the adaption and pursuit of the manipulated goal. They called this effect “goal contagion.”

The Goal Contagion Effect – Early and Recent Evidence

In the first empirical goal contagion paper, Aarts and colleagues (2004) reported six studies testing several aspects of goal contagion. They could show that participants who read about another person earning money, worked more quickly through a subsequent task, in which they could also earn money, when compared to a control group. This was especially true for participants who had a high need for money (Study 1).

Moreover, the authors showed that after male participants read about someone's goal to have casual sex, they would desire and indirectly pursue this goal by providing more help to a female experimenter compared to a male experimenter (Studies 2 and 3). They would also pursue it less often if the person in the text had a pregnant girlfriend at home (Studies 4 and 5), indicating that moral acceptability of the observed behavior is important. Finally, the authors could exclude that goals other than casual sex were simultaneously active and the potential driver of the effect (Study 6). Hence, the main message of this initial goal contagion paper was that several moderators may be at work. The whole mediation process, however, was of less interest.

Therefore, a point of critique of these studies was that the goal contagion effect was not demonstrated in its theoretical nuances in one experiment (see Figure 0): Either a quick and automatic inference (on a more or less implicit level) was shown, or a behavior (goal pursuit) as its consequence. Dik and Aarts (2007), who manipulated prosocial goals, attempted to fill this gap in the literature. Indeed, they showed some evidence that goal inference mediated the effect between the observation and goal pursuit. Later, Jia, Tong, and Lee (2014) confirmed the mediation effect, using different goal manipulation materials and dependent measures.

Although several other studies made use of the idea of goal contagion (while often making ample changes in the paradigm, e.g., Laurin et al., 2016, Leander et al., 2016), no other published study (to my knowledge) has focused on the whole goal contagion effect as it was initially proposed, including implicit inference and goal pursuit. However, this approach

would be important to strengthen the theoretical argument in favor of the goal contagion effect.

This Dissertation Project

This dissertation serves to address these issues and summarize the existing evidence on goal contagion. For the studies reported in the following two chapters, my collaborators and I attempted to focus on paradigms that resemble those of the earlier research on goal contagion: We manipulated the goal to be prosocial (similar to Dik & Aarts, 2007) and the goal to earn money (similar to Aarts et al., 2004, Study 1) while accounting for some theoretically derived moderators. We employed very similar designs, added only a few building blocks study by study and thereby attempted to achieve sufficient statistical power for these studies to gain high confidence in the effects that we report (see Chambers, 2017, Chapter 3). The aim was to identify whether the theoretically outlined goal contagion effect also translates into measurable effects in lab experiments.

In the studies in Chapter 2, we were interested primarily in prosocial behavior as the outcome variable and whether it is influenced by the observation of casual helping behavior as it occurs in everyday life. A potential mediation by goal inference is tested on a spontaneous, but rather explicit level. In the studies reported in Chapter 3, we attempted to test the full mediation model for goal contagion in an earning-money paradigm. We included both explicit and implicit inference and goal pursuit, and also accounted for the value that people assign to the goal. In Chapter 4, we present a systematic review

and a meta-analysis of the goal contagion effect, which uses modern techniques of publication-bias correction. Additionally, we tried to identify potential moderating effects.

Taken together, although the goal contagion effect has been theoretically outlined, it was hardly tested in its entirety. Additionally, many goal-contagion studies were conducted before the replication crisis started in 2011, which called for more solid and transparent methods in general. My collaborators and I took this into account: The large majority of studies in this dissertation are preregistered. That is, we determined our main hypothesis, our research design and variables, our analysis plans, and our sample sizes before we started the data collection phase. Data, analysis scripts and materials, as well as links to the preregistrations are available online (Chapter 1: <https://osf.io/4efbc/>, Chapter 2: <https://osf.io/ef59b/>, Chapter 3: <https://osf.io/mxepy/>).

Chapter 2

Is there Goal Contagion for the Goal to be Prosocial?

This chapter is based on the following published article:

Brohmer, H., Fauler, A., Floto, C., Athenstaedt, U., Kedia, G., Eckerstorfer, L. V., & Corcoran, K. (2019). Inspired to lend a hand? Attempts to elicit prosocial behavior through goal contagion. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00545>

Minor changes in this chapter compared to the article concern the layout and are not content-related. They were communicated to and approved by the co-authors.

Introduction

Human beings are inherently social animals, as they constantly interact with each other and influence each other's lives in many ways (Dijksterhuis, 2005). We often rely on the prosocial behavior of others—like close kin, friends, or sometimes even strangers—and cannot achieve certain goals if it were not for others lending a hand. Countless examples come to mind, like the mother who supports her daughter with some extra pocket money, or the employee at work who provides help to a coworker finishing a project on time, or the stranger on the street who spontaneously provides help to a grandma crossing the street. But not only the person who receives the help profits from such behavior. Prosocial behavior is essential to both the society and interpersonal relations (e.g., Dovidio et al., 2006, Chapter 8, Tomasello, 2014, Chapters 4 & 5) and is likely innate to humans (Warneken and Tomasello, 2009). Cultures do usually thrive if there is some sort of institutionalized exchange between people who can provide help and people in need for help. However, a prerequisite for those institutions to work on the societal level are functional and positive interpersonal relations built on trust and cooperation among individuals (Cook, 2001; Newton et al., 2018). Because positive interpersonal relations and trust might be fostered by prosocial behavior (Yamagishi et al., 2005), it would be desirable to know how people can get inspired to behave prosocially. One social-cognitive mechanism that might have the potential to facilitate prosocial behavior is goal contagion.

Goal contagion is a process by which a person adopts a goal following a behavioral observation. Thus, people might be motivated to act prosocially and engage in prosocial behavior, because they adopted a prosocial goal after observing others lending a hand. Importantly, goal contagion is distinct from role modeling (Morgenroth et al., 2015) or mimicry (Chartrand and Lakin, 2013), because people could be inspired to pursue a similar goal but use different goal-directed behavior as the observed person. Furthermore, goal contagion occurs automatically and follows a specific cognitive mechanism.

The underlying principle of goal contagion is based on research on spontaneous causal inferences (Hassin et al., 2002). This framework posits that once we observe another person's behavior, we automatically try finding causes for her behavior. For example, if somebody helps a coworker to finish a project, we might infer that this person is especially helpful. In this example, we infer a trait to explain the behavior. Additionally, Aarts and colleagues (Aarts et al., 2004; Aarts and Hassin 2005; Hassin et al., 2005) hypothesized that people might also infer goals from behavior, because goals are just another cause for behavior. In one line of experiments, they showed that reading goal-implicating sentences (i.e., "The girl buys tools at the DIY shop") leads to the activation of words and terms in participants that are conceptually related to the goal (i.e., "manual labor") measured by a word probe task and a lexical decision task (Hassin et al., 2005). This indicates automatic goal inference.¹

¹ In the goal contagion literature, the activation of goal-related words is sometimes interpreted as indicating automatic goal inference (i.e.,

Importantly, in another line of studies, Aarts et al. (2004) extended the previous findings by demonstrating that people, who observed goal-directed behavior, sometimes adopt the same goal. Specifically, they presented heterosexual male participants with the story of a male protagonist buying a female person a drink in a bar, implying the protagonist's intention to attain the goal of having casual sex with that woman. After reading the story, the heterosexual male participants were asked to provide help in a subsequent task. Results showed that participants who had received the casual sex story were more willing to help a female experimenter compared to those who were asked to help a male experimenter and those who had read a control story. Because being friendly to females could increase the likelihood of intimate relationships, Aarts and colleagues interpreted their male participants' increased willingness to help as a mean for attaining the automatically inferred goal of having casual sex. Several follow-up studies (Aarts et al., 2005; Dik and Aarts, 2007, 2008; Loersch et al., 2008; Jia et al., 2014; Lee and Shapiro, 2016; Wessler and Hansen, 2016; see also Corcoran et al., 2019) could validate the goal contagion hypothesis in the context of very distinct goals like academic achievements, earning money, or dieting. However, little of this research addresses prosocial behavior as goal to be elicited in observers.

To our knowledge, there is only one article on goal contagion with casual prosocial behavior—understood as

the observer infers the goal, Jia et al., 2014) and sometimes as indicating goal adoption (i.e., the observer adopts and pursues the goal, Dik and Aarts, 2007).

helping as it often occurs in everyday life situations—as the focal goal. In these studies, participants viewed short clips about animated objects providing help to other objects (Dik and Aarts, 2007). The helping objects in those animations put different degrees of effort in their helping behavior. The more effort they showed, the more the helping goal was activated in participants and the more participants indicated willingness to help in a subsequent, unrelated task. However, there are goal contagion studies on other forms of prosocial behavior.

Some studies on goal contagion focused on the goal to cooperate (Loersch et al., 2008; Jia et al., 2014). For example, participants observed a team playing football cooperatively and then developed more cooperative strategies within hypothetical sport scenarios (Loersch et al., 2008). Furthermore, there is evidence that other priming techniques could elicit prosocial behavior. These techniques include semantical primes like crossword or scrambled word tasks (e.g., Bargh et al., 2001; Aarts et al., 2005; Prentice and Sheldon, 2015; Sheldon et al., 2015). However, none of these studies measured a prosocial behavior in line with casual helping. Rather, they investigated subsequent cooperative behavior in social dilemmas or a mere cognitive activation.

In the present paper, we want to extend previous findings and examine whether goal contagion does facilitate prosocial behavior. Thereby, we focus on casual prosocial behavior that could be understood as voluntary helping and assisting in situations where neither the benefits of receiving help nor the costs of providing help are very high. In this sense, it is close to helping situations as they can occur on an everyday basis. Casual prosocial behavior does not consume a high amount of

resources (like time, money, or energy), but it also does not provide life-changing (or life-saving) assistance. We focus on this type of prosocial behavior for two reasons: first, casual prosocial behavior often occurs in public space and is therefore observable by others and, second, other factors than goal activation that affect prosocial behavior might play a lesser role.

Unlike more severe situations (as when someone is trapped in a burning car), the potential helper should not feel a strong pressure or obligation to help. In addition, situations for casual help are usually relatively easy to solve by the person in need him- or herself (as when someone accidentally drops a pile of folders), further minimizing the observer's feeling of responsibility and pressure by social norms. Although avoiding social punishments or public shaming when the norm of providing help is not followed are certainly concerns that have been rightly addressed in the context of other cooperative and social behavior (Schwartz and Howard, 1984; Fehr and Gächter, 2002; Goette et al., 2006; Rost et al., 2016), we argue that they play only a minor role for casual prosocial behavior. Casual helping also differs from the game-theoretical concept of cooperation which is often based on strategic considerations about individual and mutual payoffs (Axelrod and Hamilton, 1981; Fischbacher et al., 2001; Reuben and Suetens, 2009; Rand et al., 2014; Rand, 2016). Such considerations are less important for casual helping as utilities for outcomes are not as obvious and readily quantifiable. Although they certainly play a role on a more implicit level, they are not as present as in social dilemma games in the lab (e.g., by payoffs for each party in dictator games or points in resource-dilemma games).

Finally, casual helping is not much influenced by the helper's empathic concern regarding the person in need for help. Empathy often increases with the severity of the situation (Darley and Batson, 1973; Cialdini et al., 1997) and is crucial for altruism (Batson et al., 1981, 2007; Leiberg et al., 2011; Tusche et al., 2016). Altruism could result in prosocial behavior that involves sacrificially large costs for the helper. However, in our type of prosocial behavior, which is characterized by low costs not only for the provider for offering help, but for the receiver in case of omitted help, this plays a lesser role.

Taken together, casual prosocial behavior might not be the most dramatic and thought-through type of prosocial behavior. But similar to other acts of kindness (Van Doesum et al., 2013; Van Lange and Van Doesum, 2015), it conveys the message of interpersonal liking and respect. Furthermore, it occurs rather frequently and is often performed in public. Importantly for our research, it is less guided by other factors like empathic concern, the pressure of social norms or strategic considerations. Yet, it definitely provides an opportunity to pursue a prosocial goal. Thus, if goal contagion is a mechanism that can influence prosocial behavior, we are likely to detect it in the context of casual prosocial behavior.

However, prosocial behavior might not be equally contagious for everybody. There is a diverse range of moderators that have been investigated in the literature on goal contagion, such as effort of the observed person (Dik and Aarts, 2007), situational emotions (Jia et al., 2014) or the perceived social distance between the observer and the observed person (Wessler and Hansen, 2016). In the very first study on goal contagion by Aarts et al. (2004), participants'

individual need for money moderated the relationship between the inferred goal (earning money vs. control) and the adoption of that goal (earning money): the goal was most contagious for those in high need for money. This moderation effect suggests that an activation of a goal due to goal contagion is more likely if the goal is previously part of the observer's general goal system (Kruglanski et al., 2002). Thus, observer-related dispositions could be crucial to be considered in the context of prosocial behavior.

One of the main dispositional factors of prosocial behavior is social value orientation (SVO). SVO indicates to what degree people consider the interest of others in (inter) dependent situations (Messick and McClintock, 1968; McClintock et al., 1973; Kramer et al., 1986; Van Lange, 1999). To measure SVO, participants are confronted with several options of predetermined payoff-allocations and then have to choose between these options (Murphy et al., 2011; for a comparison of different measures, see Murphy and Ackermann, 2014). Eventually, a higher SVO score indicates a greater willingness to benefit an anonymous person rather than oneself.² People who would allocate resources in a mutually beneficial way or even provide the anonymous other with more resources are categorized as prosocials. On the contrary, people who would rather benefit oneself than another person or even maximize the difference between oneself and another person are categorized as proselFs.

² This is true for the Slider Measure (Murphy et al., 2011), whereas with older measures like the Triple-Dominance Measure (see Van Lange, 1999) participants are categorized directly.

SVO is predictive in a wide array of social contexts. It has been demonstrated that the more prosocially oriented people are, the more time they spend on others' requests (McClintock and Allison, 1989), the more they donate money for charity (Van Lange et al., 2007), the more socially mindful they select preferable objects (Van Doesum et al., 2013), the more often they interpret situations as a cooperative endeavor (Yamagishi et al., 2013), and the more they value moral behavior, including fairness, honesty, and equality (Liebrand et al., 1986; Sattler and Kerr, 1991; Joireman et al., 2003). Prosocials and proselves differ in their world views resulting in different expectations of others' behavior (see also generalized expectations in Kelley and Stahelski, 1970; Van Lange, 1992; Bogaert et al., 2008; Pletzer et al., 2018). Proselfs think that others would act in a selfish way when given the option to cooperate, whereas prosocials have a stronger initial expectation that others will cooperate in such situations.

In sum, there is ample evidence favoring SVO as a dispositional factor. In that regard, we think that prosocials more than proselves are stimulated by observing another person helping someone to pursue a prosocial goal themselves. Therefore, we investigate the moderating effect of SVO on the contagion of prosocial goals.

The Present Research

The main objective of the present research is to test whether observing an act of every day helping facilitates prosocial behavior due to goal contagion and whether this effect depends on the observer's social value orientation.

Specifically, we predict a main effect of goal contagion: participants in the goal condition should adopt the prosocial goal more often than participants in the control condition. However, this effect should be qualified by an interaction with SVO: the goal contagion process should be more pronounced the stronger participants are oriented toward prosocial values. In line with previous research, we also expected a main effect of social value orientation in a way that individuals should behave more prosocially with increasing prosocial orientation, regardless of the goal contagion effect.

Three studies were designed to test the aforementioned hypotheses. The first study was conducted as an online study via Amazon's Mechanical Turk (MTurk), the second one was conducted as a lab study with university students, and the third study was again conducted as an online study, but within a population mainly consisting of students. All three studies were conceptually similar and in line with previous research on goal contagion. They differed with respect to the manipulation material (texts in Study 1 and videos in Study 2 and 3), the point in time where SVO was measured (just before the manipulation in Study 1 and 2 and a week before the manipulation in Study 3) and the dependent measure of prosocial behavior. Crucially, the measure of the DV as well as the behavior observed was always consistent with our narrow focus on every day helping as one type of prosocial behavior. For the purpose of transparency, all data and materials are available on the Open Science Framework. Additionally, Study 2 and 3 were preregistered before data collection. Links are provided in corresponding study sections. All studies were

approved by the ethics committee by University of Graz and complied with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Study 1: Contagion of Prosocial Goals in an Online Study

Study 1 was an online study conducted on MTurk. Our first goal was to see if we could identify a goal contagion effect with prosocial behavior. This way, the study was to some degree similar to Dik and Aarts (2007), who also utilized prosocial goals, but additionally manipulated effort. Secondly, we investigated the moderation effect of SVO. We hypothesized that prosocial goals would be more contagious the more prosocially oriented people are. In addition, we expected that prosocial orientation would predict helping behavior in general (McClintock and Allison, 1989).

Similar to the original goal contagion studies (e.g., Aarts et al., 2004), we used short stories where a person was described in a situation where help was required. This happened after the participants' SVO was assessed and before they were confronted with an unrelated situation aimed at measuring their prosocial behavior. We measured SVO beforehand to avoid having the SVO score being influenced by the manipulation material (see Ackermann et al., 2016).

Sample and Participants

We determined the required sample size with G*Power (Faul et al., 2007) based on previous effects in the domain of goal contagion. This was problematic because reported effects ranged from small (e.g., Dik and Aarts, 2008, Experiment 3, r

= 0.16) to large for psychological standards (e.g., Aarts et al., 2004, Study 4, $r \sim 0.40$). Due to small sample sizes in most of the original studies, which potentially introduced a strong bias in the estimates, we reasoned that a medium population effect size (i.e., $r = 0.3$) was most realistic to assume. Therefore, we calculated our sample size for a linear OLS regression model with ΔR^2 representing the effect of the interaction term of SVO and the goal manipulation. For a $\Delta R^2 = 0.06$ ($f^2 \sim 0.06$), $\alpha = 0.05$, and $1 - \beta = 0.8$, we obtained a sample of $N = 105$ (one-tailed) to 133 (two-tailed) and decided in favor of the larger, more powerful sample.

We collected data from 138 MTurk workers, but had to exclude 12 participants because they either did not score on the dependent variable due to technical issues or failed the attention checks (see Materials and Methods section). The final sample of $N = 126$ had a mean age of 34.2 years of age ($SD = 11.12$), consisted of 49 females, 77 males, and 113 of them were native English speakers. The analysis without the non-native speakers did not change the pattern of results for the main hypothesis, although it did reduce the correlation between SVO and prosocial behavior. An analysis with demographic covariates did not change the pattern either, which is why we decided to report results from the final sample and without covariates below. For interested readers, all other results and analyses, as well as descriptive statistics, can be found online in the OSF (<https://osf.io/h8zj9/>).

Methods and Procedure

The study was prepared with the survey software Unipark (QuestBack GmbH, 2017). The general set-up of all three

studies can be seen in Figure 1. Participants read the consent form and agreed to participate in this 10-min study for \$1.00 compensation.

SVO. Afterward, they filled out the 6-item SVO measure by Murphy et al. (2011), in which they were instructed to allocate hypothetical resources between themselves and another agent. The resource was represented in “point” units, ranging from 15 to 100 for each person across items. This measure has been demonstrated to have excellent psychometric properties and all participants’ SVOs can be identified and pinpointed on a continuous scale (for details, see Murphy et al., 2011).

Goal Manipulation Texts. Subsequently, participants answered demographic questions about their age, ethnicity, education, and gender, the latter of which enabled us to adapt the gender of the characters in the following three short goal manipulation texts (i.e., by adapting pronouns and names). Those three stories were narrated in the third-person perspective and always described a person in an everyday life situation. Story 1 described a person on his or her way to a meeting; in Story 2, the character wanted to catch a connecting train, and in Story 3, he or she was on the bus on his or her way to a date. Hence, in all three stories, the main character had a certain destination just before another person appears in the scenario.

However, the stories differed across experimental conditions: In the goal contagion condition, another character appeared who needed help. In Story 1, the other person accidentally dropped a pile of papers and folders and the main character decided helping him or her to pick up all the folders (vs.

control condition in which nothing happened and the main character went on to the meeting). In Story 3, the main character was about to leave the bus and noticed another passenger with a lot of luggage who needs help (vs. control condition in which the other passenger did not have luggage and was not in need of help). Story 2 was a filler story that did not involve any intervention of the main character in either condition. The endings of the stories were always presented on a second page to separate the climax of the story from the conclusion.

The stories were created so that the decision of the main character to help was associated with some small costs (like going on a date, but helping someone heaving luggage or hurrying to a meeting, but assisting someone picking up folders). Moreover, the helping situations we depicted were not severe for the victim. Even if the main character had not offered help, the person in distress would not have been subjected to any harm. We did so to avoid potential emotional confounders in our goal manipulation, which may be typical in related research (Batson et al., 1981, 2007; Cialdini et al., 1997) while highlighting the actual casual helping behavior in an everyday situation.

To ensure that participants had read the texts, we asked them two questions about the content of each story (six in total). Participants who did not answer at least five of those questions correctly were excluded from the analysis ($n = 10$).

Volunteering as Dependent Measure. Following the previous questions, participants were partly debriefed. However, on the same page below, they were offered to volunteer in another

Figure 1. General set-up of Study 1–3. (1) Data on SVO was collected prior to the manipulation (Murphy et al., 2011). (2) Goal manipulation was carried out through texts in Study 1 and video clips in Study 2 and 3. (3) DVs were measured with a drag and drop task in Study 1 and 3, and with the ZPG in Study 2. Note that written informed consent was obtained from all depicted individuals for the publication of these images.

student's experiment (similar to Aarts et al., 2004 and Dik and Aarts, 2007 we avoided the word "help" in this description, see OSF). They were told that the student could not compensate them with money because she or he did not receive any funding. However, participants could still support the student by completing some pages of her study. They were also told that they could terminate their participation any time and proceed to the end of the survey. Participants' agreement or disagreement to start the unpaid extra study was the first dependent measure we obtained (DV1).

The second measure (DV2) was then obtained by the number of pages participants completed in the extra study, described as "Geometrical Figure Task." Here, they had to drag and drop scrambled symbols, which could vary in color or shape, from the left-hand side of the screen to the right-hand side in a way that similar symbols were stacked next to each other (see Figure 1, third frame). Thus, the task was purposely designed to be neither too complicated nor too exciting in the long run, as too fascinating tasks could confound our DV. After all, we intended to measure prosocial helping rather than excitement over a task. One page could be completed in approximately 10 s and we prepared 160 pages to ensure that participants would be occupied for some time to complete the whole task, if they really intended to finish it. Indeed, we were deliberately unspecific in the instructions about the approximated time to complete the task. This served the purpose that participant's initial intention to help would not be confounded by their reflection on the length of the task (e.g., if they knew there were 160 pages, they could plan ahead to complete 10 pages only).

Whether Mturk workers participated or not, the last page would contain HIT code for their compensation.

Results and Discussion

Before submitting the data, we dummy-coded the goal manipulation texts (control texts = 0, goal texts = 1) and centered SVO on the threshold between proselves and prosocials ($SVO = 22.45$; see Murphy et al., 2011). The same coding was applied in the subsequent studies. Then, we ran two confirmatory analyses using SPSS 24 with the PROCESS macro (Hayes, 2013). First, we calculated logistic regressions with participants' decision to help the student (DV1) regressed on SVO and goal manipulation (Model 1). In Model 2, we added the interaction term as predictor. In total, we found that 45 out of 126 (36%) participants chose to help the student in need. However, neither the effect of SVO, Wald's $\chi^2(1) = 2.276$, $p = 0.131$, $OR = 1.021$, nor the effect of the goal manipulation, Wald's $\chi^2(1) = -0.032$, $p = 0.931$, $OR = 0.968$ led to any significant result. Also, the model with the interaction term (Model 2) did not yield the expected moderation effect either, Wald's $\chi^2(1) = 0.840$, $p = 0.360$, $OR = 0.975$, $\Delta\chi^2(1) = 0.846$.

Second, we regressed the number of completed pages (DV2) on SVO, the goal manipulation (Model 1), and their interaction term (Model 2). As expected, we found a marginally significant effect of SVO in Model 1, $b = 0.083$, $t(123) = 1.831$, $p = 0.069$. However, the goal manipulation did not have an influence on the amount of prosocial behavior provided, $b = -0.274$, $t(123) = -0.274$, $p = 0.831$. Furthermore, the goal manipulation and SVO did not interact, $b = -0.020$, $t(122) = -0.226$, $p = 0.822$,

$\Delta R^2 < 0.001$. As visualized in Figure 2, the simple slopes of SVO for both conditions overlapped considerably and did not differ from 0, control condition: $b = 0.092$, $t(122) = 1.542$, $p = 0.126$, prosocial goal condition: $b = 0.072$, $t(122) = 1.136$, $p = 0.258$. Although we could identify a small effect of SVO, our manipulation for goal contagion did not affect participants' helping behavior. Importantly, the aforementioned effect of SVO on helping behavior was brought to light only for the continuous dependent measure, but not for the dichotomous measure. This indicates that proselves and prosocials do not differ much in their mere signaling of providing help, but some differences can be spotted in prosocials' endurance in providing help.

There may be several reasons why the goal manipulation did not work. First, although several goal contagion studies used text-based priming, these kinds of manipulations might be limited in evoking sensitive cognitive processes (see Kanning et al., 2006 for a test of different stimuli). Secondly, MTurk workers might rather be oriented to finish up studies for a financial compensation, as many might even participate for a living (Semuels, 2018). Thirdly, there are few and rather mixed findings on the quality of MTurk studies (Paolacci and Chandler, 2014; Rouse, 2015; Hauser and Schwarz, 2016). Overall, we wanted to address these issues in our second study, which we conducted in a more controlled lab setting in order to get a cleaner effect of goal contagion. Moreover, the lab setting enabled us to utilize another dependent measure suitable for casual helping behavior.

Figure 2. Prosocial Behavior as a function of SVO in Study 1. The separate regression lines represent two conditions. Shades depict 95% CIs. Higher density of the scatter signifies higher concentration of data. Vertical dashed line separates “proselfs” (left) from “prosocials” (right).

Study 2: Prosocial Goals in the Lab

In Study 2, we wanted to investigate the contagion of prosocial goals in a lab setting, testing the same hypotheses as before. We intended to use short video clips for our goal manipulation in order to make the helping situation more vivid than in Study 1 and therefore foster the effect. Moreover, we decided to use a relatively recently introduced measure of prosocial behavior: the Zurich Prosocial Game (ZPG; Leiberg et al., 2011). The ZPG can be altered to measure prosocial behavior freed from competitive contexts, contrasting it with other social dilemma games (e.g., Prisoner's Dilemma, Ultimatum Game or Trust Games). This study, the initial hypothesis, and sample size calculation were preregistered in the OSF before the data were collected (<https://osf.io/rt4b9/>).

Participants and Sample Size

We did not find the expected goal contagion effects in Study 1. Therefore, in Study 2, we aimed for a smaller effect size with a large sample: for $\Delta R^2 = 0.04$ ($f^2 \sim 0.04$) for the relevant interaction effect, with $\alpha = 0.05$ and $1 - \beta = 0.8$, we obtained a sample of $N = 156$ (one-tailed) to 199 (two-tailed) and decided to collect data from at least 180 participants. Eventually, our sample consisted of 183 students recruited on the campus of the University of Graz, Austria, of which 21 had to be excluded according to the preregistered exclusion criteria (such as missing data on the key variables: $n = 17$; and failed attention checks after the video clips: $n = 4$; see OSF-link above). We were left with a final sample of $N = 162$, with a

mean age of 22.60 years ($SD = 10.50$), 101 females, and 160 native German speakers.

Inclusion of demographic covariates did not change the main pattern of results, which is why we focus on the main analysis here. Additional analyses and descriptive statistics can be found in the OSF.

Methods and Procedure

Participants were welcomed to the lab and seated in front of one of several computer work stations, which were separated by blinds. They filled out the consent form and were introduced to the ZPG (see below) because we wanted to avoid that a later introduction would reduce the effect of the manipulation. SVO, the goal manipulation, and post hoc questions were recorded in Unipark (QuestBack GmbH, 2017) and the scores for the dependent measure were recorded in a separate window.

SVO. As in Study 1, participants filled out the SVO items by Murphy et al. (2011) prior to the goal manipulation. Afterward they filled out the competitive jungle worldview scale (Perry and Sibley, 2010) for another research question. Inclusion of this worldview as factor in two-way and three-way interactions with the goal manipulation and SVO did not influence the pattern of results (additional variables can be found in the data set, see OSF).

Goal Manipulation Video Clips. We produced short video clips depicting three situations in which people showed helpful intentions toward another person in an everyday life situation

in the experimental condition (vs. no help was required in the control condition). Similar to the texts from Study 1, the helping situations depicted were not too severe, to avoid inducing empathy in participants.

Situation 1 and 3 differed per experimental condition, whereas Situation 2 was a filler situation and identical in both conditions. In Situation 1, participants saw a woman walking down a narrow street on the sidewalk noticing another person with many grocery bags on the other side of the street, struggling to open a front door. The woman then decides to quickly run to the other side to provide help (vs. someone from inside the building opens the door). In Situation 2, a young woman in a park observes another person's glove accidentally fall out of his pocket while answering a call. However, this other person quickly turns around and picks up the glove. Lastly, Situation 3 depicted a young man in business attire hurrying up a staircase. He passes a female person carrying many folders down the staircase. After she accidentally dropped the folders, he turns around to go back to her (vs. she does not drop the folders and no help is required).

The videos' lengths were between 24 and 38 s. They were edited in such a way participants would assume helping intentions by the main characters in the experimental condition but not in the control condition. Participants then answered three attention check questions concerning the content of the videos (see the exclusion criteria above).

Prosocial Behavior with the Zurich Prosocial Game (ZPG). In the ZPG (Leiberg et al., 2011; Böckler et al., 2016; Bornemann et al., 2016), participants have to navigate a smiley character along

a path that leads to a treasure. Another character—described as another participant, but played by the computer in reality—navigates through a separate path toward his or her own treasure. Obstacle gates fall on both paths randomly and players are required to use keys to open them in order to proceed. We pretested the ZPG and gave detailed instructions to ensure that participants understood the specifics of the game (see OSF).

Our participants were instructed to perform five rounds of this game. To draw participants' attention toward their treasures, we told them that they would receive a “special reward” (they could draw a lottery ticket from a pot), if they successfully obtained the treasure in at least four out of the five rounds. Importantly, in three of these rounds, we altered the game so that the other character did not have enough keys to open the last remaining gate before arriving at the treasure. The participants always had one spare key that they would not need anymore. Thus, they had the option to help the other player without encountering much cost apart from losing few seconds from their liberal time limit of approximately 50 s (whereby one round was easily completed in 30–40 s). The number of times participants decided to open the other player's gate counted as the measurement of prosocial behavior. As each participant could offer his or her help in three rounds of the ZPG, the resulting scale ranged from 0 to 3.

The strength of the ZPG lies in the increased subtleness of the experimental procedure compared to other measures. Many established prosociality measures are more overt with respect to their purpose, as participants are relatively explicitly

confronted with the situation or asked to provide help (Study 1 & 3 in this paper; Aarts et al., 2004, Study 3; Dik and Aarts, 2007, Experiment 3). Here, the purpose is disguised in the context of a game, where the player's primary goal is to reach the treasure at the end of a path. Hence, helping the other player in this situation is optional and should depend on whether participants perceive this situation as an opportunity to help through either goal activation or their dispositional SVO.

Before the actual ZPG, participants played two test rounds (before the SVO and the manipulation) aimed at familiarizing them with the task.

Post-measure Questions. In the last part, participants were asked demographic questions and several exploratory questions about the manipulation and the ZPG, including three goal inference questions about what the goals of the protagonists in the clips had been (for each clip one goal-related answer out of three options) and how often the other player in the ZPG had needed help (0–5 times). We also asked them to what extent they thought that the other player in the ZPG would help them if they were trapped behind a gate (expectation measured on a scale from 0 to 100%) and the degree to which they believed that the other player had been another participant (human player, 1 “not at all authentic” to 7 “very authentic”). We report those variables for the sake of transparency. Exploratory analyses with those variables can be found in the OSF.

Figure 3. Prosocial Behavior as a function of SVO in Study 2. Separate lines refer to the two conditions. Shades depict 95% CIs. Higher density of the scatter signifies higher concentration of data. Vertical dashed line separates “proselfs” (left) from “prosocials” (right).

Results and Discussion

Confirmatory Analysis. We computed two OLS regression models. In the first model without the interaction term, we observed an effect of SVO on casual helping, $b = 0.022$, $t(159) = 2.427$, $p = 0.016$, but not of the goal manipulation, $b = -0.011$, $t(159) = -0.062$, $p = 0.951$. Importantly, in the second model, the interaction did not reach significance either, $b = -0.022$, $t(158) = -1.104$, $p = 0.271$, $\Delta R^2 = 0.009$. The simple slope for SVO (see Figure 3) was significant in the control condition, $b = 0.033$, $t(158) = 2.585$, $p = .011$, but not in the goal condition, $b = 0.011$, $t(158) = 0.846$, $p = 0.399$.

Exploratory Analyses and Goal Inference as Mediator. As described above, we also collected data on the two variables expectation and human player, which we explored in a regression model with the other predictors. In line with previous research (Pletzer et al., 2018), expectation turned out to be a significant predictor, $b = 0.027$, $t(155) = 9.601$, $p < 0.001$, and the human-player variable was, as well, $b = -0.082$, $t(155) = -2.094$, $p = 0.038$. The latter showed a negative slope coefficient, indicating that the less participants believed that the other player was human, the more they behaved prosocially afterward. Therefore, we inspected the item and observed that most participants actually did not believe that the other player was human to begin with, $M = 2.55$, $SD = 1.74$ (on a 7-point scale from 1 “highly inauthentic” to 7 “highly authentic”).

As has been suggested by various studies in the domain of goal contagion (e.g., Aarts et al., 2004), but hardly ever tested (Dik and Aarts, 2008; Jia et al., 2014; Corcoran et al., 2019), it is necessary for a goal to be correctly inferred in order to

become contagious. Hence, we suspected goal inference to mediate the relationship between the goal manipulation and prosocial behavior. Because we asked participants which goal the people in the three videos pursued, we could build a score of explicit prosocial goal inference. When participants indicated that the people wanted to help somebody, we coded their answer with 1. As a result, participants' inference scores ranged from 0 ("no inference") to 3 ("high inference"). Additionally, we kept SVO as a moderator in the model on the direct path between the goal manipulation and prosocial behavior and between goal inference and prosocial behavior. Therefore, we submitted the data to a mediation analysis with the goal manipulation as IV, prosocial behavior as DV, goal inference as mediator, and SVO as moderator. Goal inference was strongly predicted by the manipulation, $b = 1.393$, $t(160) = 14.857$, $p < 0.001$, but neither goal inference \times SVO nor goal manipulation \times SVO interactively predicted prosocial behavior, $b = -0.005$, $t(156) = -0.309$, $p = 0.758$ and $b = -0.015$, $t(156) = -0.536$, $p = 0.593$, respectively (see Figure 4). The main effects (based on mean-centered predictors) for SVO, $b = 0.022$, $t(156) = 2.168$, $p = 0.032$, and goal manipulation, $b = -0.082$, $t(156) = -0.318$, $p = 0.751$, had similar slopes as before, and no effect of goal inference on prosocial behavior was spotted, $b = -0.06$, $t(156) = -0.392$, $p = 0.696$. Thus, none of the conditional direct or indirect effects explained prosocial behavior either (see OSF for additional information). This analysis suggests that explicit goal inference did not affect prosocial behavior. Hence, in this study, prosocial behavior could not be attributed to a goal contagion process—neither directly nor over explicit inference.

In sum, results of Study 2 showed a pattern similar to Study 1. Again, prosocial behavior was not influenced by the goal manipulation and goal contagion did not get stronger the more prosocially oriented participants were. However, the prosocial orientation in itself predicted participants' willingness to help. This relationship underlines that the ZPG indeed assessed variation in prosocial behavior in our study and therefore weakens concern of a null effect due to a fallacious measurement of the DV. Moreover and in line with other research (Aarts, 2004; Jia et al., 2014; see also Corcoran et al., 2019), we could demonstrate an effect of our manipulation on explicit goal inference. However, no relation between goal inference and prosocial behavior emerged. Although participants in the relevant condition had correctly inferred the goal of the observed person, it turned out that this was not a necessary condition for their own prosocial behavior.

The previous two studies did not yield the expected interaction effect of the goal manipulation and SVO, although we found a small but consistent effect of SVO on prosocial behavior. For Study 3, we decided to gain more power by enhancing our priming material further and considerably increase the sample size. Therefore, we decided to turn back to the initial DV measure from Study 1 because that one is more feasible in online settings and because most participants in Study 2 did not believe they were playing against another human player.

Figure 4. Exploratory mediation models for Study 2 (panel A) and Study 3 (panel B); b_s represent unstandardized path coefficients; b_2 and b_3 are interaction effects with SVO as moderator; note: * $p < 0.001$.

Study 3: Confirming the Effect of SVO

Study 3 aimed at maximizing the power, while addressing some potential critiques of our IVs. First, one could argue that our former control condition always depicted people in situations, where one person was in some need and where social interactions with other people were potentially looming for the main character. Therefore, we included a second control condition in the form of a video that did not depict any social interaction among humans and from which participants could not infer any goal. Consequently, we tested our hypotheses with focus on the goal condition vs. control condition 2. Second, since SVO was measured right before the manipulation in both studies, it is possible that SVO itself primed participants to behave in a proself or prosocial manner in the voluntary task (Study 1) and in the ZPG (Study 2) and thus hindered the effects of the goal manipulation. To address this issue, we conceptualized Study 3 as a two-part online study and measured SVO 1 week before the actual goal manipulation. As dependent measure, we relied on the voluntary task from Study 1. The study was designed in Unipark (Questback GmbH, 2017).

Participants and Sample Size

Employing a second control condition video clip, we were striving for a small effect between this clip and the experimental condition. Hence, we calculated the sample size with G*Power, using a priori multiple regression, $\alpha = 0.05$, $1 - \beta = 0.80$, one tested predictor (SVO interacting with Dummy 1 for goal conditions vs. control condition 2), a total

of five predictors (SVO, Dummy 1, Dummy 2 for control 1 vs. control 2, SVO \times Dummy 1, and SVO \times Dummy 2), and $\Delta R^2 = 0.023$ ($f^2 \sim 0.023$) as parameters. This yielded $N = 351$ participants. The study was designed as online study and a link was sent to the student population of the University of Graz, distributed via Facebook messages and Facebook groups, and finally to students which we had approached on campus and in different introductory lectures. As incentive, students were given the opportunity to take part in a lottery for vouchers.

A total of 1148 people clicked on the link for the first part of the study and 616 completed this first part. One week later, a link to the second part was sent to these participants via email. A total of 642 clicked on the second link (26 clicked on it twice) of which a total of 423 reached the end of Study 3. We matched participants across study parts using anonymous ID codes and excluded those who did not fulfill our registered criteria (see <https://osf.io/57ukg/>). These criteria included that they should not take more than 10 min to reach the voluntary helping task after the goal manipulation, reported having not been distracted during the task, reported having had no trouble with the video buffering, and answered at least two questions correctly in the attention checks (see next section). Thus, our final sample had 371 participants, consisting mainly of students from several schools of the University of Graz. Their mean age was 22.48 years ($SD = 3.79$) and a majority of them were women ($n = 272$).

Methods and Procedure

In the first part of Study 3, we only collected data about participants' SVO, measured via Murphy et al.'s (2011) scale.

Participants then provided their email address so that we could send them the link to the second part after 1 week. This second link led them to the actual experiment, in which participants were randomly assigned to one out of three conditions and watched one of three video clips. Two clips (goal condition, control 1) were identical to the ones used in Study 2. The third clip represented another, potentially more minimal control condition (control 2), showing a blue whale in the ocean (similar control condition clips with nature documentary contents were used by Schnall et al., 2010).

After three attention check questions, participants were partially debriefed and given the opportunity to volunteer in another student's extra task that would not be monetarily rewarded. We used participants' response to this helping behavior request as our first DV in a logistic regression model. Moreover, we used the number of pages participants voluntarily completed from this additional task as our second DV in an OLS regression model (material was adopted from Study 1). Before students could take part in the lottery, they had to answer three goal inference questions identical to those of Study 2 (in goal and control 1 only). Also, they were asked if they were distracted while doing the study (from 1 "not at all" to 4 "very much") and whether they could watch the video without problems (from 1 "yes, without problems" to 4 "no, not at all").

Results and Discussion

Confirmatory Analysis. We first performed logistic regressions to evaluate participants' initial indication to help the student as a dichotomous measure with SVO and two

dummy variables (goal vs. control 2 and control 1 vs. control 2) for the three experimental conditions in Model 1, and the interactions between SVO and the conditions as additional predictors in Model 2. Model 2's interaction terms were not significant, goal \times SVO: Wald's $\chi^2(2) = 0.209, p = 0.647, OR = 1.01$, control 1 \times SVO: Wald's $\chi^2(2) = 1.946, p = 0.163, OR = 1.03$. In Model 1, we did not find any effect of SVO, Wald's $\chi^2(1) = 0.042, p = 0.837, OR = 1.002$, but we observed a significant difference between the goal condition and control condition 2, Wald's $\chi^2(1) = 3.878, p = 0.049, OR = 0.594$, as well as between the control 1 and control 2 conditions, Wald's $\chi^2(1) = 7.148, p = 0.008, OR = 0.493$. Contrary to our expectations, the effect of the manipulation indicated that participants who watched the control 2 clip with the whale were more willing to help ($n = 99, 71\%$) than participants who watched the goal clip ($n = 69, 59\%$) or the control 1 clip ($n = 62, 54\%$).

However, this latter effect was not confirmed in the OLS regression with the amount of completed pages as continuous DV. There was no effect found for neither of the two dummy variables (reference group: control condition 2), goal condition: $b = 0.181, t(367) = 0.102, p = 0.919$; control 1: $b = -1.189, t(367) = -0.668, p = 0.505$, nor for SVO on casual helping, $b = 0.052, t(367) = 0.898, p = 0.370$. Here again, the model with the two interaction terms did not explain further variance, $F(2, 363) = 0.968, p = 0.381, \Delta R^2 = 0.004$; goal \times SVO: $b = 0.049, t(365) = 0.338, p = 0.735$; control 1 \times SVO: $b = 0.167, t(365) = 1.301, p = 0.194$. Yet, the slope of SVO in control condition 1 reached statistical significance, $b = 0.156, t(365) = 2.000, p = 0.047$, whereas the slope in control

condition 2, $b = -0.111$, $t(365) = -0.112$, $p = 0.911$, and the goal condition, $b = 0.037$, $t(365) = 0.368$, $p = 0.713$, did not. Inspection of the graphs (see Figure 5) revealed that proselves' helping behavior in the prosocial goal condition laid in between the helping behavior of proselves in the two control conditions. However, as people showed more prosocial values, the scores of helping behavior reached similar levels across conditions. This is clearly not in line with our initial hypothesis, as we assumed higher (and not equal) scores on prosocial behavior in the prosocial goal condition compared to control condition 2. However, as people showed more prosocial values, the scores of helping behavior reached similar levels across conditions. This is clearly not in line with our initial hypothesis, as we assumed higher (and not equal) scores on prosocial behavior in the prosocial goal condition compared to control condition 2.

Exploratory Mediation Analysis for Goal Inference. We tested the same mediation model as in Study 2 with the goal condition (vs. control 1) as IV, goal inference as mediator, prosocial behavior as DV, and SVO as moderator on the direct and the indirect paths leading to prosocial behavior. We computed goal inference scores by adding the prosocial-related answers (coded with 1) of the three manipulation check items for the goal condition and control 1 condition. The more prosocial people are, the more their inference of observed prosocial behavior should lead to their own prosocial behavior. However, this is not what we found in the mediation analysis: It revealed that although the path between the goal condition

Figure 5. Prosocial Behavior as a function of SVO in Study 3. Separate lines signify conditions. Shades depict 95% CIs. Higher density of the scatter signifies higher concentration of data. Vertical dashed line separates “proselfs” (left) from “prosocials” (right).

and goal inference was significant, $b = 1.515$, $t(229) = 17.509$, $p < 0.001$, goal inference did not interact with SVO to predict prosocial behavior in a substantial manner, $b = -0.139$, $t(226) = 1.862$, $p = 0.064$. Contrary to Study 2, the two main effect slopes of the goal condition and inference just reached significance, goal: $b = 5.550$, $t(226) = 2.016$, $p = 0.045$, inference: $b = -2.708$, $t(226) = -2.029$, $p = 0.044$, but SVO did not, $b = 0.104$, $t(226) = 1.527$, $p = 0.128$. Moreover, the marginally significant inference \times SVO effect was indicative for higher scores of inference leading to less prosocial behavior the more prosocially oriented people were (for the full model description, see OSF). The interaction term of the direct path did likewise not reveal an effect, $b = -0.081$, $t(226) = 0.481$, $p = 0.631$.

In sum, the large sample did not confirm any of the hypotheses—neither the expected effect of the goal condition or the goal condition by SVO interaction, nor the previously found effect of SVO alone could explain prosocial helping behavior. Moreover, the mediation over explicit goal inference did not contribute to our understanding of the goal contagion effect.

Meta-Analysis

Even though goal contagion is an established effect in the literature (Aarts et al., 2004, 2008; Custers and Aarts, 2010), we did not find any evidence for it in any of our three studies. Furthermore, results were rather mixed for the predictive power of SVO on prosocial behavior: we found marginally

significant (Study 1) and significant (Study 2) SVO effects, but those effects did not replicate in Study 3.

To be able to come to a more conclusive interpretation of these results, we decided to reanalyze the effects of goal manipulation and SVO across all three studies in two random-effects meta-analyses using the R package *metafor* (Viechtbauer, 2010). To align the design of Study 3 to the design of the first two studies, we excluded all participants from control condition 2 (the whale video) in Study 3. We used partial correlation coefficients as effect sizes and extracted their bootstrap standard errors (with 10,000 iterations). Before running the analyses, we set equivalence-test margins to $\Delta r = \pm 0.10$. In line with Cohen (1988), we reasoned that an effect, which explains less than 1% of variance, could be deemed too small to be relevant beyond experimental settings. Across studies we reached a relatively large cumulated sample ($N = 519$). However, sufficient power for the equivalence test of $1 - \beta > 0.80$ was achieved at slightly larger bounds of $\Delta r = \pm 0.13$ (Julious, 2004; Lakens, 2017).

Results of the meta-analyses are summarized in two forest plots in Figure 6. They show that the tiny effect of the goal manipulation, $r = 0.01$, does not differ significantly from zero and neither the upper, nor the lower bound of the 95% CI cross the equivalence bounds of $\Delta r = \pm 0.10$ (and ± 0.13). Those results do not leave much room for speculation about any potential effect of goal contagion within the scope of our studies: participants' prosocial behavior was virtually unaffected by the manipulation material. For SVO, there is a different picture. Despite the insignificant and high-powered effect in Study 3, the summary effect of SVO, $r = 0.12$, remains

outside of the equivalence-test margins and the lower bound of its 95% *CI* does not overlap with zero. Thus, dispositional SVO was predictive for helping behavior across studies.

General Discussion

The investigation of determinants of prosocial behavior is a worthwhile endeavor within the psychological sciences as it has profound implications for the improvement of interpersonal relations, which could in the long run affect the societal level as whole.

Looking at the cognitive process of goal contagion—the adoption of a goal following the observation and inference of goal-directed behavior—was therefore reasonable, as previous research indicated that this phenomenon can be applied to a broad range of goals. A selection of goals encompasses earning money, casual sex, cooperative and competitive behavior, and health-conscious behaviors. Moreover, there was some limited evidence for goal contagion on prosocial behavior (Dik and Aarts, 2007).

Building onto this research, we performed three studies investigating the contagion of prosocial goals. These studies aimed at demonstrating that these kinds of goals can be activated in participants when they observe someone intending to provide help to another person. Empirically, we hypothesized that participants observing a prosocial goal in another person's behavior would be more likely to provide their help in a different kind of situation. Moreover, we tested the hypothesis that the contagion of prosocial goals is moderated by participants' SVO. We assumed that the more

SVO
 $Q(2) = 3.204, p = .202$

<i>Summary Effect</i>	.12 [.02; .21]
<i>Study 1</i>	.16 [.01; .32]
<i>Study 2</i>	.19 [.04; .34]
<i>Study 3</i>	.05 [-.05; .14]

GOAL
 $Q(2) = 0.207, p = .902$

<i>Summary Effect</i>	.01 [-.07; .09]
<i>Study 1</i>	-.02 [-.19; .15]
<i>Study 2</i>	-.01 [-.16; .15]
<i>Study 3</i>	.02 [-.08; .13]

Figure 6. Meta-analyses for SVO (panel A) and Goal (vs. control 1; panel B) on prosocial behavior; point-estimates are partial correlation coefficients controlled for Goal and SVO, respectively; 95% CIs are based on bootstrapped SEs; summary effects (\diamond) are based on random-effects models; vertical dashed lines are equivalence bands of $\Delta r = \pm 0.10$, which were defined after data collection; sample sizes: $n_{S1} = 126$, $n_{S2} = 162$, $n_{S3} = 231$; control condition 2 was omitted from the analysis. Q refers to heterogeneity across studies.

prosocial participants are oriented, the stronger the goal contagion effect. Our data did not verify any of these hypotheses. In none of the three studies did we find a goal contagion effect or a moderation by SVO. In addition, exploratory mediation analyses did not reveal an influence of explicit goal inference on the adoption of the prosocial goal, either. What we observed, however, was that the more prosocially participants were oriented the more often they provided help to others.

What are possible reasons for our studies not yielding the expected effects? First, one might argue that the manipulation materials were insufficient. However, there are reasons to doubt this explanation. In Study 1, we used short vignettes, in which the main character provided help to another person in an everyday situation in the goal condition. Those texts were inspired by other goal contagion studies and were similar in design and length (Aarts et al., 2004; Jia et al., 2014). One could nevertheless criticize that text vignettes are too weak to elicit goal contagion. We therefore enhanced our manipulation material further. Specifically, we decided to produce video clips for Study 2 and 3, depicting similar everyday life helping situations as in Study 1. These videos provided vivid and rich observation of a person intending to help, which should foster a goal contagion effect. In Study 3, we further increased the impact of the manipulation by introducing a second control condition. Whereas the control conditions in Study 1 and 2 partially depicted a potential helping situation (which than resolved), the additional control video in Study 3 did not hint at any social interaction at all. In addition, we have empirical evidence in Study 2 and 3 that participants indeed inferred the

goal of helping to a greater extent in the goal condition than in the control condition. Given the similarity to established goal manipulations (e.g., Dik and Aarts, 2007; Loersch et al., 2008), the vividness of the material, and the strong effect of the manipulation on explicit goal inference, it seems unlikely that an insufficient manipulation is responsible for the non-significant results.

Second, one could argue that both our DVs did not allow picking up the priming effect due to goal contagion. However, we think that the lack of a goal contagion effect in our DVs is unlikely due to the measures themselves. The DVs we employed were in line with our working definition of prosociality, emphasizing casual helping behavior, where people make a decision to volunteer without strategic concerns or fearing consequences if they do not. In Study 1 and 3, we invited participants to volunteer in an additional study conducted by a student, who could not compensate them. Such tasks in which participants are asked for voluntary help are well established (Karremans et al., 2005; Twenge et al., 2007; Greitemeyer and Osswald, 2010) and have been used repeatedly in previous goal contagion studies as DV (Aarts et al., 2004, Study 3; Dik and Aarts, 2007, Experiment 3). However, asking for help directly (even though the word “help” was not used) might undermine a potential priming effect due to goal activation³. Priming might work best, if the DV is applicable but ambiguous (Loersch and Payne, 2011). Thus, even though this method picked up a goal contagion effect in a previous study (Dik and Aarts, 2007), such a blatant

³ We thank a reviewer for this suggestion.

measure might overshadow a goal contagion effect, because everybody is primed to act prosocially by the DV itself. Fortunately, this issue is addressed in Study 2, where we employed the ZPG. This game was introduced relatively recently for experimental purposes (Leiberg et al., 2011) and has also been utilized to dissect cooperative motivations and personalities (Böckler et al., 2016; but see Wilhelm et al., 2017). As participants are instructed to reach a treasure at the end of a path, the prosocial aspects of the game are more disguised than in Study 1. Furthermore, due to its flexible settings, it is one of few games enabling the measurement of spontaneous and low-cost help. Such low-cost assistance is typical for our targeted casual helping behavior, that is, situations where people usually do not worry about rewards or compensations.

Third, we think that the effects of SVO buttress the validity of our outcome variables: Although those effects were small across studies, they turned out to be robust in a small meta-analysis. This is in line with previous research, showing SVO is predictive for a diverse range of cooperative and prosocial behaviors in both experimental and real-life settings (see Bogaert et al., 2008). Hence, our studies are no exceptions.

Fourth, based on the original findings of goal contagion using similar measures (Aarts et al., 2004; Dik and Aarts, 2007; Jia et al., 2014), we were confident that the statistical power of our studies was sufficient to detect the hypothesized effect. In particular, while enhancing manipulation materials to boost the effect in theory, we increased our sample sizes successively from study to study, culminating in a large sample in Study 3. With that sample, we could have spotted a true effect of $r =$

0.15, which would have been smaller than virtually all comparable goal contagion effects reported thus far.

Besides the strengths we highlighted in the last section, there are obvious points that have to be discussed more thoroughly. A first point concerns the role of SVO. In our studies, we intentionally measured SVO first to avoid potential confounding influences by the stimulus material or the assessment of prosocial behavior. However, the concern occurred that SVO itself could have primed participants, which is why we split the assessment of SVO and the actual experiment in Study 3. SVO measurement 1 week prior to the experiment was reasonable only under the assumption that SVO is a trait concept. However, as research by Ackermann et al. (2016) as well as Pulford et al. (2016) implies, SVO can be sensitive to the situation. Thus, participants' SVO during the experimental session might differ from the one measured a week earlier. This would explain to some extent why a weaker and non-significant association between SVO and prosocial behavior was found in our Study 3. Post hoc collection of SVO or even controlling for a shift in SVO over time could be approaches to deal with this issue in the future.

Another point for discussions might be our explicit measure of goal inference for the exploratory analyses in Study 2 and 3. We think that the depiction of a clear intention to help is a strength of our manipulation and explicit goal inference, as used in prior studies (see Aarts et al., 2004), and was employed to verify that the goal is inferred. As one would expect, we did find a strong link between the goal manipulation and explicit inference. Despite goal inference not being related to prosocial behavior, this could be interpreted as a partial support of the

goal contagion model. However, according to some empirical work on the matter (e.g., Jia et al., 2014), not explicit, but implicit goal inference should mediate the goal contagion effect. In fact, an explicit attribution of a goal as the cause of another person's behavior might be indicative for participants being too aware of the fact that helping was the other person's goal and, hence, would fail to misattribute it as their own (Laurin, 2016). Because goal contagion is described as an automatic and unconscious process, future research might want to focus on implicit goal inference measures (Aarts et al., 2004, Hassin et al., 2005; but see Corcoran et al., 2019) to test the mediation process. Unfortunately, such a measurement could hardly be conducted after measuring the goal pursuit itself. In our research, we tried to minimize any disturbance between observing goal-directed behavior and showing goal pursuit. Therefore, we measured goal pursuit directly after the manipulation. However, we certainly agree that a systematic approach to quick, automatic, and implicit goal inference as a mediator would be beneficial and should be applied with equally powerful samples as in this present study.

From Present to Future Research

Prosocial behavior is worth paying attention to, as it is important on societal and interpersonal levels. This research focuses on the interpersonal level and contributes to the understanding of the contagion of prosocial goals. It shows that it is difficult to assume that a straightforward and automatic cognitive process like goal contagion could foster peoples' prosocial behavior.

For some this might not come as a surprise, because former research came to different conclusions about the determinants of prosociality. For instance, prominent lines of research often assumed rather deliberative models (e.g., Latané and Darley, 1970), involving several cognitive steps until an individual decides to provide help in certain situations to anonymous others. Other research suggested empathic concern, perspective taking, identification with the others' goal or elevation as cognitive and emotional drivers of prosocial behavior (e.g., Batson, 1981; Haidt, 2003; Tusche et al., 2016; Michael and Székely, 2017). And even other research highlighted group norms, partly as evolutionary preferences and explained helping by the motivation to avoid punishment (Fehr and Gächter, 2002; Silk and House, 2016; Tomasello, 2016; see also Nook et al., 2016). As described in the method sections in more detail, we deliberately did not include most of those factors in our manipulation materials. We did so due to our specific interest in goal contagion and how it could uniquely elicit prosocial behavior. However, given our results one might wonder whether minimizing all those factors also minimized the likelihood of any prosocial behavior.

One possible conclusion of our research might then be that prosocial behavior is no suitable goal to be adopted following a pure goal contagion process including behavioral observation and goal inference. However, foreclosing any effect of goal contagion might be premature, as we focused only on a very specific type of prosocial behavior and it likely hinges on the mediating role of implicit goal inference, which we did not address.

As a wide array of elicited goals and moderating conditions becomes apparent in the goal contagion literature, we would recommend a meta-analytic evaluation thereof to identify generalizable differences across studies. Future research on prosocial goal contagion might then build on those findings, while taking predictors into account that showed reliable effects in other areas, such as emotions and norms (see introduction).

Regarding SVO, our final study yielded a non-significant correlation with prosocial behavior. We argue that this finding should not be overinterpreted, as it was not the confirmatory aspect of this research, the direction of the effect turned out as one would expect and the meta-analytic summary effect was in favor of SVO being predictive for casual helping as we define it. Nonetheless, the associations of SVO and casual helping and potential boundary conditions might spark interest to be pursued further.

Furthermore, other theories on prosocial traits would be worth paying attention to in order to account for more aspects of a prosocial personality in the context of the contagion of prosocial goals. Potentially, research on moral foundations (Graham et al., 2009; Haidt, 2012) and agreeableness from the Big 5 personality traits (Habashi et al., 2016) is worth mentioning here: the authors of those studies apprehend prosocial personality and traits as more complex rather than unidimensional constructs. They could also present some evidence that relations between those traits and prosocial tendencies might partly depend—yet again—on intermediary emotional processes. Thus, including these traits in future research on prosocial goal contagion could be promising.

Conclusion

Overall, our research showed that the cognitive mechanisms of goal contagion might not be sufficient to elicit prosocial behavior in a person observing every day helping. Even though observers inferred the prosocial goal, they did not act on it when given the opportunity. For now, it remains unclear whether goal contagion is limited to specific kinds of goals—not including a prosocial goal—or whether other factors hindered the effect in our studies. However, we think that once future research has established reliable moderators and mediators within the process, a richer and more comprehensive picture can be drawn of goal contagion.

Chapter 3

Is there Goal Contagion for the Goal to Earn Money?

This chapter is based on the following manuscript:

Corcoran, K., Brohmer, H., Eckerstorfer, L. V., & Macher, S. (2020). When your Goals Inspire my Goals: The Role of Effort, Personal Value, and Inference in Goal Contagion. Stage 2 Registered Report submitted at *Comprehensive Results in Social Psychology* [Stage 1: <https://osf.io/8qtfk/>]

Minor changes in this chapter compared to the manuscript concern the layout and are not content-related. They were communicated to and approved by the co-authors.

Introduction

The social environment has a great impact on peoples' behavior. Even though we tend to underestimate the influence of our social surroundings (Ross, 1977), there is plenty of evidence that people conform to the behavior of others. This influence could be based on normative or informational social influence (Cialdini, 2003), observational learning (Bandura, 1977), imitation (Meltzoff & Moore, 1989), mimicry (Chartrand & Lakin, 2013), or because others serve as inspiring role models (Morgenroth, Ryan, & Peters, 2015).

In cases of mimicry and imitation, people closely model the observed behavior. However, this is not always true. For example, in the famous Bobo-doll experiment by Albert Bandura (1963) it became clear that children not only directly imitate the aggressive behavior of the role model, like kicking the doll through the room. They also showed new kinds of aggressive behavior, like pointing a gun at the doll. Thus, observing another person's behavior might increase the likelihood of showing the exact same behavior, or the likelihood of showing a somewhat related behavior. But how are these different types of behavior related to each other?

Sometimes, two different behaviors are related because both are means for the same goal. Kicking a doll and pointing a gun at the doll both indicate the intention to "harm" the doll. Observing the behavior of other people therefore might not only trigger expression of the same behavior, but also the adoption of the goal that the other person pursues with this behavior. This process has been coined goal contagion (Aarts, Gollwitzer, & Hassin, 2004).

If we think about the power of the social environment, goal contagion is interesting to consider for several reasons. First, goal contagion elicits goal-directed behavior that is highly flexible and persistent. People can adjust their behavior to reach the goal to given opportunities and circumstances (Gollwitzer & Moskowitz, 1996). Even if it is not possible to imitate the behavior of the inspirational other directly, there might be opportunities for alternative behavior to pursue the goal. Second, activated goals tend to influence behavior over a longer period. Once a goal is activated, it directs attention and behavior toward goal pursuit until it is fulfilled or suppressed by other, competing goals (Moskowitz, 2002). Finally, goal-directed behavior can occur automatically, outside of peoples' awareness and without recruiting additional cognitive resources (Chartrand & Bargh, 1996). Thus, goal contagion is a potential tool to elicit prolonged goal-directed behavior automatically.

In an initial study on goal contagion by Aarts et al. (2004), participants read about a student who is looking forward to a vacation with his friends and uses the remaining time to either work on a farm or volunteer at a community center. Working on a farm implies the goal to earn money. Thus, when later given the opportunity to earn an extra income themselves, the participants in this condition eagerly took the opportunity. Participants were inspired by the observation of the other's behavior and adjusted their own behavior accordingly. However, such a goal contagion process does not occur under all circumstances.

Several moderators have been identified which might strengthen or weaken goal contagion. For example, in the

study on earning money (Aarts et al., 2004), only those people were infected for whom this goal had a high value because they were in a high need for money. Other moderators are for example psychological distance (Wessler & Hansen, 2016), social acceptability (Aarts et al., 2004), group membership (Loersch, Aarts, Keith Payne, & Jefferis, 2008), the effort of the observed behavior (Dik & Aarts, 2007), gratitude (Jia, Lee, & Tong, 2015) or social power (Jia, Koh, & Tan, 2018). In the present research, we want to take a closer look at the effects of moderators on goal contagion. In particular, we argue that there are at least two classes of moderators that unfold their effects in two distinct ways. This distinction becomes possible because goal contagion is conceptualized as a two-step process and a moderator might alter either the first, or the second step.

The first step of people is to infer a goal from the observed behavior. Research on spontaneous trait inferences and on automatic internal attribution indicate that people often, but not exclusively (Ham & Vonk, 2003), consider internal causes for other people's behavior. These cognitive inferences occur fast, unconsciously, and without intention (Hassin, Bargh, & Uleman, 2002). Because goals direct and motivate behavior (Gollwitzer & Oettingen, 2012), goals are likely internal causes. Even young children are able to automatically infer the goals from other people's behavior (Hassin, Aarts, & Ferguson, 2005). Thus, when seeing the model kicking the doll, the children might automatically infer that the person's goal is to harm the doll. The second step involves adopting the goal and pursuing it. Research on goal contagion indicates that behavior observation does not only activate the corresponding goal in the observers' mind, it also motivates them to engage in

behavior to pursue this goal themselves. Consistent with research on unconscious goal pursuit (Custers & Aarts, 2010) this step occurs in a quick and automatic fashion outside conscious awareness (Laurin, 2016).

Taken together, goal contagion describes an automatic effect of observation on goal activation or goal pursuit that is mediated by goal inference (Custers & Aarts, 2010). A moderator might therefor either influence the likelihood by which an observer infers from the behavior on the pursued goal (goal inference) or it might influence to what extent the inferred goal activates this goal as personal goal of the observer and initiates goal-directed behavior (goal adoption). So far, only very little research focuses on explaining the influence of moderators in more detail and specifying which part of the process is influenced.

One exception to this shortcoming is research on effort. Dik and Aarts (2007, 2008) demonstrate that effort does not only moderate the effect of observation on behavior, but also on goal inference. In their studies (Dik & Aarts, 2007), participants observed the movements of geometric shapes in an animated movie. The scene depicts a small ball trying to free a kite that is stuck in a tree. A big ball enters the scene and approaches a square with four closed doors containing a ladder. Effort was manipulated by the number of doors the big ball tries to open to reach the ladder in the square and the accessibility of helping related words in a word completion and a reaction time task served as indicator for automatic goal inference. As expected, the more doors the big ball tried, the more accessible helping related words were in the observers' mind. In a third experiment, participants had indicated their

willingness to help (filling out an extra questionnaire without additional payment) after watching the animated movie. Again, the more effort the big ball showed in the movie, the higher participants' willingness to help. This series of experiments strongly implies that effort moderates the effect of goal contagion, because it moderates the first step in the process, which is goal inference.

It is less clear at which step the other moderators influence the process of goal contagion. Gratitude, for example, might increase goal inference, because “gratitude involves a heightened sensitivity toward social others’ experiences” (Jia, Tong, & Lee, 2014, p. 749). However, gratitude might in addition strengthen goal adoption. Gratitude nurtures fruitful relationships and brings people together (Algoe, Haidt, & Gable, 2008). To ease coordinated actions, automatically adopting the goals of others would be helpful (Jia et al., 2014). Value, on the other hand, might specifically increase goal adoption. In other words, the higher the value of a goal, the more a person considers reaching the goal to be beneficial (Locke, 1969; Tang, Chen, & Sutarso, 2008) and the more intensively she pursues a goal (Gollwitzer & Oettingen, 2012). For example, a person might infer the goal to earn money when observing a student who is working on a farm, but their own low need for money might prevent them to adopt this goal and act on it. Finally, socially unacceptable behavior might decrease goal contagion despite increasing goal inference. Because strong external causes like social norms seem unlikely for socially unacceptable behavior, internal causes like goals might readily be inferred. If socially unacceptable behavior leads nevertheless to little goal contagion (Aarts et al., 2004),

strong effects in the opposite direction in the second step (goal adoption) have to take place. Overall, we still know very little about the mechanisms by which certain moderators shape the goal contagion process.

To disentangle an effect on goal inference from an effect on goal adoption, we need to separate the two steps of goal contagion by measuring goal inference. Unfortunately, the basic mediation model was rarely tested and no established goal inference measure within the framework of goal contagion exists yet.

One difficulty arises out of the distinction between explicit and implicit goal inference. Apparently, explicit goal inference does not necessarily mediate goal contagion. In the study by Dik and Aarts (2007), participants observed a big ball “trying to help” a small ball. Afterwards, participants indicated their willingness to fill out an extra questionnaire. To assess goal inference, they were asked whether they thought that the big ball wanted to help. Interestingly, including this explicit goal attribution measure as covariate into the analysis did not alter the effect of the video on participants’ willingness to help. Thus, goal attribution did not mediate goal contagion. Dik and Aarts (2007) conclude that such an explicit goal attribution measure might not capture the implicit goal inference that is part of automatic goal contagion.

Instead of asking people about the goal of the other person, one might incorporate an implicit goal inference measure. There is one study, in which implicit goal inference seems to mediate goal pursuit. Jia et al. (2014) used the classic earning money goal and assessed participants’ accessibility of money-related words with a lexical decision task. In this study, the goal

contagion effect was indeed mediated by accessibility of money-related words. However, there are downsides to using implicit measures when trying to capture goal inference.

Implicit measures like lexical-decision tasks or word completion tasks (Dik & Aarts, 2007; Jia et al., 2014) do not differentiate between goal inference, goal activation/accessibility, and construct accessibility. Even though goal inference necessarily leads to goal accessibility (if one infers that another person works to pursue the goal of earning money, the goal of earning money will become accessible), goal inference refers to the goal of the other person, whereas goal accessibility does not differentiate between personal goals or goals of other people. Therefore, it is not surprising that in the framework of goal contagion, goal accessibility is sometimes used to measure goal adoption (e.g., Jia et al., 2014, Study 3) and sometimes used to measure goal inference (Dik & Aarts, 2007, Experiment 1). The differentiation between goal accessibility and construct accessibility is also fuzzy. If a goal is activated, the corresponding construct is accessible (Kruglanski et al., 2002): an active goal of earning money should make words like “money”, “wealth”, “rich” more accessible. However, such words would also be more accessible if one merely thinks about the construct money, without having the actual goal to earn money. Thus, measures like lexical decision tasks or word completion tasks might have the advantage to be implicit, but they have the disadvantage to be less diagnostic for goal inference.

Another difficulty of measuring goal inference as mediator for the automatic goal contagion process is the point of measurement. Ideally, one would want to assess goal inference

between manipulating the observed behavior and measuring goal adoption because mediation is inherently causal (Baron & Kenny, 1986). However, explicit goal inference measures could easily interrupt or disturb the automatic process, because participants would explicitly think about the goal of the observed person, or it would at least shift the process into consciousness. Therefore, such measures have to be conducted after goal adoption. It seems to be less risky to implement implicit measures at the point of mediation within the process. However, depending on the task, the implicit measurement might potentially prime a certain construct and thereby reduce or even override an effect of the goal manipulation on goal adoption. For example, if all participants work on a lexical decision task including several words related to money, the construct money might be primed by the task and influence subsequent behavior (Weingarten et al., 2016). Thus, neither explicit nor implicit measures of goal inference are ideal to capture goal inference as mediator of the automatic goal contagion process. Even though this is not the main purpose of the present research, we will address this issue and explore several measurements.

Our main goal is to understand better under which circumstances people are inspired by others, take over their goals, and start pursuing these goals themselves. Therefore, we have to acknowledge the complexity of this process. Goal contagion could be powerful, because it unfolds automatically and results in flexible and persistent goal pursuit. However, it is also vulnerable. Two crucial steps are necessary, goal inference and goal adoption, and both could be interrupted.

We assume that some moderators mostly influence the first step, whereas others unfold their effect at the second step.

To shed light on this issue, we will focus on two moderators: effort and goal value. Effort is an expression of how much value the observed person places on the goal, whereas goal value focuses on the observer's perspective. Both moderators should make a goal more contagious, but the precise mechanisms might differ. The effort the observed person puts into a behavior shall make goal inference more likely. As has been demonstrated by Dik and Aarts (2007), the manipulation of effort facilitates goal inference. However, once the goal is correctly inferred, effort might have little effect on goal adoption. On the other hand, the value of a certain goal might strengthen the goal adoption step because it accurately represents something that the observer considers to be beneficial and valuable. However, the value the observer sees in a goal might have little influence on the inference of the other person's goal from his or her behavior (Aarts et al., 2004, Study 6). Thus, even though effort and personal goal value both moderate goal contagion, they might do so in a very different way.

A second aim of our research is to provide empirical evidence for the assumed two-step model and the mediation via goal inference. We assess automatic goal inference and include it into the statistical model in order to differentiate between moderators that alter the effect of the observed behavior on goal inference (like effort) and moderators that alter the effect of goal inference on goal adoption (like goal value). In our research, we will explore and combine several methods to measure automatic goal inference.

Study 1a: Influence of behavior observation and effort on goal inference

In the first study, we focused on the first step of goal contagion: goal inference. Similar to the classic study by Aarts et al. (2004), we manipulated the implied goal of the observed behavior by either describing the protagonist as planning to work (implying the goal to earn money) or to volunteer. In this study, we wanted to ensure that the behavior descriptions indeed produce the implied goal inferences. In addition, we manipulated effort as the crucial moderator in this step. If somebody is planning to work, an observer should infer the goal of earning money and especially so, if the protagonist shows high effort. We also included two measures for goal value, even though we did not expect an effect on goal inference. We used need for money as situational goal value like in Aarts and colleagues (2004) and we added greed for money (see Seuntjens, van de Ven, Zeelenberg, & van der Schors, 2016) to take dispositional goal value into account. However, we only used those measures for exploratory analyses.

Methods and Procedure

We preregistered this and the following two studies in the OSF⁴. All materials and data are also accessible via this link. This study was approved by the university's ethics committee and written informed consent was obtained of each participant in compliance with the principles contained in the European

⁴ <https://osf.io/ef59b/>

Federation of Psychologists' Associations Meta Code of Ethics and in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (this procedure was identical for all other studies mentioned in this article).

Materials. To manipulate the goal, we presented participants with a text about a same-sex student who was planning to either work in a supermarket (goal: earning money) or to volunteer as an intern in a community center (control). In the high effort condition, the student expected to invest extra time in evenings and on weekends, which is out of the question in the low effort condition. The texts can be found in the OSF. Previously to this study, we had tested other versions of these texts, which were more closely modelled after Aarts and colleagues (2004) and contained information about an upcoming vacation with friends. Because an insufficient number of participants in our sample inferred the goal of earning money if the student was planning to work in the supermarket (36%; $N = 327$; further information in the “pilot study” folder in the OSF), we omitted direct references to alternative goals (like going on a vacation or spending time with friends).

Directly after reading the texts, we administered the goal inference task. Based on the assumption that explicit goal attribution is a stronger indicator of automatic goal inference if people spontaneously perceive and report this goal, this task consisted of two components. First, participants answered an open *spontaneous goal inference* question (“What do you think Stefanie is trying to achieve?”). Answers were coded with 2 if indicating the goal of earning money and with 1 if not. Second

– on the next page – we listed the target goal (earning money) and four distractors (job experience, self-fulfillment, life satisfaction, and work-life balance). Participants rated the likelihood by which the student pursued each of these goals (*explicit goal inference*, 1 “not at all likely” to 9 “very likely”). By multiplying spontaneous with explicit goal inference for the target goal, we created a measure for *automatic goal inference*⁵, in which the spontaneous measure served as a weight for the explicit measure.

Next, we measured perceived *effort* with two questions, $r(N = 160) = .49$, (e.g., “How much effort will the work require?”; from 1 “not at all” to 9 “very much”). Finally, we included two measures capturing the value of the goal to earn money. Like Aarts et al. (2004), we assessed people’s *need for money* by asking about people’s financial situation (“Do you have enough money in everyday life at the moment?”; from 1 “not at all” to 9 “absolutely” – reversed). In addition, we measured *greed for money* with an altered dispositional greed scale (Seuntjens et al., 2016). Participants indicated on 9-point scales to what extent they agreed with the following items: “I think one can never have enough money”, “Actually, money is quite important to me” and “Even if I have a job, I always think about how I could earn more money” (Cronbach’s $\alpha = .74$).

⁵ In the preregistration, we planned to code spontaneous goal inference with 1, if participants report the goal to earn money, and with 0 otherwise. However, this resulted into an artificial skew in the distribution of the automatic goal inference variable, because the vast majority of participants in the control condition would score 0. We therefore decided to change the coding scheme to 1 and 2. All further analyses are based on that coding. Results for both coding schemes showed a similar pattern and can be found in the OSF.

Design, Power, and Sample

We realized a 2 (goal: earning money vs. control) \times 2 (effort: high vs. low) between-subjects design. Sample size was determined a priori (Faul, Erdfelder, Lang, & Buchner, 2007), assuming power $1 - \beta = 0.8$, α err probability = .05 and a small effect of $r = .230$ ($f = .236$), which yielded $N = 151$. The effect estimation was based on the smallest reported effect of effort on goal inference (Dik & Aarts, 2007). To account for potential dropouts, we decided to increase the sample size to $N = 160$. We recruited students of the University of Graz on campus and randomly allocated them to one of the four conditions. All material was presented on paper. Participants' mean age was 22.35 years ($SD = 2.78$) and 57.5% were female.

Results

Manipulation Check. In a first step, we checked with the spontaneous goal inference measure how often the goal of earning money was correctly reported in the earning money condition and incorrectly reported in the control condition. In the earning money condition, 83.8% reported the goal, compared to 8.8% in the control condition, $\chi^2(1) = 90.50$, $p < .001$, $OR = 53.75$. Next, we checked the effort manipulation. A 2 (goal: earning money vs. control) \times 2 (effort: high vs. low) between-subjects ANOVA with perceived effort as dependent variable revealed the hypothesized main effect of effort, $F(1,156) = 142.54$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .477$. Participants perceived the student's behavior as more effortful when it was described as such – regardless of the goal condition (high effort: $M = 6.12$, $SD = 1.34$; low effort: $M = 3.54$, $SD = 1.54$). The interaction was not significant, $F(1,156) = 1.93$, $p = .167$, $\eta_p^2 =$

.012, but people who read about a student planning to volunteer in a community center perceived his/her behavior as more effortful ($M = 5.23$, $SD = 2.03$) than people who read about a student planning to work in a supermarket ($M = 4.37$, $SD = 1.74$), $F(1,156) = 18.39$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .105$.

Confirmatory Analysis. To test if the student's effort facilitates goal inference in the earning money condition, we submitted the data to a 2 (goal: earning money vs. control) \times 2 (effort: high vs. low) between-subjects ANOVA with automatic goal inference as dependent variable. We found a significant two-way interaction of goal and effort, $F(1, 156) = 10.87$, $p = .001$, $\eta^2 = .065$, and a significant main effect of goal manipulation, $F(1,156) = 327.99$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .678$. There was no main effect of effort, $F(1, 156) = 0.67$, $p = .414$, $\eta^2 = .004$. The effect of the goal manipulation was apparent in both effort conditions. Bonferroni-corrected comparisons revealed that participants inferred the goal of earning money more strongly when earning money was the actual goal (high effort: $M_1 = 16.25$, $SD_1 = 3.50$; low effort: $M_2 = 14.73$, $SD_2 = 4.48$) than when it was not (high effort: $M_3 = 3.08$, $SD_3 = 2.29$; low effort: $M_4 = 5.61$, $SD_4 = 4.75$), $F(1, 156) = 226.32$, $p < .001$, $d_{M1-M3} = 4.445$; $F(1, 156) = 111.11$, $p < .001$, $d_{M2-M4} = 1.973$. Furthermore and in line with our hypothesis, participants in the earning money condition inferred the goal marginally more often when the student showed high effort, compared to when he or she showed low effort, $F(1, 156) = 3.07$, $p = .082$, $d_{M1-M2} = 0.380$. The manipulation of effort in the control condition produced a significant effect in the opposite direction, $F(1, 156) = 8.47$, $p = .004$, $d_{M4-M3} = 0.674$.

Exploratory analyses. To see if need for money or greed influences goal inference, we calculated two regression models with goal (effect coded), effort (effect coded), need or greed (centered on the mean) and all interaction terms as predictors and automatic goal inference as criterion. In these analyses, none of the three-way interactions yielded an effect (see OSF). However, in the greed model, Goal \times Greed predicted goal inference, $b = -1.76$, $t(152) = -2.64$, $p = .009$. The goal manipulation effect on goal inference was stronger for people low in greed, $M-1SD$: $b = 12.57$, $t(152) = 14.62$, $p < .001$, than for people high in greed, $M+1SD$: $b = 9.28$, $t(152) = 10.49$, $p < .001$. Furthermore, the greedier people were in the control condition, the more they inferred the goal of earning money, $b = 1.45$, $t(152) = 3.05$, $p = .003$. This relation was not significant in the earning money condition, $b = -0.32$, $t(152) = -0.67$, $p = .503$.

Discussion

Our behavior descriptions successfully affected the perceived goal and perceived effort. More than 80% of the participants spontaneously reported the goal correctly in the earning money condition compared to less than 10% who falsely mentioned this goal in the control condition. Furthermore, participants perceived the work of the student who was willing to work extra time as more effortful. Crucially, effort facilitates goal inference when goal-relevant behavior is observed. This supports our main hypothesis that effort influences goal contagion because it moderates goal inference.

We also expected that the value of the goal does not alter goal inference. In line with this hypothesis, the effect of the goal manipulation on goal inference was not stronger the higher people's need or greed was. It only seems to be the case, that people with higher greed infer a goal to earn money to a greater extent even if the other person does not show any behavior pursuing such a goal – as it was the case in our control condition. It is also noteworthy that the need for money revealed a floor effect with two thirds of the participants scoring in the lower third of a 9-point scale. This indicates that need for money might not capture variation for goal value in our population. Even though null effects have to be interpreted cautiously, these results are in line with the hypothesis that the effect of goal value on goal contagion (Aarts et al., 2004) emerges because the value of the goal alters goal adoption – the second step in the goal contagion process.

Study 1b: Including implicit goal accessibility in the goal inference measure

Even though Study 1a confirms a successful manipulation of goal and effort, our measurement of goal inference seems to be suboptimal for several reasons. First, we could not use the planned coding of spontaneous goal inference and furthermore, the effect of effort in the goal-relevant condition was only a tendency. Second, one could argue that the inference measure contained no real implicit component, which is required for automatic processes. Third, one could question whether the product term of spontaneous and explicit goal inference is capturing the underlying psychological

processes accurately. Fourth, to test the full two-step model of goal contagion it would be preferable to have a measure for the mediator goal inference that can be administered before the dependent variable goal adoption. However, administering the measure from Study 1a at this position would interrupt an automatic goal contagion effect, because we explicitly ask about the goal to earn money.

Therefore, we wanted to replicate the previous study with an additional implicit goal accessibility indicator. If participants automatically infer the goal of earning money, this goal and the concept of money should be rendered accessible (Aarts et al., 2004; Dijksterhuis & Aarts, 2010). Thus, the main goal of this study was to refine our automatic goal inference measure. We obtained data about spontaneous goal inference, explicit goal inference, and implicit goal accessibility, which – together – should be capturing automatic goal inference. Changing the measure for spontaneous goal inference from dichotomous to continuous enabled us to check whether all three load on a single automatic goal inference factor. Thus, while keeping the manipulation identical to Study 1a, we used a structural equation model to analyze the influence of goal and effort (and its interaction) on automatic goal inference, which was a latent variable indicated by implicit goal accessibility (IMP), spontaneous goal inference (SPON), and explicit goal inference (EXP).

Methods and Procedure

We conducted Study 1b online by using Questback Unipark (QuestBack GmbH). The estimated time frame to complete this study was three weeks and we concluded it in

two weeks. Participants from the student population first gave their informed consent and then answered basic demographic questions (age, gender, status as student).

Goal manipulation. Participants read the earning money vs. control texts that we already applied in Study 1a. The text appeared for 30 seconds on the screen. Subsequently, participants indicated whether they were able to read the text in the allotted time (“yes” or “no”).

Indicators for Automatic Goal Inference. To assess *implicit goal accessibility* (IMP), we presented participants with a word completion task directly after they read the goal manipulation texts (Dik & Aarts, 2007). Using a seemingly random letter, participants had to generate as many one-syllable words as possible within 30 seconds and type them into an answer field. All participants received the letter “G”, because our target word associated with the goal to earn money was “Geld” (“money” in German). The position of the target word within the string of produced words indicates the accessibility of the goal. Similar to Dik and Aarts (2007), we calculated participants’ relative score by dividing the position of the target word (counting backwards from the last word) by the total amount of produced words. For example, if “Geld” was mentioned on the second position in a list of seven words, participants would have received a score of $6 / 7 = 0.857$. In that way, higher scores indicated higher goal accessibility. This measure was \sqrt{x} -transformed.

Participants then answered an open question for *spontaneous goal inference* (SPON) as before but with the addition “to list

everything that comes to your mind”. Similar to Aarts and colleagues (2004, Study 6), we expected to receive a list of possible goals from the participants and applied the same recalculation and ξ -transformation as for the IMP score.

Afterwards and along with the distractor items, we adopted the *Explicit goal inference (EXP)* measure from Study 1a. As the other measures, it was ξ -transformed.

Love of money. Next, we measured goal value. Because the item assessing need for money used in Study 1a revealed a floor effect and greed for money alone might be too narrow of a definition for the varying value of earning money, we replaced both measures with the importance of money subscale from the love of money questionnaire (Du & Tang, 2005). We added the word “earning” to each item to measure the value of earning money instead of the value of money itself. Our five items were “Earning money is important”, “Earning money is valuable”, “Earning money is good”, “Earning money is an important factor in the lives of all of us” and “Earning money is attractive”, which were measured on 7-point scales (higher scores = more agreement).

Manipulation check and other measures. We assessed perceived effort with the same item as in Study 1a. In addition, we included two attention check questions regarding the text (“What will the person in the text be doing during the holidays?” and “When will the person start the described activity?” with specified responses from a list). We also asked participants whether they worked on the study undisturbedly and whether they themselves would include their data into our

analysis (both “yes” or “no”). Thereafter, participants were thanked and offered a debriefing and a lottery participation via email.

Sample, Design and Power

As preregistered, we conducted a structural equation model analysis containing a 2 (goal: earning money vs. control) \times 2 (effort: low vs. high) between-subject design with automatic goal inference as latent dependent variable. We analyzed the data with a structural equation modeling approach, reporting results from Mplus 8 (Muthén & Muthén, 2010), but provide code for both Mplus and lavaan (Rosseel, 2017) in R (R Core Team, 2018) online (<https://osf.io/cdp9v/>).

We calculated the power for a liberal not-close-fit model with 9 degrees of freedom (21 variances and covariances; 12 parameters) and an alternative Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (*RMSEA*) of .08, compared to a Null *RMSEA* of .01 (MacCallum, Lee, & Brown, 2010; Preacher and Coffman, 2006). At a power of 80%, this yielded a sample size of $N = 300$. However, we were also interested in the contrast between high and low effort in the earning money condition, which yielded an effect of $d = .38$ ($f = .19$) in Study 1a. To detect this contrast, a total sample size of 440 participants (220 per goal condition) was required to reach a power of 80% at $\alpha = .05$ (Faul et al., 2007; Giner-Sorolla, 2018).

As indicated, we recruited participants via email and social media (Facebook groups). 895 persons clicked on the link to the study, 525 reached the final page and 481 were interested in the lottery. As specified beforehand, participants were excluded from the confirmatory analysis if they reported that

they had not read the manipulation text entirely within the allotted time, if they did not answer the two attention check items in the final questionnaire correctly, if they failed to complete the experiment (e.g., due to technical issues), or if they themselves encouraged us to do so. Based on these criteria, we had to exclude 101 participants from the analysis, leaving us with a final sample of $N = 380$, which laid between the two sample size calculations from above. A sensitivity analysis for the relevant low effort vs. high effort contrast in the goal group suggested that we could find a Cohen's d of .41 with this sample size, which we deemed sufficiently close to the estimate above. As expected, participants were predominantly women and university students ($n_{\text{female}} = 294$, $n_{\text{student}} = 364$, $M_{\text{age}} = 24.64$ years, $SD_{\text{age}} = 7.11$).

Results

All descriptive statistics can be found online on the OSF. As a manipulation check, we asked participants how much effort the main character in the stories would have to put in her or his work. A strong effect was found between the high effort ($M = 7.23$, $SD = 1.41$) and low effort condition ($M = 3.60$, $SD = 1.76$), $F(1, 376) = 489.08$, $p < .001$, $d = 2.30$.

Confirmatory analysis. We fitted several consecutive models, with goal and effort (both effect-coded) as well as their interaction predicting the latent variable goal inference, which consisted of IMP, SPON and EXP (all α -standardized) in different combinations. Our goal was to identify the model capturing a strong effect of our goal manipulation for goal inference, which was preferably moderated by effort.

Model 1 to 3 consisted of the two manipulations (goal vs. control and low effort vs. high effort) and their interaction (Goal \times Effort) as IVs. The three indicators for the latent construct goal inference served as DV. Model 1 contained all three indicators and showed sufficient model fit, $\chi^2(9) = 23.74$, $p = .005$, $RMSEA = .07$, 90% CI [.03; .10], $p_{RMSEA \leq .05} = .182$, $SRMR = .04$, $CFI = .96$, $TLI = .94$. $AIC = 4005.59$, $BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 4019.26$, but the interaction was only marginally significant, $b = 0.48$, $z = 1.67$, $p = .095$, and IMP did not load on inference, $\lambda_{IMP} = 0.03$, $z = 0.76$, $p = .445$. Hence, IMP was eliminated for Model 2. In this model the Goal \times Effort interaction remained marginally significant, $b = 0.50$, $z = 1.76$, $p = .078$, with both indicators loading sufficiently on inference, $\lambda_{SPON} = 0.40$, $z = 12.42$, $p < .001$; $\lambda_{EXP} = 0.51$, $z = 9.84$, $p < .001$. Moreover, most model fit criteria improved, $\chi^2(5) = 11.67$, $p = .040$, $RMSEA = .06$, 90% CI [.01; .10], $p_{RMSEA \leq .05} = .309$, $SRMR = .04$, $CFI = .98$, $TLI = .97$. $AIC = 2928.21$, $BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 2938.18$) and according to a χ^2 -difference test, Model 2 fitted significantly better, $\Delta\chi^2 = 12.07$, $SRMR = .03$, $CFI = .99$, $TLI = .94$. $AIC = 4002.08$, $BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 4020.31$; $\Delta\chi^2 = 3.44$, $\Delta df = 2$, and again none of the three Goal \times Effort interactions were statistically significant.

To see, if more parsimonious models would provide stronger effects on the key variables, we proceeded by eliminating effort and performed three more analyses similar to the previous three. Again, IMP did not load on inference in Model 4 ($\lambda_{IMP} = 0.03$, $z = 0.80$, $p = .422$; $\chi^2(2) = 7.39$, $p = .025$, $RMSEA = .09$, 90% CI [.03; .15], $p_{RMSEA \leq .05} = .140$, $SRMR = .02$, $CFI = .98$, $TLI = .95$. $AIC = 2880.48$, $BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 2888.07$), so we eliminated it. However, for the saturated

Models 5 and 6 we did not identify considerably different effects of the goal manipulation on the latent variable, $b = 2.49$, $\zeta = 8.31$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.95$, or on the three variables separately. We did find strong effects of goal on EXP, $b = 1.29$, $\zeta = 17.99$, $p < .001$, $d = 4.93$, and SPON, $b = 1.00$, $\zeta = 10.43$, $p < .001$, $d = 1.27$, but not on IMP, $b = 0.15$, $\zeta = 1.41$, $p = .160$, $d = 0.15$, so we decided to stick to the two-indicator solution of Model 2.

Exploratory Analyses. For the implicit measure, several participants came up with one-syllabus words that were indirectly related to money. Those words were “gold” and “greed” (German: “Gold” and “Gier”). We also coded the position of those words and reran the analysis for Model 1. In this model, factor loadings remained unreliable for IMP, $\lambda = -0.01$, $\zeta = -0.22$, $p = .829$, and we did not find larger effects for the interaction, $b = 0.48$, $\zeta = 1.70$, $p = .089$.

We also collected data concerning participant’s Love of Money (LOM). We reran the analysis for Model 2, but with Goal \times Effort and Goal \times LOM as a partially latent interaction (Kline, 2011, Chapter 12). Although all indicators were significantly predicted by the latent variable LOM, all λ s ≥ 0.52 , ζ s ≥ 6.82 , p s $\leq .001$, which in turn showed a statistically significant effect on inference, $b = 0.171$, $\zeta = 2.07$, $p = .038$, the LOM \times Goal interaction, $b = -0.294$, $\zeta = -2.07$, $p = .076$, indicated a slightly negative effect in the goal group with higher appreciation of money.

Figure 7. Violin plots for the three goal inference measures of Study 1b. Violins depict kernel density of the data. Black dots represent estimated means and whiskers represent the 95% confidence intervals. IMP (A), SPON (B) and EXP (C) are z-standardized.

Discussion

The primary aim of this study was to find a reliable measure for goal inference. We partially achieved this goal using a continuous version of the spontaneous goal inference measure and explicit goal inference measure as indicators. However, implicit goal accessibility did not bring about the expected loading as an implicit component of goal inference. Moreover, it was not predicted by the manipulations neither as part of the latent inference variable nor individually, as depicted in Figure 7 (panel A).

The apparent advantage of our IMP variable was that its operationalization as word completion task could be easily integrated in a complex experimental design as we have in Study 2. This way, it would have stood out from other, often more laborious setups employing cognitive measures like lexical decision tasks or dot probe paradigms. A downside of these other measures is that participants would be much longer involved, which may be detrimental to the goal manipulation, especially when behavioral measures yet have to follow. However, the word completion task did not detect differences across conditions.

The apparent floor effect (i.e., “money” was almost never mentioned) raises the question if this kind of word completion task leaves participants too many options for free associations. Possibly, words more common than “Geld” in the German language came earlier to their minds or earlier words influenced which words participants came up later with (e.g., coming up with a verb first might lead to another verb). Either way, the few times “Geld” did occur, it did not show a pattern across groups. Because false-negative findings can nevertheless

occur, we kept it in our design for Study 2 as we preregistered, but did not focus on it in the confirmatory analysis.

A second result of Study 1b is that our effort manipulation yielded the expected simple effect only in marginally significant fashion despite utilizing a sample twice as large as in Study 1a. This is notable because if an effect truly exists, one would expect it to become more apparent in larger samples. Nonetheless, we decided to keep effort and directed our attention on the Goal \times Effort interaction in the main study as the respective Model 2 showed the best model fit compared to other models. In Study 2, we tested the two moderators effort and personal goal value within the two-step model of goal contagion.

Study 2: Influence of effort and goal value on goal adoption

Using a structural equation model approach (Breitsohl, 2018), we investigated if the path from the goal manipulation (earning money vs. control) on automatic goal inference was moderated by effort and the path from automatic goal inference on goal adoption by goal value. Based on the results of Study 1a/b, we expected a main effect of the goal manipulation on automatic goal inference, but hesitated to expect a goal by effort interaction. However, effort was kept in the model as indicated in the preregistration.

Within this model, we further tested if the effect of the goal manipulation on goal adoption was mediated by automatic goal inference. Baseline measures for the dependent variables

were included as covariates. The full conceptual model is depicted in Figure 8 (upper panel).

Methods and Procedure

We conducted Study 2 in two sessions. The first session was online, using Questback Unipark (QuestBack GmbH) and the second session was in the lab using Questback Unipark and PsychoPy, version 1.85 (Peirce, 2007). This study took approximately six months to be completed, which was longer than the anticipated 10 weeks. This is largely due to the conservative exclusion criteria (see below), which resulted in the necessity to oversample substantially. We recruited from the local universities' student population. All materials were presented on a computer and are accessible via the OSF. In the first session, we measured goal value. The main part of the study took place in session two. The procedure in Session two followed Studies 1 a/b closely, but we added two additional tasks to measure goal adoption. We measured all three automatic goal inference indicators (IMP, SPON and EXP). To measure IMP, we administered the word completion task between the manipulation and the tasks assessing goal adoption, whereas SPON and EXP were assessed after the goal adoption tasks. A final questionnaire at the end of the study included manipulation checks, demographics, and additional questions.

Session one. In the first part of the study, we measured goal value with the questions from Study 1b along with some demographics (age, gender, student status) and distractor questionnaires (borrowed from Boer, 2013, and Thomas et al.,

Figure 8. Preregistered conceptual model and model comparisons. Upper panel depicts the full model with the two-step process of goal contagion; note: IMP = implicit goal accessibility (not part of the tested model in Study 2), SPON = spontaneous goal inference, EXP = explicit goal inference, LOM = love of money; lower panel depicts model comparisons, note: the full model (A) will be compared to the less complex models (B) and (C) and the least complex model (D), variables in squares are observed variables, variables in circles are latent variables, G = goal manipulation, E = effort manipulation, AI = automatic inference, V = value, B = baseline, DV = dependent variable.

2015), which we did not analyze. In the previous studies, we measured goal value after the manipulation, but there was a risk that the moderator would be influenced by the manipulation itself. Participants might read about a person trying hard to earn money, infer and adopt this goal and subsequently place more value on the goal while it is activated. We therefore decided to separate questions about goal value from the rest of the study. There were at least three days in between Session one and Session two, so that participants would not be influenced by the goal value measure.

Session two. During the second part of the study, we informed participants upon arrival that “the study contains several parts which will all take place at the computer. The exact number of tasks involved is flexible and depends on how far you will get in the allotted time frame. All of this will be explained in the instructions”. This cover story was necessary for our goal adoption measure (for a similar procedure see Aarts et al., 2004). Participants sat in front of one of several computer workstations, separated by partitions. They wore acoustic earmuffs over the course of the study.

Materials and measures for the goal and effort manipulation, implicit goal accessibility, and spontaneous as well as explicit goal inference were the same as in Study 1b.

Goal adoption. We measured goal adoption in two ways. In our first measure, we analyzed how quickly participants worked through a simple character search task to reach an opportunity for goal fulfillment. Therefore, participants were informed that the next task was about to start and if sufficient

time was left by the end of this task, participants would get “the opportunity to earn some additional income” (in German: “Möglichkeit auf einen Zusatzverdienst”) in an extra task. Similar to the task used by Aarts and colleagues (2004), the character search task is an easy mouse-clicking task that lasts about 2 minutes. We instructed participants to click on all characters of one predefined kind in a 5×5 grid of different characters. The task encompassed 15 pages with four characters to find on each page. Participants proceeded automatically from page to page. The overall working time in seconds served as dependent variable (*speed*). We took a baseline measure of participant’s performance (*speed_base*) over 5 pages (plus one test trial beforehand) in the beginning of the experimental session, which we included as covariate in the design. As in the original study by Aarts and colleagues (2004, Study 1), we also asked participants whether it was their intention to work quickly on the character search task after this task was finished. They answered this question on a 9-point scale (from 1 “not at all” to 9 “absolutely”).⁶

Our second measure of goal adoption was participants’ performance in the extra task. All participants were informed that there was enough time left to work on the extra task for additional income. Specifically, we told them that the better they performed on the upcoming symbol counting task, the more tickets they would win and the higher their chances

⁶ Both the awareness item after the character search task and the instructions of the symbol counting task were in accordance with the preregistered materials, but deviated slightly from the descriptions in the preregistered manuscript, where we did not explicitly mention the awareness item (as it is not part of the confirmatory analysis) and used a different wording of the instructions.

would be to receive an additional cash prize of 50€ (~ 60\$), determined by a raffle. In this task, participants had to count the number of identical symbols in a cloud of jumbled symbols (squares, circles and triangles) on the left-hand side of the screen as fast as possible and to write the numbers in text fields on the right hand side of the screen. Numbers ranged between 5 and 9. The next page appeared automatically once all numbers were filled in correctly. The number of pages completed within two minutes served as indicator of participants' performance. Completing one page took about 10 seconds and we programed 20 pages in total (so participants' score could range from 0 to 20). Better performance and therefore higher scores indicated greater adoption of the goal to earn money because performance determined the likelihood to win the cash price. Again, we took a baseline measure of participant's performance (number of pages completed) over 45 seconds (including a one-page test trial) in the beginning of the experimental session, which we included as covariate in the design. The full experimental set-up is depicted in Figure 9.

Manipulation check and further measures. In addition to the questions of Study 1b, we inquired participants' suspicion with three questions on three consecutive pages. We asked whether they thought the parts of the Study were connected ("yes" or "no"), whether they thought their behavior in the character search task and the symbol counting task was influenced by the text ("yes" or "no") and how they thought they were influenced by the text (text field). Only if they directly indicate that they worked quicker in part 2 or they wanted to solve more

pages in part 3, we counted that as suspicion. Finally, participants were thanked and offered a debriefing via email.

Sample and Power

We estimated the required sample size for our structural equation model (which is equivalent to a partially latent structural regression model; Kline, 2011) in a conservative manner, where we assumed only one mediating variable (e.g., IMP) to obtain a conservative sample size estimate. Subtracting the parameters (24: 8 path coefficients, 4 indicator paths [one path will be set to 1] for goal value, 4 variances, and 8 error variances) from the known elements (66 variances and covariances without the latent variables) yields 42 degrees of freedom. We used those *dfs* along with an α err rate = .05, power of 80%, an alternative *RMSEA* = .05 and Null-*RMSEA* = .01 (not-close-fit hypothesis, see Kline, 2011; MacCallum, Browne, & Sugawara, 1996) and calculated the sample size via Preacher & Coffman (2006). This yielded a sample of 297 participants. To account for a potential dropout rate, we intended to add 10% more participants. For an equal distribution of participants across groups, we preregistered a sample size of $N = 332$ participants.

During data collection, a much higher dropout rate became apparent because some participants could not be matched across the two sessions based on their anonymous self-created code or because they did not answer the SPON question with regard to the text they had read. Even after we had 400 participants in the lab, we only had usable data from $N = 228$ participants. As we looked into the data at this point, we adjusted the α error via the R package GroupSeq (Pahl, 2018;

Lakens, 2014) for multiple data peeking: the p -value for the moderated mediation effect (i.e., the effect of interest) should have been lower than .04 (with the effect in the expected direction) for the case that we would consider to stop data collection. However, this was not the case. Hence, we continued data collection to reach the full sample with the initial alpha-level.

In the end, 1461 persons clicked on the link to session one and 886 completed it. Then, 525 participants came to session two in the lab. After excluding participants according to the preregistered criteria (i.e., if they reported that they have not read the manipulation text entirely within the allotted time frame, if they did not answer the two attention check items in the final questionnaire correctly, if they could not complete the study due to technical issues, or if they indicated suspicion), we reached a final sample of $N = 300$. Our sample had a mean age of 22.04 years ($SD = 4.26$) and consisted mainly of women ($n = 222$) and students ($n = 296$)

Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistics and models can be found online (see <https://osf.io/f9xc5/>). As manipulation check, we checked if participants recognized the story character's effort, which was the case between effort conditions, $F(1, 296) = 266.32, p < .001, d = 1.88$). Participants also indicated, whether they have worked intentionally quicker in the high effort condition than in the low effort condition in the speed task, which was largely not the case, $F(1, 296) = 2.80, p = .096, d = 0.19$.

Figure 9. Experimental set-up for Study 2. Tasks in grey took part in PsychoPy, other tasks took part in Unipark (see materials <https://osf.io/zgkjt/>)

Confirmatory Analysis. We tested the main moderated-mediation model depicted in Figure 8. Because of the results of Study 1b, we included only SPON and EXP as latent variables to assess the mediator automatic goal inference for the confirmatory analyses. IMP was included in exploratory analyses. We expected that goal contagion is mediated by automatic goal inference and effort moderates the indirect path in the first step, whereas goal value moderates it in the second step. Thus, higher effort will facilitate automatic goal inference and thereby increase the goal effect on goal adoption. Goal value, on the other hand, will moderate the association between automatic goal inference and goal adoption. The higher participants' individual perceived importance of earning money, the better automatic inference of the earning money goal will predict goal adoption. Like effort, love of money representing the value of the goal shall increase the effect of the goal manipulation on goal adoption. Goal adoption refers to two different and independently measured variables, namely participants' speed in the character search task, and the number of completed pages by participants in the symbol-counting task.

We conducted those moderated mediation analyses and preregistered model comparisons (Figure 8, lower panel; see supplementary spread sheets for statistics) using MPlus (Muthén & Muthén, 2010) as it is the most suitable program for latent variable interactions, which we have in our design (Maslowsky, Jager & Hemken, 2015). The zero-order correlation between both outcome measures was large, $r = .460, p < .001$ (Cohen, 1988) and remained significant when we controlled for the baseline measures, $r = .189, p = .001$, so we

reduced the α error probability to .025 for the two analyses to account for familywise error.

Using participants' speed and symbol-counting as DVs in two full moderated-mediation models, only two model fit parameters, the *AIC* and the *BIC*, could be produced. This was due to the continuous latent variables as both exogenous and endogenous variables and latent interactions in these models. Along with path coefficients and 95% bootstrap CIs, we present the results for both DVs in Figure 10. Interpretation will therefore focus on path coefficients.

First, for the DV speed, we did not find the anticipated effects in the Model A, $AIC = 11616.92$, $BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 11638.74$. Although we replicated the main effect of the goal manipulation on the goal inference, $b = 2.53$, $z = 8.16$, $p < .001$, there was no interaction with effort, $b = 0.01$, $z = 0.06$, $p = .956$. Inference and goal value did not show an interaction effect on speed, $b = 0.72$, $z = 0.83$, $p = .407$, rendering conditional indirect effects irrelevant. There was also no direct effect from the goal manipulation on participants' speed of completing the task, $b = -0.57$, $z = -0.16$, $p = .876$. The baseline measure on speed, $b = 1.10$, $z = 6.85$, $p < .001$, as well as all indicators on their respective constructs, all $\lambda s \geq 0.48$, $z s \geq 8.81$, $p s \leq .001$, revealed significant effects even after a corrected alpha level.

Those patterns were similar for Model A of the symbol-counting task, $AIC = 7838.50$, $BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 7858.74$. Emphasizing the most important effects, there was no interaction effect between goal and effort on inference, $b = 0.01$, $z = 0.04$, $p = .966$, no interaction effect of inference and goal value on the number of pages solved in the task, $b = 0.02$,

Figure 10. Confirmatory full statistical models. Coefficients with 95% CIs are unstandardized; DVs are *speed* (upper panel; higher scores = more speed) and symbol-counting (*count*; lower panel; higher scores = more pages completed); black → indicates statistically significant effect ($p < .025$); grey → indicates non-significant effect; variances and error variances are omitted for simplicity

$\zeta = 0.40, p = .691$, and no direct goal effect on the DV, $b = -0.11, \zeta = -0.43, p = .665$.

None of the other models depicted in Figure 8 contained effects that we would describe as meaningful (see statistics and model comparisons online). Firstly, the mediator model (Figure 8, lower panel, B) did not yield a mediation for neither speed, $b = -1.87, \zeta = -0.62, p = .534$; model fit: $AIC = 3874.74, BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 3881.66, \chi^2(4) = 8.05, p = .090, RMSEA = 0.06, 90\% CI [0.00; 0.12], p_{RMSEA \leq .05} = .338, SRMR = .03, CFI = .99, TLI = .98, \Delta AIC = 7742.18, \Delta BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 7757.08$), nor number of pages solved, $b = -0.19, \zeta = -0.89, p = .372$, model fit: $AIC = 6503.04, BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 6508.89, \chi^2(4) = 6.52, p = .163, RMSEA = 0.05, 90\% CI [0.00; 0.11], p_{RMSEA \leq .05} = .463, SRMR = .03, CFI = .99, TLI = .99, \Delta AIC = 1335.46, \Delta BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 1349.85$).

Secondly, as our mediator goal inference could be criticized for being incompatible with the theory because it does not contain an implicit element, we report results from the double-moderation model highlighted in Figure 8 (lower panel, C), which does not contain inference. In this model, the moderators effort and goal value should affect the goal contagion process for the behavioral outcome measure directly (see Aarts et al., 2004; Dik & Aarts, 2007). However, this was not case. For the DV speed, $AIC = 8051.94, BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 8067.38, \Delta AIC = 3564.98, \Delta BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 3571.36$, there was no interaction of either moderator, $b_{\text{Goal} \times \text{Effort}} = 2.00, \zeta = 0.57, p = .568, b_{\text{Goal} \times \text{Value}} = 3.29, \zeta = 1.48, p = .140$, and no main effect observed, $b_{\text{Goal}} = -2.80, \zeta = -1.54, p = .123, b_{\text{Effort}} = -2.46, \zeta = -1.34, p = .180, b_{\text{Value}} = 0.88, \zeta = 0.77, p = .440$, beside a baseline effect, $b_{\text{Base}} = 1.10, \zeta = 7.10, p < .001$. This

was also true for the DV number of pages solved in the following count task, accounting for an adjusted alpha error, $b_{\text{Goal} \times \text{Effort}} = 0.27$, $\zeta = 1.03$, $p = .301$; $b_{\text{Goal} \times \text{Value}} = 0.08$, $\zeta = 0.50$, $p = .614$; $b_{\text{Goal}} = -0.29$, $\zeta = -2.17$, $p = .030$; $b_{\text{Effort}} = -0.12$, $\zeta = -0.87$, $p = .383$; $b_{\text{Value}} = -0.12$, $\zeta = -1.60$, $p = .110$; $b_{\text{Base}} = 1.48$, $\zeta = 12.00$, $p < .001$; model fit: $AIC = 6473.75$, $BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 6489.18$, $\Delta AIC = 1364.76$, $\Delta BIC_{n\text{-adjusted}} = 1369.56$).

Thirdly, a similar pattern was observed for the simple multiple regression Model D, where the goal effect was not significant for speed, $b = -0.08$, $\zeta = -1.62$, $p = .105$, and significant only without alpha correction for the DV symbol-counting, $b = -0.30$, $\zeta = -2.16$, $p = .031$. It has to be noted that both DVs showed a direction contrary to the hypothesis with control group participants being on average faster and completed more pages than participants in the goal group.

Exploratory Analyses. Beside exclusion criteria, the higher-than-expected dropout rate was caused by participants not remembering their codes from session one in which we assessed goal value and due to a misunderstanding of the spontaneous inference question in session two. Dropping these variables for exploratory purposes enables us to include $n = 78$ ($N = 378$) participants for an analysis of goal, effort and the baseline without other moderators or mediators. In this parsimonious factorial model, we did not find an effect on speed for either independent variable, $b_{\text{Goal}} = -1.79$, $z = -1.12$, $p = .263$, $d = -0.12$; $b_{\text{Effort}} = -0.83$, $\zeta = -0.52$, $p = .604$, $d = 0.05$, or their interaction, $b = 2.37$, $\zeta = 0.74$, $p = .461$. Similar small effects close to zero were observed for the number of pages solved, $b_{\text{Goal}} = -0.16$, $\zeta = -1.44$, $p = .151$, $d = -0.15$; $b_{\text{Effort}} =$

-0.06, $\zeta = -0.53$, $p = .596$, $d = -0.05$; $b_{\text{Goal} \times \text{Value}} = 0.23$, $\zeta = 0.97$, $p = .335$. The baseline remained significant in both models, $b_{\text{Speed}} = 1.16$, $\zeta = 13.95$, $p < .001$; $b_{\text{Pages}} = 1.42$, $\zeta = 14.43$, $p = .072$. The mean differences are depicted in Figure 11.

As we also collected data on the implicit measure that was utilized in Study 1b, we checked whether any evidence for an implicit inference could be found. However, we did not find an effect of the Goal \times Effort interaction on IMP, $b = 0.23$, $\zeta = 0.97$, $p = .335$, and no main effect, either, $b_{\text{Goal}} = -0.16$, $\zeta = -1.44$, $p = .151$, $d = 0.15$; $b_{\text{Effort}} = -0.06$, $\zeta = -0.53$, $p = .596$, $d = 0.05$. Furthermore, implicit inference was not associated with either outcome measure ($r_s \leq .05$, $p_s \geq .441$).

Finally, we wanted to evaluate whether our non-significant effects may be indicative for the null hypothesis being more likely than our alternative hypothesis. We used the goal manipulation and both DVs (controlled for the baseline) for a test of the null hypothesis via Bayes Factor. We employed the robust test statistics from the t test, which was 1.09 for speed and 1.40 for symbol counting. Those test statistics and the sample sizes of $N = 378$ ($n_{\text{control}} = 193$, $n_{\text{goal}} = 185$) were used in JASP's summary statistics add on (JASP team, 2019). We assumed a wide prior (Cauchy priori) to test the likelihood of the null hypothesis given the data. For both speed, $BF_{01} = 6.87$, and page counting, $BF_{01} = 4.71$, we found moderate evidence that the null is more likely than the alternative hypothesis.

Taken together, the data of Study 2 did not yield evidence of the goal contagion process described in the introduction. Moreover, no evidence for an implicit inference process was found, either. As we applied conservative inclusion criteria, collected data from hundreds of participants and found

Figure 11. Exploratory analyses for speed, counting and implicit accessibility using a larger sample ($N = 378$). Violins depict kernel density of the data. Black dots represent estimated means and whiskers represent the 95% confidence intervals; implicit accessibility is z-standardized

moderate evidence for the null, we are confident in those results.

General Discussion

Everyday life shows us that people are getting inspired by other people: after learning about someone's goals and aspirations, we sometimes adapt similar behaviors to pursue similar goals. A social-cognitive approach to this phenomenon is the effect of goal contagion (Aarts et al., 2004; Dik & Aarts, 2007). An implicit activation of a goal due to observing goal-directed behavior of another person would be a great base for inspiration, because goals guide behavior in a persisting and flexible way. However, the assumed two-step process of goal contagion is also vulnerable to the influences of moderators.

Thus, our primary interest was to better understand the effects of moderators that have been shown to be relevant in previous research (Aarts et al., 2004; Dik & Aarts, 2007). Those were the effort by the observed person to attain her goal and the observer's individual value for the goal. We assumed that in the two-step model, the observed person's effort strengthens the inference and adoption becomes more likely if the observer's goal is in line with what s/he observes. With this Registered Report we set out to find evidence for the goal contagion effect within the full moderated-mediation model using the first goal that has been utilized in the context of the theory: earning money (Aarts et al., 2004, Study 1).

Across all three studies, there was strong evidence that participants could indeed infer the goal from the observed behavior. Participants always identified the goal of the person

(spontaneous inference) and thought it was highly likely that the person wanted to earn money in the goal conditions (explicit inference), respectively. Hence, these two components could be treated as parts of the common factor goal inference. However, complications arose when we introduced an implicit measure to the same factor. The results of Study 1b were not indicative for an implicit accessibility: most participants did not list the word money and those who did were nearly equally distributed across conditions. This null-effect was replicated in Study 2 and persists in both studies even if the observed person showed high effort.

Effort should have moderated the path between the observation and inference. We found some evidence for this effect on the spontaneous and explicit inference components in Study 1a and b, but no evidence for such a moderation in Study 2. Importantly, even within the significant interaction, the crucial contrast between low and high effort in the goal condition was only marginally significant. Furthermore, there was no significant interaction on the implicit measure. Together, these mixed results do not substantiate our moderation hypothesis.

Thus, people correctly inferred the goal from the observed behavior. But did this translate into goal adoption as goal contagion would give reason to expect? This was not the case. In Study 2 we tested behavioral goal pursuit with two dependent variables in the moderated-mediation model: Participants had the opportunity to earn lottery tickets for a cash prize in task 2 (symbol-counting task), if they worked fast enough in task 1 (speed). As higher speed in task 1 and more pages solved in task 2 indicate goal-directed behavior, they

should have been associated with a successful inference. Moreover, goal value – participants’ love of money (Du & Tang, 2005), which was measured at least three days prior – should have moderated the path between goal inference and the DVs. Results of Study 2 for the two DVs did not turn out as hypothesized: neither inference, nor inference moderated by goal value showed an effect on the outcome measures. Furthermore, there was no main effect of the goal contagion manipulation on the two behavioral measures and, consequently, no support for adoption of the goal to earn money can be reported. These results raise several questions regarding our studies and the goal contagion effect.

First, one could ask whether our manipulation material was sufficient to elicit goal contagion. Given that previous research – both older (Aarts et al., 2004) and more recent (Laurin et al., 2016) – employed text-based material, we are confident that we followed established procedures. Importantly, our material was thoroughly pretested beforehand to ensure that the relevant goal was indeed recognized, which was approved before data collection started. Still it is possible that more vivid manipulation materials like videos could exert a more pronounced effect, although other studies of ours raise doubts to that claim (Brohmer et al., 2019a).

Second, one could ask whether the inference indicators were sufficient for our purposes. However, similar measures as SPON, EXP and IMP were employed by previous research on the same topic (Aarts et al., 2004; Dik & Aarts, 2007). Another critical issue is the position of the inference measure in the mediation model. Even though not uncommon (e.g., Jia et al., 2014), one

might criticize that we measured SPON and EXP after the dependent variable in Study 2. We realized this order, because an explicit measure would bring the goal into conscious awareness and this might disturb an automatic goal contagion effect. We did not want to jeopardize the goal contagion effect – at the risk of reducing accuracy in capturing the mediation. Unfortunately, even without including the mediator in the model, we could not detect a goal contagion effect. Further, there are more profound issues with inference.

A closer look at these measures in the literature reveals some inconsistencies. For instance, evidence from a rather explicit inference measure of a goal (similar to our SPON measure) in Aarts et al. (2004, prestudy for Study 1, Study 6) was used to argue that the goal was activated in observers, implying that inference also worked on an implicit level and that goal contagion would occur. However, in another paper (Dik & Aarts, 2007, Experiment 2), it is argued against explicit inference (similar to our EXP measures) within the goal contagion process. Even though there was an effect on this explicit measure, this was not related to goal pursuing behavior. In our studies, we also show that both spontaneous and explicit measures are highly associated with our manipulation, but not with goal pursuit. In this regard, using explicit measures to show that participants recognize the goal correctly - even as a manipulation check, might be fruitless within goal contagion research, as they seem to be irrelevant for goal adoption.

Implicit measures, on the other hand, are manifold in the literature (e.g., Hassin et al., 2005; Dik & Aarts, 2007; Jia et al., 2014; Wessler & Hansen, 2016) and several authors argue in

favor of them within the goal contagion process, which is sensible in theoretical terms. Therefore, it is surprising that few have tested a mediation model utilizing those measures (see exceptions Dik & Aarts, 2007; Jia et al., 2014). We used a variation of a word completion task twice and found two times no association with any variable in the model. Quite the contrary, data on our implicit measure clustered around zero across conditions. Unless we produced two false-negatives, our data strongly suggest that researchers interested in similar inference processes need to dedicate substantial effort to identify implicit measures that work well. This relates back to a wider issue of implicit measures we alluded to in the introduction.

Several implicit measures, like the word completion task, the lexical decision task and others (see Eckerstorfer, Brohmer & Corcoran, 2019) are often employed in the literature (e.g., Dik & Aarts, 2007, Jia et al., 2014) to measure very different things: Foremost, they indicate construct accessibility (i.e., having a construct in mind due to internal processes or priming), but they are also used to measure goal inference (i.e., an observer processing someone's goal), and goal activation / accessibility (i.e., having a goal cognitively activated to be pursued). Even though both goal inference and goal activation go hand in hand with construct accessibility, these are not the same. A goal is more than a construct and contains affective and motivational components. Thinking about money is not the same as thinking someone else wants money or wanting money oneself. However, none of the implicit measures seem to be able to differentiate between these three aspects. This is potentially why other authors have used the same implicit

construct accessibility measure to assess goal adoption (e.g., Jia et al., 2014, Study 3) and goal inference (Dik & Aarts, 2007, Experiment 1). A differentiation, however, would not only be relevant in the context of goal contagion, but also for other goal activation processes (Kruglanski et al., 2002).

Our critical view of implicit measures is substantiated by other recent research in the field, which calls the validity of implicit measures into question (e.g., the Implicit Association Test, see Schimmack, 2019) or could not replicate effects that are based on assumptions of implicit activations (e.g., facial feedback, see Wagenmakers et al., 2016; professor priming, see O'Donnell et al. 2018). We would therefore suggest more direct replications of studies using other implicit measures, such as the lexical decision task (Jia et al., 2014; Wessler & Hansen, 2016). This step is essential for a substantial argument in favor of the theory, as there needs to be implicit measures found which can distinguish between mere construct accessibility, goal inference, and goal activation and which can be used to assess the mediator in the two-step goal contagion process.

Third, one could argue that our behavioral measures did not work and have to be improved. We relied on behavioral measures as they can show that a goal is not only inferred and accessible as a goal of another person, but also adopted by the observer. The downside of such a behavioral measure is, that people do not always act on a goal – even though it is activated. We believe this downside is minimized within our experimental setup, as we provided participants an easy opportunity to pursue the goal to earn money. One might also have the concern that if a task for the dependent measure is

too blatantly referring to an obvious goal, everyone might show the behavior that is relevant for the goal – regardless of the manipulation. Some ambiguity may be useful throughout the procedure (Loersch & Payne, 2011). In our studies, we avoided using the words “earning” and “money” with respect to the first dependent measure (speed), which was modeled after behavioral measures used in previous goal contagion studies (Aarts et al., 2004). However, for our second dependent variable (symbol-counting), we clearly pointed out the opportunity to get lottery tickets for a cash prize, which might have been sufficient to activate the goal of earning money in everybody and thereby spoil the manipulation. However, we did not detect effects on any of the two dependent variables.

Fourth, one could ask if goal contagion actually exists. Goal contagion relies on a purely cognitive process. Maybe this viewpoint is too limited and one also has to consider motivational or emotional pathways that are important for goal activation (see Jia et al., 2014). For instance – and as we argue elsewhere (Brohmer et al., 2019a) – in order to get inspired for helpful behavior, one might first feel elevated by the observation in order to consider helping later. Likewise, a motivational boost by the observation of someone earning money might be required to truly stimulate observers pursuing the same goal. In this regard, the idea of implicit activations of associations that connect constructs and goals outside conscious awareness might not be sufficient for a goal contagion process. Just because earlier research on goal contagion has focused on a cognitive pathway and has rarely included emotional or motivational assessments does not

mean that these alternative pathways do not exist or even sustain the goal contagion process.

It might also be, that some aspects of the cognitive goal contagion process are not specified enough to enable replicability. For example, so far it is not quite clear whether goal contagion could be implicit and automatic or has to be implicit and automatic. On the one hand, the process seems to be highly plausible given its deduction from cognitive theories like implicit causal inference (Hassin et al., 2002), goal system theory (Kruglanski et al., 2002), implicit goal pursuit (Custers & Aarts, 2010), and associative networks (Shiffrin & Schneider, 1977, but see Amodio, 2018). On the other hand, our difficulties suggest some hidden procedures or unknown constraints. Moreover, by looking into the literature on goal contagion, we found a substantial publication bias (Brohmer, Eckerstorfer, van Aert & Corcoran, 2019b; see Chapter 4) and a lack of close replications of experimental paradigms. In other words, there are several published studies showing an effect, but these may be biased and none of those studies were replicated to substantiate, advance or question the theory (which defines an “undead theory” according to Ferguson & Heene, 2012; Chambers, 2017). We do think that inspiration is real, as everyday experiences show us. However, it is possible that the underlying processes are different and / or more complex than stressed by the seemingly straight-forward goal contagion process. In order to gain insight into mechanisms which impact goal contagion, we recommend that future research on this topic employs open science practices to ensure efficient theory-building.

Chapter 4

Is there Goal Contagion *at all?*

This chapter is based on the following manuscript:

Brohmer, H., Eckerstorfer, L. V., van Aert, R. C. M., Corcoran, K., (2020). Do Behavioral Observations Make People Catch the Goal? A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis on Goal Contagion. Manuscript submitted for publication [*preprint*: <https://osf.io/xydgf/>]

Supplementary materials: <https://osf.io/wvq8e/>

Minor changes in this chapter compared to the manuscript concern the layout and are not content-related. They were communicated to and approved by the co-authors.

Introduction

Goals are essential to many species' existence. Understood as representations of desired states that are attainable through action (Kruglanski & Kopetz, 2009), they determine the upcoming steps of living beings as they strive to achieve something, be it nourishment, sex, company or a place to hide. Humans are no exception, but beyond these aforementioned basic needs (Jolly, 1976; Maslow, 1943), our complex cognitive structure allows us to incorporate many goals in our daily life, like "catching the train to the workplace," "going grocery shopping," or "going jogging after work." Moreover, we can plan ahead so that our daily goals serve as a means for higher-order goals like "earning money," "being healthy," or "keeping in shape," which usually serve self-regulatory purposes in the long run (Carver & Scheier, 1981, 2012). However, it is also due to our cognitive architecture that we often monitor other people's behavior as this can contain important information (e.g., My colleagues bring their home-cooked meals for lunch – I also want to live healthily!). Consequently, observing other people's goal-directed behavior might affect our own goals.

We can take others as a source to adjust our goals. A social-cognitive approach to this phenomenon is provided by the theory of goal contagion (henceforth, GC), which was introduced by Aarts and colleagues (Aarts, Dijksterhuis, & Dik, 2008; Aarts, Gollwitzer, & Hassin, 2004) more than a decade ago. As much research has been conducted on this topic, we intend to summarize the evidence for GC in a meta-analysis and search for potential moderators. To do so, we will first provide a clear description of GC, based on theoretical

introductions and empirical studies in the literature. We need to overcome vague concepts and paradigms to formulate precise guidelines for the later extraction of studies and effects in the meta-analysis.

The process of and evidence for goal contagion

The original authors of the first GC studies based their theoretical approach on the spontaneous causal inferences framework (Hassin, Bargh, & Uleman, 2002), which posits that people make spontaneous inferences about traits. For instance, the observation of a person offering to help someone else likely leads to the inference that this person might be helpful in general. However, Aarts et al. (2004) extended this idea from traits of the observed person to the goals he/she is pursuing. Thus, an observed helpful behavior could be an indicator for both the observed person's trait of being helpful in general, but also for his/her current goal of offering help. The latter is the prerequisite for the GC process.

The process of GC can be described as follows: People observe others behaving in a certain way and infer their goals quickly, automatically, and on a rather implicit level outside their conscious awareness. If this inferred goal has some relevance to the observers, they are inclined to adopt this goal thereafter. This way, GC is actually a two-step process, predicting a goal-directed behavior of an observer, following the implicit inference of that goal through observations. Laurin (2016) even compared GC to a misattribution process, because the implicitly inferred goal of the other person is unconsciously attributed to the self and thus directs the observer's thoughts and actions. Although research on GC does not exclude

explicit pathways from the model – indeed GC research sometimes reports explicit measures as manipulation checks or additional dependent variables (DVs) (Dik & Aarts, 2007; Jia, Tong, & Lee, 2014) – it has to be noted that the inference step is mostly described to be on a rather implicit level. This is also theoretically sensible and in line with regard to GC's origin in the spontaneous causal inferences framework (Hassin et al., 2002) as described above.

Several studies have presented evidence for the existence of GC and three things become apparent from the empirical literature: First, a wide array of diverse goals was tested by different research teams. Therefore, the GC effect was shown for goals ranging from having casual sex (Aarts et al., 2004) to behaving prosocially (Dik & Aarts, 2007) to achieving high scores in a task (Leander & Shah, 2013) to dieting (Lee & Shapiro, 2015). Secondly, in most of the literature, GC manipulation is additionally accompanied by moderators that might operate in a unique way for some goals but potentially not for others. For instance, an observed person showing extra effort in his or her behavior (as moderating condition) might be beneficial for the observer adopting a prosocial goal (Dik & Aarts, 2007), but not for self-serving goals like earning money (Corcoran, Brohmer, Eckerstorfer, & Macher, 2018). Third, most studies focus on either demonstrating the implicit inference of the observed goal or behavioral measures as goal adoption, without looking at inference (for exceptions that focus on both, see Corcoran et al., 2018; Dik & Aarts, 2007; Jia et al., 2014). Recently, more labs have attempted to contribute to the body of research on GC by testing both formerly used and new goals, as well as the two-step model,

including moderators (Brohmer et al., 2018; Corcoran et al., 2018; Wessler & Hansen, 2016). Interestingly, these attempts often did not yield significant results, with the GC effect being close to zero.

Because these studies demonstrated that the GC effect does not seem to be as stable as could be expected from the previously published literature, we reasoned that a meta-analysis on GC would be advantageous to 1) summarize the evidence for GC, 2) discern implicit and behavioral measures and 3) identify further moderating effects that might turn out to be important across goals. In other words, our motivation was to see which goals that we perceive in others are truly affecting our own goals and under which conditions, which will be described in the following section. Moreover, we will also test and correct for potential publication bias to obtain more accurate effect size estimates, which has proved to be effective in other social-psychological research (Francis, 2012; Kühberger, Fritz, & Scherndl, 2014; Lane & Dunlap, 1978).

Potential moderators

In accordance with the aforementioned three points, we selected the DV that was used (henceforth: DV category) as a first moderator of interest, which has the advantage of being relatively objectively identifiable: it can be implicit goal inference or goal pursuit (including behavioral intention). Implicit goal inference is indicated by the cognitive and automatic activation of goals, which is usually measured via tasks such as the lexical decision or word completion task (e.g., Dik & Aarts, 2007). Goal pursuit contains both behavioral

measures and an expression of intention (see supplementary materials for more information).

Our second moderator of interest differentiates elicited goals to test the idea that some goals might be more contagious than others. There are many dimensions on which goals might differ. We decided to look at goals based on how many people would pursue this goal, which hints at whether a goal can be perceived as quite “common” (henceforth: common goal). Crucially, this moderator is useful because the GC process is theorized to be strengthened when observers assign a high or positive value to the goal that they infer (Aarts et al., 2004; Brohmer et al., 2018; Corcoran et al., 2018). If a goal is pursued by a majority of people, this indicates a high value in the eyes of many and demonstrates a broader relevance. This in turn could make it more likely from the perspective of a specific individual (such as a study participant) that he/she might also assign a high value to this goal, which should foster the GC process. Therefore, common goals might be more contagious overall.⁷

The last two moderators have a more methodological focus and might provide insights into how best to study GC. The third moderator will be the presentation of stimulus material, depicting a goal-directed behavior (henceforth: presentation). This measure is relatively objective as most stimulus material could be expected to be identifiable as texts or video clips and animations, these forms being most likely to depict behavior in a standardized form. More vivid materials – such as video clips – are likely more effective to elicit GC.

⁷ Note that in the preregistration, we refer to the “common goal” moderator as “basic goal” moderator, see <https://osf.io/zgqub/>
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Lastly, we are also interested in to what extent the control conditions for each study might be neutral or contrary to the goal (henceforth: contrast control). It is expected that conditions that are rather contrary to the goal might result in a stronger GC effect.

Method

We defined general inclusion criteria for extracting published articles from databases and specific inclusion criteria to identify relevant studies in those papers. In addition, we developed our coding scheme for the GC studies based on a preliminary coding of five original papers. This was necessary due to differences in reported statistical information, which often affect the extraction of relevant effects. Hence, we used those five studies to gain general experience for the coding and how to deal with limited information. Those three steps – general inclusion of papers, specific inclusion of studies and the coding of relevant effects – will be described in the following paragraph. All materials, data, codes, and a PRISMA-guidelines checklist for meta-analyses can be accessed in the accompanying Open Science Framework (OSF) project folder (<https://osf.io/mxepy/>).

General inclusion criteria for articles and database search

General theoretical eligibility. Prior to the database search, we committed ourselves to a definition and general criteria of GC as the benchmark, which we derived from the literature (e.g., Aarts et al., 2004; Dik & Aarts, 2007) and summarized in three crucial points. First, for GC to occur, an observer has to observe or read about a behavior by another person that

implies a certain goal, but the goal is not explicitly mentioned. This is crucial for GC from a theoretical perspective, as a behavior is the originator of the proposed cognitive process of goal inference. This distinguishes GC from other routes of goal activation, such as goal priming (e.g., Bargh, Gollwitzer, Lee-Chai, Barndollar, & Trötschel, 2001, see also Weingarten et al., 2016), in which the goal itself is presented as a semantic concept. Second, the observer should infer this goal from that behavior in an implicit, quick and automatic fashion. Third, the GC process should ultimately lead to the adoption of the goal by the observer resulting in goal-directed behavior or intentions. From a design-specific viewpoint, GC should be demonstrated in an experimental-psychological study. That is, there has to be a goal manipulation including an experimental condition, in which participants observe a goal-directed behavior and (some sort of) control condition, followed by a measure of implicit inference or goal pursuit.

The second and third points are not independent: the inference of the goal in the observer is theorized to occur quickly and automatically and on an implicit level outside conscious awareness after the observation (Aarts et al., 2004, pp. 24–25). It has to be reiterated that explicit inference is usually of minor interest in GC-related research and serves rather as a manipulation check or additional measure, which is why we do not include it as a central part of our definition. Only after an accurate inference should goal adoption occur, which is typically measured in participants' goal-directed behavior (i.e., goal pursuit) or intention for goal-directed behavior. Notably, inference is often described as a mediator between observation and adoption of the goal, but as the path

from inference to goal pursuit or intention is rarely studied, we will focus on the relationships between goal manipulation and goal inference or goal pursuit.

The theory on GC does not set restrictions on the goals to be elicited. This also became apparent during the preliminary coding of five papers, which revealed a diverse range of goals that these authors were interested in. Therefore, we set no restriction either, and recognized all kinds of goals – be they “academic achievements” (Wessler & Hansen, 2016), “being helpful” (Dik & Aarts, 2007), or “having casual sex” (Aarts et al., 2004). In the same vein, we expected that in an experimental setting the focal goal toward which the behavior is directed should be rather obvious to strengthen the manipulation (although behaviors are sometimes multifinal, see Shah, Kruglanski, & Friedman, 2003).

Systematic search. After fixing definition and criteria, we conducted a systematic search between March and April 2018 in four databases for published work, namely PsychInfo, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and JSTOR. In all four databases, we applied a similar search logic: we looked in the title, abstract, and keywords for the term “goal” in combination with “contagion,” “social learning,” “modelling,” “modeling,” “role model,” “social standard” and its alterations, “comparison standard” and its alterations or “observational learning” (for specific search syntaxes, see OSF folder data & coding). The initial systematic search resulted in $k = 2821$ articles.

Screening of articles. The articles were split equally among three trained student assistants, who applied the criteria of the general theoretical eligibility to separate relevant from irrelevant papers based on titles and abstracts. This culminated in $k = 30$ articles that remained of interest. Afterwards, the same coders applied the same criteria again, by looking into the 30 articles in more detail. After this screening, 17 articles had to be excluded, as it turned out they were not eligible, and 13 relevant articles (including the five preliminary articles) and one registered report (see section on unpublished studies) were kept.

Additional searches. However, some potentially relevant GC articles did not show up during this search, which is why we decided to perform an additional browsing in citing literature on Google Scholar and in the reference lists of articles that we obtained from the systematic search. We also performed another extended search on PsychInfo for studies with adult samples, using the keywords “observational learning,” “role model,” and “social learning.” For this search, we excluded the word “goal” to make sure we would not miss studies conceptually related to GC, despite not employing the same wording.

These procedures, the additional browsing and extended search, yielded a total of $k = 2908$ articles and documents (including the ones from the previous paragraph). Checking the content of articles again yielded an additional $k = 12$ articles, which seemed to be of relevance due to a fitting experimental setup, although they did not necessarily self-identify as being GC-related. In total, we found $k = 24$ articles

that were of relevance as they potentially contained studies that would fit in this meta-analysis (see Figure 12).

Specific inclusion criteria for studies in published articles

After coding all studies that were initially theoretically eligible (resulting in a total of $e = 96$ effects that measured implicit inference or goal pursuit; $e = 127$ when also including explicit inference measures), we proceeded to look into the method sections of all selected studies to see if they also fit our specific inclusion criteria.⁸ These criteria encompassed points like whether there was an identifiable goal the authors wanted to elicit in their experimental design, whether participants were adults of at least 18 years of age, whether the specific goal the experimenters wanted to trigger was not mentioned in between the manipulation and the measurement of the DV. This last point is crucial for a clear distinction of GC from goal priming because GC includes a goal-inference step, which would be obsolete if the goal is mentioned before the DV is measured. Other points were that the goal-directed behavior of the observed person was not identical to the one shown by the participant, in order to distinguish GC from role modeling (Morgenroth, Ryan, & Peters, 2015) or mimicry (Chartrand & Lakin, 2013), and whether the control condition differed sufficiently from the experimental condition (i.e., by not using an attenuated version of the experimental conditions). Finally, it was important that sufficient statistical information was

⁸ Please note that our specific inclusion criteria were extended during the coding of articles. Any changes made to the preregistered coding scheme are documented online by date (see OSF folder “Data & Coding”).

reported according to our preliminary set criteria for the extraction of effects (see section after next).

We applied these specific criteria study by study to identify suitable effects (as there is often more than one DV measured per study) and had to exclude 38 effects, leaving $e = 58$ effects. Some of these effects were taken from the same studies and had to be either combined (e.g., if two effects from the same study were based on implicit inference) or reduced to the preferred effect (i.e., only pursuit was used when there was implicit inference and pursuit measured). Finally, this left us with $e = 48$ effects for the confirmatory analysis. It has to be noted that some effects from self-identified GC studies had to be eliminated from the confirmatory analysis – for instance, if goal pursuit was too close to the manipulation or the goal manipulation itself was too explicit about the goal. Those individual coding decisions that did not fit the criteria are marked in the accompanying spreadsheet as excluded (see <https://osf.io/w8b9m/>).

Unpublished studies and studies from registered reports

We also looked for unpublished studies via the OSF and ProQuest using the same search terms as before (see search syntax in the OSF). Furthermore, we contacted relevant labs via email, asking whether there are more unpublished GC studies available. Neither approach yielded further results. Hence, we could only include effects from our own lab, which were not published at the time of the coding procedure, and published studies from registered reports (henceforth: RRs). As RRs employ the main peer-review procedure before the data collection and therefore before any bias can occur, they

Figure 12. Decision tree for search for articles leading to the confirmatory and extended analysis; * including effects that did not fit inclusion criteria, explicit inference and effects from five preliminarily coded articles; all $e = 127$ coded effects can be found in the data matrix online: <https://osf.io/dkxsr/>

have to be treated differently from common publications (see Chambers, 2019). Data and codes for the extraction of effects from these studies, along with preregistrations when available, are also provided online.

Criteria for the extraction of relevant effects

We intended to code effects and variables that can broadly be summarized in four categories and which will be discussed in the following sections: effects relevant for GC (confirmatory effects); effects from all studies that passed the initial criteria of general theoretical eligibility (extended effects); effects hypothesized by the original authors (originally hypothesized effects); and potential moderators. The coding was done for all effects that passed the initial criteria for general theoretical eligibility.

Effects for the confirmatory analysis. Criteria for the extraction of a relevant confirmatory effect were as tangible as possible: We were interested in DVs that represented implicit inference, goal pursuit or behavioral intention. We took the main effect only if this was the only manipulation or when the original authors expected an attenuation of the GC effect through a second variable (factor) as a moderator. Otherwise, when a knockout effect (e.g., GC effect in one condition of the second factor, but not in the other one) or even a crossover effect (e.g., GC effect in one condition, but reverse effect in the other condition of the second factor) was expected (Giner-Sorolla, 2018), we would consider the simple effect in that condition of the second factor, in which the GC effect (higher scores in the goal condition vs. control condition) was expected.

If more than two groups were present on the goal factor, whereby the additional condition was a control condition (e.g., control 1 vs. control 2 vs. goal), we took the effect that was most neutral and least opposed in comparison to the goal condition. If more than two groups were present on the goal factor, whereby the additional condition was an additional goal condition (e.g., control vs. goal low vs. goal high), we would aggregate the goal conditions.

Means, standard deviations (or standard errors) and group sizes were crucial descriptive statistics for the calculation of the effect size Hedges' g , which is the standardized mean difference Cohen's d corrected for positive bias (Hedges, 1981). During the coding phase, we found that reporting standards varied strongly across papers. Therefore, when descriptive statistics were not reported in studies, we based the calculation of the effect sizes on test statistics like t -values, F -values, χ^2 -values and r -estimates. An automated procedure is provided by Del Re's R package *compute.es* (Del Re, 2015).⁹

Effects for the extended analysis. Using our definition of, and our conservative inclusion criteria for, GC might have a side effect: our attempt at higher precision could work at the expense of variance that could explain moderating effects. That is, because we will probably have to exclude several studies for the confirmatory analysis, we will also reduce our

⁹ Note that correlation coefficients r were included during the coding procedure as it turned out that some studies reported them, rather than regression coefficients with accompanying t -values. Additional exploratory coding that was not considered a priori is described online and corresponding exploratory analyses are reported in the supplementary materials.

chance of identifying moderating conditions. Therefore, we will conduct an extended, not preregistered analysis using all effects that passed the initial criteria for general theoretical eligibility, $e = 96$. Again, similar effects from these studies were combined, resulting in a sample of $e = 75$ effects.

Originally hypothesized effects. The originally hypothesized effects, which are the hypothesized effects in the primary studies by the original authors, were not always equivalent to the relevant effects for this meta-analysis as the former could contain specific interactions with other variables (e.g., other manipulations) that could deactivate or even reverse the goal contagion effect. Therefore, both effects have to be clearly distinguished to avoid certain effects being falsely attributed to GC alone (for a recent example of such a case see Crede, 2019 in response to Cuddy, Schultz, & Fosse, 2018). P - and z -values for these effects were extracted for power estimations (Schimmack & Brunner, 2017, 2019, Simonsohn, Nelson, & Simmons, 2014, 2019).

Moderators. As the GC effect was expected to be heterogeneous across studies, we intended to identify potential moderators of this effect, which we described in the theory section. They encompass *DV category* (implicit inference vs. pursuit), *common goal* (number of people expected to pursue the goal); *presentation* of manipulation material (texts vs. video clips and animations; excluding single pictures), *contrast control* (neutrality of the goal condition). Other differentiations, such as whether goals are directed towards the self vs. towards others, are more short-term vs. more long-term oriented or

approach-related vs. avoidance-related implying wins and losses might also be of interest. However, due to the relatively low number of studies (see results section), we decided to not test all possible moderators, thereby avoiding an inflation of the false-positive error rate.

In this vein, it has to be noted that the two moderators common goal and contrast control leave some leeway for interpretation, especially with regard to the other more objective moderators (e.g., when different studies employ clear goal conditions, but ambiguous control conditions, see for instance Aarts et al., 2004 and Jia et al., 2014). We therefore conducted a pre-study on Amazon Mechanical Turk ($N = 57$) to assess which goals are potentially perceived as being pursued by more people (common goal) and to what degree control conditions are indeed perceived as being neutral or contrary to the goal in the experimental conditions (contrast control). Mean estimates from this pre-study were extracted as values for the continuous moderators (see also supplementary materials; preregistration of the pre-study: <https://osf.io/zgqub/>).

Results of the Meta-analysis

Analyses were conducted in R (R Core Team, 2019), using the metafor package (Viechtbauer, 2010, 2017), the robumeta package (Fisher, Tipton, & Zhipeng, 2017), puniform (van Aert, Wicherts, & van Assen, 2016), weightr (Coburn & Vevea, 2019; Vevea & Hedges, 1995), and ggplot2 (Wickham, 2019).

Agreement for all codings was assessed based on the rating of two trained raters, who applied the specific inclusion criteria

Study	Goal	Sample	Hedge's g	95% CIL
Loersch, 2008 (2b)	cooperation	12	1.50	0.30, 2.71
Jia, 2014 (1)	cooperation	45	1.24	0.61, 1.87
Aarts, 2004 (2)	casual sex	24	1.18	0.33, 2.02
Loersch, 2008 (2)	cooperation	22	1.12	0.25, 1.99
Jia, 2014 (2)	earning money	41	0.95	0.31, 1.59
Fast, 2010 (4)	blame	31	0.90	0.18, 1.62
Aarts, 2004 (4)	casual sex	48	0.75	0.17, 1.32
Wessler, 2016 (2p)	achievement	51	0.74	0.18, 1.31
Loersch, 2008 (1)	cooperation	66	0.67	0.18, 1.16
Brescoll, 2013 (2)	system advocacy	38	0.67	0.03, 1.31
Jia, 2014 (3)	earning money	50	0.65	0.07, 1.24
Leander, 2011 (3)	earning money	40	0.63	0.00, 1.25
Dik, 2007 (2)	helping	98	0.58	0.17, 1.00
Leander, 2013 (3a)	achievement	69	0.57	0.09, 1.05
v.d. Weiden, 2010 (3)	gaze at object	39	0.52	0.07, 0.97
v.d. Weiden, 2010 (2)	gaze at object	51	0.50	0.11, 0.89
Aarts, 2004 (3)	casual sex	65	0.49	0.00, 0.97
Leander, 2011 (2)	volunteering	57	0.47	-0.05, 0.99
Fast, 2010 (3)	blame	117	0.47	0.10, 0.83
Dik, 2007 (1)	helping	116	0.46	0.08, 0.84
Fast, 2010 (1)	blame	95	0.42	0.02, 0.83
Jia, 2018 (1p)	cooperation	157	0.42	0.10, 0.74
Leander, 2013 (3b)	achievement	44	0.41	-0.06, 0.88
Dik, 2007 (3)	helping	166	0.39	0.08, 0.70
Aarts, 2004 (1)	earning money	83	0.38	-0.05, 0.81
Zhou, 2017 (1)	eating	144	0.38	0.05, 0.71
v.d. Weiden, 2010 (1)	gaze at object	44	0.36	-0.05, 0.78
v.d. Weiden, 2010 (2b)	gaze at object	39	0.32	-0.12, 0.76
Fast, 2010 (2)	blame	87	0.26	-0.16, 0.68
Leander, 2013 (1)	achievement	36	0.24	-0.42, 0.90
Hassin, 2005 (4)	several	51	0.20	-0.19, 0.58
Jia, 2018 (2)	voluntary work	152	0.19	-0.13, 0.51
Corcoran, 2018 (1b)	earning money	320	0.16	-0.06, 0.38
Corcoran, 2017 (1)	studying	97	0.12	-0.27, 0.52
Aarts, 2004 (5)	casual sex	34.67	0.12	-0.53, 0.77
Tobin, 2015 (3)	earning money	201	0.10	-0.18, 0.38
Jia, 2018 (1)	cooperation	88	0.06	-0.36, 0.48
Corcoran, 2016 (1)	cleanliness	45	0.05	-0.54, 0.63
Brohmer, 2018 (3)	helping	231	0.04	-0.17, 0.26
Brohmer, 2018 (1)	helping	126	0.04	-0.30, 0.39
Wessler, 2016 (2)	achievement	168	0.04	-0.26, 0.34
Brohmer, 2018 (2)	helping	162	0.01	-0.30, 0.32
Corcoran, 2017 (2)	physical activity	95	-0.01	-0.40, 0.39
Tobin, 2015 (1)	achievement	51.33	-0.04	-0.58, 0.50
Corcoran, 2017 (3)	studying	245	-0.09	-0.35, 0.17
Eckerstorfer, 2017	physical activity	201	-0.12	-0.40, 0.16
Wessler, 2016 (1)	achievement	208	-0.20	-0.47, 0.07
Corcoran, 2018 (2)	earning money	300	-0.20	-0.42, 0.02
Summary		4751	0.30	[0.21, 0.39]

Figure 13. Forest plots for all analyses. Note that sample sizes sometimes include decimals due to insufficient information in original articles; thickness of CIs indicates higher precision; the green \diamond is the summary effect; Panel A: confirmatory analysis; ...

Figure 13 continued. Panel B: extended analysis; ...

Figure 13 continued. behavior only (C: confirmatory, D: extended).

for all studies and extracted the relevant effects. The agreement was low for all coded effects, $\kappa = .35$ and also for the hypothesized effects, $\kappa = .42$, despite our carefully developed coding scheme. In addition to these effects, we also coded the DV category, $\kappa = .82$, and presentation, $\kappa = .58$, as moderators by two raters, which yielded higher scores. These relatively low agreement ratings were likely due to the often complex and diverse study designs, which made it difficult to pinpoint the effects of interest despite our coding scheme. For instance, if authors were ambiguous about their expectation of the GC effect either on a certain factor or as a main effect, the coding would be exacerbated for us. Also, interpretation of hypothesized effects could become complicated if interaction effects were tested but only main effects were addressed. Nonetheless, disagreements between our two raters were thoroughly discussed. For eight remaining disagreements (across both confirmatory and hypothesized effects), a third rater served as a tie-breaker. We also conducted the confirmatory and extended analysis using the second rater's codings to see whether the summary effect would be different compared to rater 1. Interestingly, this was not the case: Despite nominal differences in individual estimates across raters, which yielded low reliability scores, the conclusion remained the same (see supplementary Figure S2). In the following, we will report results only from the first rater as the large majority of discussions upon initial disagreement resulted in agreeing with his codings.

Confirmatory and extended analysis

Summary effect. We conducted the random-effects meta-analysis using the restricted maximum likelihood estimator for estimating the between-study variance in true effect size for $e = 48$ effects from the published and unpublished literature. We opted for the random-effects model instead of the equal-effect model, because we wanted to estimate the average true effect size in the population from which the effects were randomly sampled (Borenstein, Hedges, Higgins, & Rothstein, 2010). Those effects represented either a measure for implicit inference or goal pursuit and were based on 4751 participants. The results indicated a small summary effect of GC, Hedges' $g = 0.30$, 95%CI [0.21, 0.40] (see Figure 13, A), which was accompanied by some heterogeneity across studies, $Q(47) = 113.00$, $p < .001$, $\tau^2 = 0.05$, 95%CI [0.03, 0.13], $I^2 = 57.57\%$, 95%CI [40.19%, 77.67%], $H^2 = 2.36$, 95%CI [1.67, 4.48]. The extended analysis was based on more effects, $e = 76$, and yielded roughly the same effect, $g = 0.29$, 95%CI [0.22, 0.36], and a similar amount of heterogeneity, $Q(75) = 164.08$, $p < .001$, $\tau^2 = 0.05$, 95%CI [0.03, 0.11], $I^2 = 53.11\%$, 95%CI [39.51%, 72.20%], $H^2 = 2.13$, 95%CI [1.65, 3.60] (see Figure 13, B).

For the previous analyses, we combined intention and behavior / goal pursuit. As a behavioral intention can also be seen as different from actual behavior, we additionally report pure behavioral results for the confirmatory data ($e = 26$, Figure 13, C), $g = 0.30$, 95%CI [0.16, 0.44], $Q(25) = 73.27$, $p < .001$, $\tau^2 = 0.08$, 95%CI [0.04, 0.26], $I^2 = 67.90\%$, 95%CI [48.93%, 87.29%], $H^2 = 3.12$, 95%CI [1.96, 7.87], and extended

data ($e = 40$, Figure 13, D), $g = 0.31$, 95%CI [0.21, 0.41], $Q(39) = 92.96$, $p < .001$, $\tau^2 = 0.05$, 95%CI [0.02, 0.14], $I^2 = 56.78\%$, 95%CI [36.18%, 77.84%], $H^2 = 2.31$, 95%CI [1.57, 4.51]. As one can see, these effects are no different from the larger data sets.

Publication bias and correction. To assess potential publication bias, we first correlated the sample size per study with the size of the effect. The negative and significant correlation (see Figure 14, A) hinted at potential publication bias as studies with a smaller sample size yielded larger effects (Kühberger et al., 2014). We split the data into published and unpublished relevant effects, where unpublished effects also included effects from RRs, as most publication bias corrections require traditional publications (without preregistration) only. Effects from both subgroups differed considerably: The summary effect of the published studies was larger, $g = .42$, 95%CI [0.34, 0.50], $Q(34) = 41.12$, $p = .187$, $\tau^2 = 0.003$, 95%CI [0.00, 0.08], $I^2 = 5.83\%$, 95%CI [0.00%, 61.19%], $H^2 = 1.06$, 95%CI [1.00, 2.58] than that of the unpublished studies, $g = -0.01$, 95%CI [-0.10; 0.08], $Q(12) = 15.76$, $p = .900$, $\tau^2 = 0.004$, 95%CI [0.00, 0.10], $I^2 = 15.24\%$, 95%CI [0.00%, 80.62%], $H^2 = 1.18$, 95%CI [1.00, 5.16], which in turn yielded an effect very close to zero (i.e., no effect). Interestingly, heterogeneity was much smaller and nonsignificant in the subgroups.

We proceeded by funnel-plotting the effect sizes of the published effects against the standard errors of the effects (see Figure 14, B). Egger's regression (Egger, Smith, Schneider, & Minder, 1997), which is depicted as the diagonal dashed line in Figure 3A, $b = 2.45$, $t = 4.86$, $p < .001$, also suggested that

small-study effects were present and one possible cause of small-study effects is publication bias. The estimates for the other three models yielded similar results and can be found in Supplementary Table S1.

Next, we applied several correction methods for the effect size estimate (descriptions are provided in Table 1).¹⁰ These encompassed older and more recently developed techniques with higher precision for the effect size correction. For the confirmatory model, corrected effects ranged from small (Trim & Fill: $g = 0.33$; P-uniform: $g = 0.21$) to tiny (P-uniform*: $g = 0.17$; Selection model: $g = 0.15$; Hybrid method: $g = 0.11$) to negative (PET: $g = -0.12$). Corrections of the extended analysis and the behavior-only analyses yielded effects even closer to zero (see Table 1).

Assuming that the true effect is around $g = 0.15$, this corresponds to 17 to 22 participants that have to be exposed to a goal contagion manipulation in order to find one person who is actually influenced by the observation compared to a control group.¹¹

¹⁰ Note that Trim and Fill has been criticized by methodologists (Terrin, Schmid, Lau, & Olkin, 2003; Simonsohn, Simmons, & Nelson, 2014). We also preregistered Orwin's Fail-Safe-N (Orwin, 1983), which has also been criticized and is recommended not to be used anymore (Becker, 2005; Simonsohn et al., 2014)

¹¹ We would like to thank the anonymous reviewer who hinted to us to use the NNT (number needed to treat) as an intuitively interpretable effect size. We used Control Event Rates of 0.2 and 0.5 to reach 17 and 22 participants, respectively.

Figure 14. Publication bias methods. (A) association between effect size (Hedges' g) and sample size; shades are the 95% CI; (B) association between effect size and standard error in a funnel plot; vertical full line is the raw summary effect; black full dots are imputed effects for trim-and-fill; vertical dashed line is the trim-and-fill corrected effect; the diagonal dashed line is Egger's regression.

Table 1. Different effect size correction methods and Hedges' g with 95% CI. See supplementary materials for details

Correction approach	description	source	Confirmatory Model (e = 48)	Pursuit confirm. (e = 26)	Extended Model (e = 76)	Pursuit extend. (e = 40)
Trim & Fill	Liberal correction based on mirrored studies	Duval & Tweedie, 2000	0.33 [0.22; 0.43]	0.16 [-0.003; 0.33]	0.18 [0.11; 0.26]	0.19 [0.08; 0.30]
PET method	Conservative correction based on the intercept of Egger's regression (PEESE with asterisk)	Stanley, 2008	-0.12 [-0.35; 0.11]	-0.11* [-0.24; 0.02]	-0.01* [-0.10; 0.08]	-0.05* [-0.17; 0.06]
Selection model	Assigns different weights to significant and nonsignificant effects	Vevea & Hedges, 1995; Vevea & Woods, 2005	0.15 [-0.02; 0.32]	0.13 [-0.07; 0.34]	0.07 [0.02; 0.12]	0.04 [-0.002; 0.08]
P-uniform	Assumes a uniform distribution of p-values ($p < .05$) conditioned on the true underlying effect size.	van Assen, van Aert, & Wicherts, 2015	0.21 [-0.05; 0.41]	0.27 [-0.07; 0.54]	0.13 [-0.09; 0.32]	0.16 [-0.14; 0.39]
P-uniform*	Also contain information from nonsignificant effects ($p \geq .05$)	van Aert et al., 2016; van Aert & van Assen, 2019	0.17 [0.05; 0.29]	0.20 [0.03; 0.38]	0.16 [0.08; 0.24]	0.15 [0.03; 0.28]
Hybrid method	Assumes a bias in published effects, but not in unpublished effects	van Aert & van Assen, 2018	0.11 [0.001; 0.23]	0.10 [-0.04; 0.29]	0.08 [-0.01; 0.18]	0.07 [-0.07; 0.22]

Results for the originally hypothesized effects

After checking, whether the originally reported test statistics were consistent with the p -values (Epskamp & Nuijten, 2014), we applied p -curve (Simonsohn, Nelson, & Simmons, 2014, 2019) and z -curve analyses (Schimmack & Brunner, 2017, 2019) to assess publication bias based on the these tests. The idea of these techniques is that the majority of p and z -values should be very low and very high respectively, if studies were well-powered. In other words, one would rather expect most p -values to be much lower than .05 and z -values much larger than 1.96. If studies systematically do not show low p -values and large z -values, one would expect low power and low expected replication rates.

With few exceptions (e.g., when authors wanted to confirm the null hypothesis using null-hypothesis testing instead of Bayesian statistics), there were several published hypothesized effects available (for every study that also contained relevant effects); in total, $e = 96$. A P -curve analysis (using the extracted test statistics in the OSF here: <http://www.p-curve.com/app4/>) showed an average power of 29%, 90%*CI* [17%, 42%], without direct evidence for p -hacking, indicating systematically underpowered studies. Next, we validated these results via z -curve (transforming the p -values here: <https://zcurve.shinyapps.io/zcurve19/>): The replication rate for future studies in this domain is expected to be 18% only, 95%*CI* [8%, 37%], which was even lower than the p -curve power estimate. In the same vein, it is estimated that for every published study on GC, there are about five studies in the file drawer, 95%*CI* [3, 19], which corresponds to an estimated discovery rate of 17%, 95%*CI* [5%, 27%].

Results for the moderators

We conducted meta-regressions for all preregistered moderators (i.e., presentation, DV category, common goal, and contrast control) individually and controlling for the other variables. However, results were always similar: There was virtually no evidence that any moderator showed an expected effect (see Figure 15). Only the zero-order effect of contrast control had a slope coefficient statistically significantly different from zero, which was also tiny in size. However, when we accounted for whether the effect came from the published or unpublished literature, this effect vanished as well (for more detailed descriptions, see supplementary materials). Consistent with the results from the subgroups, publication status as predictor had the strongest effect and was superior to all other moderators, $b = 0.43$, 95%*CI* [0.28; 0.58].

General Discussion

Observing someone pursuing his or her goals can have a profound effect on ourselves – maybe even to the extent that we adjust our own goals. The theory on GC (Aarts et al., 2004) allows a social-cognitive approach to this phenomenon, according to which an observation of someone’s goal-directed behavior will lead to an automatic and implicit inference in the observer and potentially to a behavior towards a similar goal. Here, we set out to summarize the evidence for GC in a meta-analysis and to identify moderators of this process, which is based on 48 effects for the confirmatory analysis and 76 effects for the extended analysis.

Figure 15. Meta-regression to identify moderators. Bubble size indicates sample size of the study; estimates in the panels are zero-order and for the black lines; continuous moderators are centered on the scale-midpoint; rectangles contain potentially interesting effects (details, see supplementary materials); additional estimates: (A): gray line: $b = -0.01$, 95%CI [-0.30, 0.28], dashed line: $b = -0.09$, 95%CI [-0.25, 0.06]; (B): gray line: $b = 0.04$, 95%CI [-0.23, 0.30], dashed line: $b = 0.06$, 95%CI [-0.11, 0.22]; (C): gray line: $b = 0.21$, 95%CI [-0.18, 0.59], dashed line: $b = 0.04$, 95%CI [-0.15, 0.22]; (D): gray line: $b = -0.09$, 95%CI [-0.18, 0.01], dashed line: $b = -0.02$, 95%CI [-0.09, 0.05]; (E): gray line: $b = 0.08$, 95%CI [0.02, 0.14], dashed line: $b = 0.03$, 95%CI [-0.01, 0.07].

First, even though there is an overall summary effect of Hedges' $g = 0.30$, this can be described as small, and it seems to be biased through the current state of the publication system. On average, published studies reported larger effects, $g = 0.42$, than unpublished studies and RRs, $g = -0.01$. Publication bias correction methods estimated the effect size to be around half the size of the uncorrected summary effect. The suggestion of a true effect around $g = 0.15$ was further supported by the extended analyses after correction. All in all, GC appears to have a rather soft effect, as one needs around 20 people to also find one person being affected by the observation. Hence, an unconscious and implicit inference or even adoption of an observed goal is not something that can be expected to distract people all the time from their daily activities. Rather, the GC effect, if it exists, might be limited to particular instances in contexts that are hard to pinpoint, which also becomes clear by looking at the moderators.

Second, when looking at the DV category, there was no noteworthy difference between behavioral and implicit outcome measures. This is somewhat surprising as one could expect stronger effects of implicit inference, regarded as prerequisite for a goal to be adopted. Furthermore, focusing on behavior only goal pursuit (without intention for behavior) yielded similar effects as the overall analysis. Taken together, we found no evidence indicating that the GC is stronger or more easily detectable depending on the deployed DV (implicit inference, intention for behavior, or behavioral goal pursuit).

Third, we did not find sufficient evidence for other moderating effects. There was no evidence that the more a goal is believed to be pursued by many people, the more it was

contagious – if anything there was a small negative effect. We can only speculate that common goals that are observed in many people might not be contagious per se, as they could be perceived as too trivial. For instance, being physically active might be a great goal to achieve, but just observing others going jogging in the park is not something exceptional. Maybe, learning about individual people who have pursued a goal in the face of concrete adversities could have a stronger effect on ourselves (Morgenroth et al., 2015), although this would be different from the original idea of goal contagion. Moreover, there was no sufficient evidence that videos or animations were more successful manipulation materials than texts, which might be due to only a few studies using no text-based material.

The effect between the GC condition and the control condition, however, became slightly more pronounced the more contrary the goals in both conditions were. Therefore, only the last moderator, contrast control, could hold up in terms of statistical significance in a meta-regression with the other potential moderators included. A close inspection of the driving effects showed that cooperation vs. competition could be interesting candidates for replication studies. However, as these studies contained subsamples of between only 12 and 66 participants, we have reservations about making replication suggestions.

Additionally, it is surprising that the contrast–control moderation effect did not turn out to be much stronger, as one could expect that a non-neutral control condition might inhibit the contrastive focal goal and would boost the difference to the goal condition. Also, several studies (Dik & Aarts, 2007; Laurin et al., 2016) relied on control conditions that were

conceptually contrary to the focal goal. One reason why contrary-goal control conditions are not as effective as one would think could be that they often indirectly imply the actual goal (Moskowitz & Gesundheit, 2009). For instance, in their first study on GC, Aarts and colleagues (2004) used the goal of earning money in the experimental group through a text in which someone was described working on a farm. They also used a seemingly contrary-goal control text of someone doing voluntary work. However, one might wonder whether reading about voluntary work could not also trigger the opposite goal, which is most probably earning money. Indeed, when we used similar material (Corcoran et al., 2018, Study 1a), we found that participants sometimes indicated that earning money was a goal that the person doing voluntary work wanted to pursue. It is then likely that the goal might be active for some participants, although the control stimulus was meant to be contrary.

As with many meta-analyses in psychology, this one, too, suffers from deficiencies. An obvious limitation is probably the partially low interrater agreement scores. We intended to ensure that our preregistered coding scheme would produce similar results independent of the raters as this is currently not the standard in quantitative research (Maassen et al., 2019). This turned out to be difficult as both the relevant effects and originally hypothesized effects were often not clear enough to the coders, despite extensive training with five preliminarily coded articles as pilot. Hence, the low scores might partly depend on the experience level of the coders and partly on the large variation of the experimental designs. The latter point should not be underestimated: Different designs result in

different effect sizes, which have to be transformed into common effect sizes, which in turn can introduce bias. Concerning the first point, it is important to note that disagreements were mostly solved through discussions. Moreover, when we conducted meta-analyses for the different raters, the overall effects did not differ, despite differences in individual effects. This result, however, has to be treated with caution as studies were not randomly assigned to these raters.

An issue related to varying designs that lowered the interrater agreement was the ambiguity of the goals and their respective operationalization as manipulation and DV. This ambiguity is problematic from a more theoretical perspective because it might imply that the theory is not specific enough. This will be illustrated by looking at achievement goals here, but could really be demonstrated with other goals as well. Achievement goals were used several times to demonstrate the GC effect, but the manipulations and outcome variables were treated differently by different authors (i.e., concepts instead of studies were replicated, see Chambers, 2017), which makes it difficult to conclude that achievement goals generally show or do not show a GC effect. For instance, Leander and Shah (2013, Study 3a) had participants read about a student who had either an immediate or distant deadline for a semester paper (manipulation), which led subjects to work with higher or lower persistence on anagram tasks, respectively (DV): the closer deadline exerted a larger GC effect. Tobin, Greenaway, McCulloch and Crittall (2015, Study 1) used a similar manipulation but had participants write an essay and its quality was assessed by different raters as DV. In both examples, the original authors argued that the behavioral outcome measure

was indicative of an achievement goal being activated. In other examples, the manipulation materials also differed (e.g., Dik & Aarts, 2007 and Brohmer et al., 2018). It has to be emphasized that a high degree of ambiguity of conceptually similar studies was the rule rather than the exception. And this ambiguity was fueled even further by differences of control groups and additional interacting variables.

Given this variety, it is even more interesting that only moderate heterogeneity across studies was found. In light of this, two interpretations are possible: either, the corrected summary GC effect across studies that we extracted is so clear that it truly represents an existing effect, or the summary GC effect is no more than an artifact of consistently selective reporting in the literature, independent of the designs. The strong evidence for publication bias for both the extracted effects and the originally hypothesized effects (see supplementary materials) along with the drop in estimated between-study variance after the publication-bias correction rather indicate the latter.

Certainly, we do not intend to dismiss individual studies or even the theory on goal contagion as a whole. In fact, goal contagion remains an elegant approach to explain how people can become inspired by their peers, which needs to be explored further. However, similar to other topics of social psychology (e.g., Friese, Frankenbach, Job, & Loschelder, 2017; O'Donnell et al., 2018; Simmons & Simonsohn, 2017), goal contagion also suffers from many early studies that showed unreasonably large effects with low sample sizes. Future studies should avoid these pitfalls of low power, which increase both false-negative and false-positive findings.

Furthermore, the theory in its current state seems to be underspecified, despite 15 years of research. There are many examples for this underspecification: for instance, it is not clear whether measuring the accessibility of a goal concept already suffices to say that a goal inference took place, whether goal inference could be or needs to be on an implicit level or whether a successful GC process should manifest itself in goal pursuit only or in behavioral intentions likewise. One reason for this underspecification lies potentially in a body of research without close replications and where new studies almost always introduced changes in the research designs. Changes in research designs to identify the boundaries of a theory are, of course, important for the development of a theory. But they become problematic when the empirical basis for extended designs is uncertain and thin (see Chambers, 2017, Chapter 3). Moreover, some changes in the research designs of published studies did not correspond well to the original theory, which does not allow for more nuanced conclusions.

As a starting point for future research on goal contagion, we think that it is necessary to assume very small GC effects of standardized mean differences of around 0.15, based on the publication bias methods for the confirmatory and extended analyses. This, of course, corresponds to sample sizes of at least 1102 participants (one-sided t -test, $1-\beta = .80$, α error probability = .05), which, in order to achieve, potentially requires collaborations between labs. Anything below this number does not seem to be reasonable, as the literature does not contain enough reliable information on designs that allow for much smaller sample sizes. Additionally, applying open science practices, such as data and material sharing and

preregistration, will become necessary so that researchers can learn from each other more efficiently.

Conclusion

GC is a social-cognitive approach to understand how observing others can affect our own goal-directed behavior. However, there are indications of publication bias within the published literature and most recent studies yielded effects clustering around zero. Potential moderators that could advance the theory on GC could not be identified in this meta-analysis, either. We strongly suggest applying open science practices and determining the required sample sizes on a power analysis in future research to bring goal contagion back on track.

Chapter 5

**Summary of this Research on
Goal Contagion and
Future Directions**

A brief summary

To test the theoretical process of goal contagion that we have outlined in the first chapter, we conducted three studies using prosocial goals (inferred from helping behavior) and three studies using the goal to earn money (inferred from working behavior in a supermarket that only indicates the goal to earn money). Moreover, we conducted eight more studies in our lab with alternative goals employing various paradigms with different dependent and independent measures, which also fit our definition of goal contagion. These effects could be compared to the existing literature on goal contagion, which was effectively corrected for potential publication bias.

Across these six reported studies, the additionally studies conducted in our lab, and all published studies that met the theoretical goal-contagion criteria, the evidence for the existence of the goal contagion effect is marginal at best: Whereas overall the studies showed a small to medium effect initially (in terms of standardized mean differences), several bias-corrections revealed that the effect might be less than half the size and therefore tiny and hardly distinguishable from zero. This result was similar for both implicit inference and goal pursuit as dependent measures. Moreover, cumulated evidence from our own studies does not speak in favor of the effect, either: there were only nonsignificant effects found that mainly clustered around zero. And this was also true for goal inference and goal pursuit.

In this last section, I want to shed some light on the wider issues of goal contagion research and discuss them in the

context of alternative explanations and other research in the goal domain.

Issues with conventional inference measures

In Chapter 3 we discussed why we think our goal inference measures did not work as expected. These measures are based on popular techniques in social cognition research to detect an implicit activation of constructs or goals. These techniques usually entail some sort of veiling of their actual purpose in paradigms like the lexical decision task, word completion task or dot-probe tasks (among others). For instance, in the lexical decision task, participants are told to quickly decide whether a word string is an actual word or a non-word. However, the actual purpose is to record their supposedly quicker reaction times towards words that are related to the prime (or goal) compared to other words, implying a successful activation of the construct (or inference of a goal).

We have utilized all of these measures and none has yielded effects in the context of our research on goal contagion, which is in stark contrast to the published literature (see Chapter 4). As this literature seems to be biased in favor of statistically significant results, I suggest a thorough examination as to whether these measures should be used in the future to detect an inference or activation of goals. This could be achieved, for instance, in a multi-lab collaboration that tests these implicit measures all together and potentially with varying operationalizations (see Many Labs; Klein et al., 2018).

No goal pursuit, no mediation

Of course, underlying cognitive mechanisms are of interest, but, ultimately, effects should show in detectable behavioral patterns. Moreover, if implicit measures for these cognitive processes are flawed, one could still argue that behavioral measures might then be more reliable and can inform future applications and usage of one's research (Cialdini, 2019). Unfortunately, the behavioral results for goal pursuit that we obtained are, effect-wise, no different from the ones of the implicit measures.

From a theoretical point of view, one could critically ask whether our measures of goal pursuit are also indicative for activation and adoption of the goals that we intended to elicit. For instance, maybe our prosocial helping measures in Chapter 2 (e.g., helping out in another experiment) could have been too far removed from the casual helping depicted in the video clips. That is, maybe participants did not see this kind of helping in an experimental context as a means to fulfill the goal that they inferred. This could also indicate that the transition from inference over a goal activation in the observer to actual behavior is more complex in reality.

As is also described in Chapter 4, results for the subgroup of published studies for behavioral outcome variables that would indicate goal pursuit were almost identical to the previous findings and, again, even closer to zero for our studies. This circumstance raises at least three issues that future research has to address, which concern the meaningfulness of the effect at hand, a lack of evidence for a mediation (in regard

to the original model) and the implied potential of a theoretical and statistical underspecification.

First, the behavioral summary effect across studies could be interpreted as tiny at best, which is in line with several other social-cognitive effects (see Miles, Nind, & Macae, 2010; Eerland, Guadalupe, & Zwaan, 2011; Kramer, Guillory, & Hancock, 2014; Vohs, 2018) and raises the question about how meaningful this effect could be. After all, a standardized mean difference close to 0.1 equates to a probability of 53% that a random participant from the experimental group would score higher on the dependent variable than a random participant from the control group (Magnusson, 2020). This is barely more than a chance effect of a coin toss and not something that is noticeable in real life behaviors. Additionally, even this effect might be overestimated (and its variation is likely simultaneously underestimated) in lab experiments, which do not control for random effects as they occur in real life (Yarkoni, 2019; see also Lakens, 2020).

Second, comparing the effect from observation to pursuit and the effect from observation to implicit inference, one can see that neither effect is distinguishable in our main study in Chapter 3. But if the complete theoretical mechanism also implies a transition from inference to behavior (i.e., a mediation), there would not be much variance left that the path between inference and behavior and, hence, the complete indirect effect could account for, assuming that there actually is a zero-order effect of the manipulation on goal pursuit. More evidence for a mediation would be required, but unfortunately, only one other paper (Jia et al., 2014) has investigated the

indirect effect in its entirety.¹² While we (Corcoran et al., 2019, see Chapter 3) found no effects, either for the individual paths on goal pursuit ($\zeta \leq 0.62, p \geq 0.534$), or for the indirect effect ($\zeta = 0.62, p = 0.534$) in a large sample ($N = 300$), Jia and colleagues found a slight mediation effect (based on $\zeta = 2.66, p = .008$) with only a few participants ($n \sim 75$ in the relevant condition, inferred from an overall $N = 150$), but did not report the direct effect on goal pursuit. Based on these two mixed results, no conclusion can be drawn as to whether a transition via inference towards a behavioral effect could really occur.

Third, it is possible that other variables may be at work, which suppress the goal contagion effect either in its zero-order form or throughout the mediation process. Identifying and including these variables could lead to a boost for the indirect effect from observation over goal inference to goal pursuit in theory and statistically. This, of course, would render the current mediation model underspecified as it does not yet incorporate all relevant variables (see Meule, 2019). But one could rightfully ask, which variables should really account for these kinds of effects? To our understanding, the original theory does not contain any other factors of interest. Nonetheless, we will discuss some potential candidates from the related literature in the next section.

¹² Dik and Aarts (2007) only reported individual paths but not the indirect effect.

Potential alternative explanations: goal shielding, vicarious goal satiation and goal slippage

Some alternative effects could work against the goal contagion effect. They either need to be accounted for in the model to make goal contagion visible or even make a point against the concept of goal contagion. Rather than looking merely at context and disposition-related moderators (see also Chapter 4), I want to focus on these three candidates that may be relevant for the goal itself to be elicited: goal shielding, vicarious goal satiation and goal slippage.

One might argue that the activation of a goal in an observer through, for instance, goal contagion, should lead the observer to also pursue this goal if the contextual factors allow her to do so. As we alluded to in Chapter 1, it is also possible that other goals might be more prevalent because they are most urgent in that moment. For instance, if one tries to catch the train in the morning, it is not beneficial to get distracted by a coffee machine along the way, even though one likes to drink coffee in the morning. Catching the train has priority, and hence, this goal shields against other goals (Shah et al., 2002).

In the context of goal contagion, goal shielding could be a crucial factor but has hardly ever been (for one exception see Leander, Shah, & Chartrand, 2011). It is conceivable that participants hold goals that are more important to them than the goal that is elicited in the study. For instance, students may want to complete the study for partial course credit and do not care about the specific content of the texts that contain the goal manipulation, which could introduce systematic errors in experiments that aim to elicit goal pursuit, due to goal

shielding. However, it might not only be the participants' own goal (vs. a goal that should be elicited in the study), which may counteract the purpose of goal contagion.

A related issue comes in the form of vicarious goal satiation, which states that not only the own goals of participants can affect their response to goal manipulations, but also the goals of others – particularly when others fulfill the goal that they pursue (McCulloch et al., 2011). This might be especially relevant for the development of manipulation materials: If one attempts to depict a certain goal-directed behavior of another person, vicarious goal satiation suggests that it is not beneficial to show this person accomplishing her or his goal, but rather showing that the goal is “in progress.” Once the goal is accomplished, it is satiated for the observer and, hence, does not need to be pursued any further, leading to its deactivation on an implicit level.

Although this satiation effect works well in theory, it has to be noted that several goal manipulations in the literature either do yield effects later, even though the goal was accomplished to some degree (e.g., Jia et al., 2014), or depict goals that are ambiguous and do not contain a specific point of completion (e.g. Chen & Latham, 2014). Therefore, vicarious goal satiation may have effects for certain goals, but not for others, but could be relevant either way for the goal contagion effect.

In the same vein it is not clear either whether an observed person's failure to accomplish a goal could have an effect on its potential to be contagious. Thus far, only Lee and Shapiro (2015) have investigated this question in the context of a dieting goal, but without a proper control group. They found no significant difference in terms of an activation of that goal

between when participants saw someone else pursuing this goal (without accomplishing it) or failed to achieve this goal.

However, speculating on similar effects for other goals would be problematic, as a dieting goal is different from most other goals in the literature on many dimensions. Whereas dieting is a self-serving goal that is contrary to other self-serving goals (e.g., eating food, see Zhou et al., 2017) and requires long-term self-commitment and willpower to show visible effects, other goals are not self-serving (e.g., casual helping) or produce more directly visible outcomes (e.g., money). Again, more research is needed to exclude relevant moderating effects on failures to achieve a goal.

Finally, recent social-cognitive research in the field of developmental psychology offers new insights on how people align their goals in collaborative endeavors, which is based on a common understanding of a joint goal through shared intentionality (Tomasello, 2019, Chapter 3). In other words, a mutual understanding of at least two agents that they intend to pursue a goal through collaborative action to a mutual benefit is a requirement. As this kind of thinking has evolved to a large extent in human beings throughout the millennia, it is possible that additional mechanisms may have come along with it. Indeed, one specific mechanism was proposed by Michael and Székely (2019) as an alternative to goal contagion: goal slippage.

Goal contagion, as well as other models that rely on the goal system theory, are based on the idea that goals guide the behavior of people. Importantly, this also counts for goals that are conventionally primed or for goals of others that are accurately inferred. Michael and Székely (2019) argue that this

“rich” understanding of goals generates empirically predictions that are likely false: it assumes that the observer has a representation of the goal, which the observed person pursues, as her (the observer’s) own goal.

Goal slippage provides the alternative “lean” goal explanation that is more in line with empirical findings: The observation of goal-directed behavior activates the representation of the goal or outcome that has to be brought about for the observed person. For instance, infants who see an experimenter struggling to pick up a pencil beyond reach, do not want to reach the pencil for themselves (as predicted by goal contagion), but rather accomplish the goal that the experimenter has, by helping him/her to get the pencil (as predicted by goal slippage).

This theoretical approach can inform our understanding of why goal contagion might not reliably work in experiments. If we expect goals to be caught through mere observation, we assume that people misattribute others’ goals sufficiently often and imply that they cannot link this inferred goal to the observed person (the “carrier” of the goal) accurately. If future research accounts for this circumstance, which is likely in line with humans’ evolved cognitive architecture, the general expectations about the size of goal contagion effect probably need to be adjusted.

It has to be noted that none of the previously described theoretical approaches is sufficiently supported by empirical evidence to make a clear suggestion of what has to be done to make goal contagion “work.” Rather, I intended to outline potential explanations for why the most recent experiments on goal contagion have shaken my confidence in whether this

effect is measurable in actuality. However, there may be some other, not theory-related, issues when looking at the statistical properties in the meta-analysis.

Not much between-study heterogeneity and low precision

Not only does goal contagion suffer from a lack specificity in theoretical terms, but also from little heterogeneity in statistical terms. Where the former can be addressed by incorporating alternative theoretical approaches into one's research, the latter might illustrate the limits of such an idea.

Between-study heterogeneity is a blessing and a curse at the same time: It is a blessing as it can illuminate whether there may be moderators at work that individual studies cannot account for. It is also a curse as bias-correction (such as in publication bias) will become less precise with higher heterogeneity. In the case of goal contagion, the picture is more pronounced as the studies that we incorporated in Chapter 4 have one clear source of heterogeneity, which is related to publication bias: there was low to moderate heterogeneity across all studies, which is in line with what one would expect from research in psychology (Olsson-Collentine, Wicherts, & van Assen, 2019). However, this heterogeneity vanished when we looked at published studies and unpublished studies (including our own studies and studies from another registered report) separately.

Also, by looking at the forest plots again (Figure 13), one can see that about half of the published studies have relatively similar effects of $0.4 < d < 0.7$, with confidence intervals

ranging close to zero or crossing it only at the edge, which indicates that authors might have focused a lot on reporting marginally significant effects (Olsson-Collentine, van Assen, & Hartgerink, 2019). The other effects from the published literature are much larger $0.7 < d < 1.5$, but have even broader confidence intervals, which also approach zero.

Overall, these observations indicate a wider issue with goal contagion effects: Looking for certain moderators could be a tedious endeavor when there is nothing that could be moderated in any way. However, a large proportion of the published literature yielded too imprecise estimates to make a qualified statement on moderators. A gleam of hope might be that the above-mentioned theoretical approaches may suppress the goal contagion effect and that it could come into being once one controls for these effects statistically. But this will require more systematic groundwork first.

Future steps: back to the drawing board!

From this point on, there are three paths that one can forge. At least two of them differ greatly in the theoretical and methodological understanding of goal contagion compared to what my collaborators and I have tested throughout the last four years.

The first option was hinted at in Chapter 4. One could continue testing the original effect, but should keep in mind that more than 1000 participants per study would be required as there is simply not enough reliable empirical evidence to assume larger goal contagion effects (and, hence, a smaller sample size).

The second option would be to abandon the original goal contagion model and refocus on effects that do not rely on pure observation of others only but complement them with interactive settings. This approach would not be new in the context of goal contagion as two articles have already explored dyadic and group interactions among participants (Palomares, 2013; Laurin et al., 2016). As these kinds of setups contained interpersonal and group dynamics, which are different from classic experimental designs and which did not rely much on implicit inferences either, they could not be considered in our meta-analysis. Also, these tested interactive settings used different paradigms, which makes them hardly comparable in theoretical terms and which leads me to the final point.

A third, in my opinion most preferable option, is to theoretically identify relevant boundary conditions and potentially suppressing factors of the goal contagion effect to achieve more refinement in the theory. We presented theoretical approaches such as goal slippage that may be at least as plausible as goal contagion and need to be considered before new experiments in this domain should be designed. In this regard, it would be equally necessary to not rely solely on basic understandings of quick and automatic inferences, but also to take newer findings into account (e.g., on associative networks, see Amodio, 2018) that may not have found their way into the general knowledge of social cognition yet.

No matter which path future research on goal contagion may take, it will be necessary to conduct this research as openly and transparently as possible (Nosek et al., 2015). Only by this, can we facilitate our understanding of goal contagion-related

effects in particular and social-cognitive processes in general in a meaningful and reliable way.

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¹³ An asterisk “*” indicates articles coded for the meta-analysis

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